

Training Spatial Skills with the Online Platform RIF: Development, Evaluation and Enhancement of the Learning Experience

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Abstract

This thesis focuses on examining different aspects related to spatial thinking training in the context of the online platform RIF. This platform offers more than 1500 tasks for primary, secondary and tertiary education learners to train their spatial skills costless. The studies are divided into four topics: (1) development and evaluation of tasks; (2) evaluation of the RIF platform; (3) effects of using different types of representations in mental rotation tasks; and (4) the impact of animated feedback in spatial thinking training using the RIF platform.

The first part stems from the need of designing online spatial tasks for the RIF platform that are suitable for primary school children, in order to enhance their spatial skills and lay the foundations for more difficult and spatial specific types of tasks. After the development of more than 167 tasks for the area *visualization*, they were evaluated, first by an expert group, and later by two external assessments conducted in Spain and Austria respectively. In the first external assessment participated 96 pupils from 10 to 13 years old (50 females and 46 males). Participants' results and students' and teachers' feedback revealed some aspects to improve, which were implemented for the second external evaluation. In this phase, outcomes of 795 participants (387 females, 371 males and 38 other) from 7 to 13 years old were analysed. This led to the adaptation and elimination of some tasks that were not suitable for the task groups. Additionally, for the improvement of the platform and its accessibility, a color blindness check was created, along with the translation of the platform into Spanish.

The second part consisted of the evaluation of the performance of the RIF platform participants (N = 41664; 18056 females and 23608 males) between the ages of 7 and over 21. We examined the results of 50 tasks groups of the nine areas of spatial thinking found in the platform considering age and gender, in order to establish whether there are differences in performance between genders in any of the areas and age groups. Results revealed that outcomes generally improved with age until the age of 21, when they start to decline. Regarding gender differences,

there are three principal findings: males tend to outperform females until the age of 18; from that age onwards females outperform males; and mental rotation is the area with the largest gender differences favouring males.

Regarding the third study, findings of the previous part revealed that mental rotation was the area with largest gender differences between the ages of 10 to 18. Therefore, it was analysed whether using more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks would improve students' outcomes and reduce gender differences. For this purpose, three additional types of representations to the classic one used in the platform were designed, namely grey-shaded, colored and rendered. Results from 1077 students (476 females and 601 males) from 10 to 18 suggest that including more realistic representations, (e.g., rendered images) in mental rotation tasks can have positive outcomes for learners and can reduce or eliminate gender differences in performance. Even when gender differences persist, both females and males demonstrate significant improvements compared to classic representations.

Finally, the last study focuses on enhancing the learning process with the RIF platform as a computer-based learning environment with feedback. Animated feedback in the form of videos was created to examine its impact in students' outcomes, taking into consideration gender as a moderator. 179 students (88 females and 91 males) between 10 and 14 years old were divided into the control group (no feedback) or the experimental group (feedback). Although no significant effects were found, it was observed that feedback does influence students' confidence and enjoyment, especially among girls.

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Prologue

Back home in Cádiz, every February cities from the province dress in colours and costumes to celebrate carnival. One of the most beautiful traditions is a singing contest that date back to the XV century, in which different types of songs are written with undertones of social and political critique. Some days ago, I listened to one of these, sung by a group of primary school children, in which they claimed that doing things “like a girl” has traditionally been used as an insult to boys, while girls are brave, intelligent and capable.

And it made me think about why I do what I do.

From a very young age, we, women, hear, see, and feel, that science is for boys. We are told that boys are good at maths, and we are good at art. We only learn about the inventions and discoveries of men; we only learn about Einstein, Newton, Darwin or Tesla; and we only see men’s names in theories and equations. Just Marie Curie and with luck a few others appear in our books. We decide not to follow some scientific or technical career because we don’t know if we can, and if we do, we always feel like we don’t belong because there is just a few of us and our abilities are constantly questioned.

With this thesis, I wanted to humbly contribute to this issue in a way that supports girls’ learning path, so that they feel encouraged and prepared to pursue any path they want, whether it is science or not, but at least, giving them the chance.

“Science is not a boy's game, it's not a girl's game. It's everyone's game. It's about where we are and where we're going.” -Nichelle Nichols

Table of Contents

Abstract	i
Acknowledgements	iii
Prologue	iv
Introduction	1
Theoretical Framework	7
Chapter 1: Spatial Thinking	8
Introduction	8
Spatial Thinking Skills Trainability.....	10
The Four Perspectives of Spatial Thinking	11
Developmental Psychology	12
Visual Perception	18
Factor-Analytic Models	20
Neurology	30
The RIF Platform.....	31
Current Study.....	32
Chapter 2: Mental Rotation and Gender Differences	33
Introduction	33
Research on Types of Stimuli	36
Current Study.....	41
Chapter 3: Formative Assessment	42
Introduction	42
Feedback Characteristics	43
Feedback Type	43
Feedback Timing.....	44
Feedback Levels.....	45
Computer-Based Assessments	46
Feedback Animations	48
Feedback and Gender	49
Current Study.....	49
Section Summary.....	50
Empirical Studies	51
Introduction	52
Chapter 4: Development and Evaluation of Tasks	55
Introduction	55
Development of the Tasks	55

Evaluation of the Tasks.....	58
First External Evaluation	58
Second external evaluation	68
Conclusion.....	71
Color Blindness	72
Spanish Translation.....	73
General Conclusions of the Chapter.....	74
Chapter 5: Evaluation of the Platform.....	75
Introduction	75
Research Questions and Hypothesis.....	75
Method.....	76
Design	76
Participants.....	76
Instruments.....	77
Data analysis	77
Results	78
Age group 1 (7 to 9 years old)	78
Age group 2 (10 to 12 years old)	80
Age group 3 (13 to 15 years old)	82
Age group 4 (16 to 18 years old)	84
Age group 5 (19 to 21 years old)	85
Age group 6 (+21 years old)	87
Total number of participants	88
Results in each area across age groups by gender	90
Results per area	92
Discussion.....	100
Implications	102
Chapter 6: Effects of Using Different Types of Representations in Mental Rotation Tasks	105
Introduction	105
Research Questions and Research Hypothesis	105
Method.....	107
Design	107
Participants.....	108
Instruments.....	108
Tasks development.....	112

Data analysis	112
Results	114
Total number of participants	114
Age group 1 (10-12 years old).....	117
Age group 2 (13-14 years old).....	120
Age group 3 (15-16 years old).....	123
Age group 4 (17-18 years old).....	126
Differences between age groups	128
Preferences for types of representation.....	134
Discussion.....	137
Implications	141
Chapter 7: The Impact of Animated Feedback in Spatial Thinking Training Using the RIF Platform.....	143
Introduction	143
Research Questions and Hypothesis.....	143
Method.....	145
Design	145
Participants.....	146
Instruments.....	146
Feedback development.....	149
Procedure	150
Data analysis	151
Results	153
Feedback effects.....	153
Impact on gender.....	154
Feedback effects in participants in the quartile 1.....	155
Impact on gender in participants in the quartile 1.....	156
Questionnaires.....	156
Discussion.....	164
Implications	168
General Conclusions	169
Conclusions of Chapter 4: Development and Evaluation of Tasks	169
Conclusions of Chapter 5: Evaluation of the RIF Platform.....	170
Conclusions of Chapter 6: Effects of Using Different Types of Representations in Mental Rotation Tasks	171

Conclusions of Chapter 7: The Impact of Animated Feedback in Spatial Thinking Training Using the RIF Platform.....	172
References	173
List of tables.....	192
List of Figures	195
Annexes	198
Annex 1.....	198
Annex 2.....	201
Annex 3.....	205
Annex 4.....	206
Annex 5.....	213
Annex 6.....	228
Annex 7.....	228
Annex 8.....	229
Annex 9.....	229

Introduction

STEM education (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) has become in the last years an important and ubiquitous topic across the world, as it is considered a fundamental element for national development, economic productivity, and societal well-being (Tytler, 2020). Moreover, it has the potential of addressing twenty-first century challenges such as climate change, reduction of biodiversity, energy efficiency, space explorations, clean water or emerging and re-emerging of infectious diseases, among others (Bybee, 2018).

However, the percentage of graduates in tertiary education in STEM in Europe is minoritarian, making up 21.9 % of the total percentage in 2021 (Eurostat, 2023). These figures have been stable during the past five years, with small variations since 2016 (Fondazione Deloitte, 2022). According to a study conducted by Fondazione Deloitte (2022), reasons for these low numbers stem from lack of guidance and support, preconceptions, biases and stereotypes about STEM. Generally, STEM subjects are perceived as more difficult than non-STEM subjects and suitable only for some people (Fondazione Deloitte, 2022). In addition, the gender gap in this area is also a matter of concern: in 2021 women constituted 32.8 % of the total graduates in STEM fields in Europe (Eurostat, 2024). This leads to a significant weakness in EU's economy and women's well-being, as this situation:

[...] reinforces the undervaluation of women's work and leads to their higher poverty and lower economic independence. The fact that employment growth stems from the creation of quality jobs for men but not so much for women needs to be recognised and dealt with by a much wider circle of stakeholders (Langbakk, 2017).

The European Institute for Gender Equality (2017) suggests several factors as causes for this imbalance. For instance, girls are less likely than boys to see STEM as a career choice due to its traditional association with stereotypically masculine traits. Moreover, individual factors, such as the toys they used to play with, family relations (e.g., a strong bond with fathers

increases women's likelihood to enter STEM studies), media impact or the counselling received in schools can also influence when choosing a career path.

Given the stated significance of scientific and technological knowledge in our society, it seems necessary to address these issues from an educational perspective. Though efforts to encourage students to enter the STEM field have been focused on topics such as interest in STEM, sense of belonging in STEM fields or self-efficacy in learning STEM, cognitive factors such as the spatial ability levels of students have been relatively less acknowledged (Zhu et al, 2023), albeit they are considered to be a strong predictor for success in STEM areas (Wai, Lubinski & Benbow, 2009).

Despite the fact that it has been continuously discussed about the “nature or nurture” element of spatial skills, evidence suggests that they can be trained and improved through practice (Uttal et al., 2013). Moreover, this instruction should start in the early childhood in order to have the greatest outcomes in the future (Newcombe and Frick, 2010). It is therefore fundamental for parents, teachers and educational trainers in general to have access to quality materials that meet these needs, providing a spatial training that prepares students for their future and that do not perpetuate traditional gender biases and stereotypes.

In 2019, experts from the University of Salzburg and other educational institutions in Austria created the online platform RIF 2.0, with the purpose of providing free materials that were accessible to everyone regardless of their socio-economic status to train their spatial skills. The more than 700 tasks were directed to students over 12 years old. Due to its success, a newer version of the platform, RIF 3.0, has been developed, additionally offering tasks for learners between 7 and 12 years old. It was accomplished with the support of the SellSTEM project, which aims at enhancing children's spatial skills in order to increase STEM enrolment and reduce gender imbalance.

In this context, the present dissertation attempts to contribute to the challenge of developing and improving children's spatial skills by creating suitable online materials that promote their training and equally support learners regardless of their gender. Specifically, it deals with four main topics. The first two are related to the development of the RIF platform and include (1) the design and assessment of tasks for children aged 7 to 12; and (2) the evaluation of participants' performance in the platform tasks. The other two concern the improvement of the platform by addressing the topics (3) gender differences in mental rotation tasks; and (4) supporting learning with the platform by providing detailed feedback.

The first study, *Development and Evaluation of Tasks*, corresponds to the creation phase of the dissertation. In it, the process of designing and assessing the tasks that will lately be included in the platform is detailed.

The second study, *Evaluation of the Platform*, focuses on examining participants' performance in the platform in the nine areas of spatial thinking that are trained (i.e., visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space, spatial visualization, mental rotation, spatial relations, and spatial orientation). It aims at answering the following research questions:

1. How do participants perform in each area of spatial thinking trained in the RIF platform?

1.1. How do participants perform in each area per age group?

2. Are there differences in the performance of females and males in any of the nine areas of spatial thinking trained in the RIF platform?

2.1. If so, in which area(s)?

2.2 If so, in which age group(s)?

The third study, *Effects of Using Different Types of Representations in Mental Rotation Tasks*, concentrates on the improvement of participants' outcomes in mental rotations tasks and the

gender differences usually found in this area of spatial abilities. It intends to address them by examining the effects of employing more realistic types of representations. The following research questions will guide this study:

1. Does the use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks help to improve students' outcomes?

1.1. Do they have a different effect in females' and males' outcomes?

1.2. Does the use of more realistic types of representations in tasks similar to the ones in the MRT-Test help improve students' outcomes?

2. Can the use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks decrease or eliminate gender differences?

2.1. Can gender differences be reduced or eliminated in the tasks similar to the MRT-Test when using more realistic types of representations?

3. Which type of representation do girls and boys prefer?

3.1. Is there a link between preference for type of representation and performance in the assessment instrument?

The fourth study, *The Impact of Animated Feedback in Spatial Thinking Training Using the RIF Platform*, aims at enhancing participants' experience and learning outcomes when practicing with the platform, considering it is embedded in an online context and feedback can be used as a way to interact with learners and help them in the learning process. Therefore, our purpose is to answer the following questions with this study:

1. Does immediate elaborated feedback (videos) have a positive effect on students' learning outcomes in online spatial thinking tasks?

1.1. Do low-skilled students benefit more from feedback?

1.2. Which condition (feedback or no-feedback) is more beneficial for girls and for boys?

2. Does feedback have an impact on students' confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks?

2.1. Are there differences between girls and boys on confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks?

This dissertation is organized in two sections. The first section deals with the theoretical background, divided into three chapters. In chapter 1, literature relevant to spatial thinking is reviewed. Its definition, relation to STEM, trainability and history of spatial thinking research is covered, to finish with the presentation of the spatial thinking training online platform RIF. Chapter 2 deals with the literature related to mental rotation. We revise the types of tests that are usually used to assess mental rotation and the gender differences found in them. Chapter 3 delves into the literature pertinent to formative feedback, reporting the different characteristics of feedback that have an impact in its effect, and focusing on computer-based assessments and animated feedback. These three chapters on literature review set the base of the following chapters, in which the experimental studies are carried out.

The second section corresponds to the empirical studies and is divided into four chapters. In chapter 4, the development and evaluation of tasks for the RIF platform is described. In this phase, we created numerous tasks for primary school students for different areas of spatial thinking. These tasks were then evaluated using the results of users of the platform, which led to their improvement. Moreover, the creation of a color-blindness check and the translation of the platform into Spanish is also addressed. Chapter 5 reports the evaluation of the RIF platform. Results of 41664 participants are analysed to assess their performance in each area of spatial thinking trained in the platform. Results are presented by age groups and gender to examine whether there are gender differences in any of the areas and age groups. Based on the

results of chapter 5 that show gender differences in mental rotation tasks, chapter 6 focuses on exploring the effects of using different types of representations in mental rotation tasks to improve students' outcomes and reduce gender differences. Also linked to the outcomes on chapter 5, in chapter 7, we aim at enhancing the learning process when practicing with spatial tasks in a computer-based environment, where there is little to no interaction between the instructor and students. Therefore, in this chapter the impact of animated feedback in spatial thinking online training is analysed.

Theoretical Framework

Chapter 1: Spatial Thinking

Introduction

Spatial thinking is one of the most essential elements of human cognition. It influences every aspect of our lives, from navigating our environment to understanding complex scientific concepts. It is based on our natural ability to perceive, interpret, and manipulate spatial information and constitutes a fundamental framework for understanding the relationships between objects, places, and concepts in the world around us.

Spatial thinking is an umbrella term that contains a wide range of mental skills, such as spatial perception, spatial ability, visual perception, or spatial intelligence, and can be defined as:

the human ability to direct optical stimuli received by the eye into the brain, to be able to interpret these stimuli, to be able to recognize spatial objects, to be able to mentally imagine spatial objects (with or without prior optical stimuli), to be able to manipulate these objects mentally, to be able to imagine taking other perspectives in space, to be able to perceive and interpret motion sequences, and to be able to execute spatial motor movements. (Maresch & Sorby, 2021, p. 274).

Historically, spatial thinking skills were immensely valuable (e.g., for hunting, gathering, sailing, etc.). In today's society, with the introduction of numerous technological systems, such as the GPS, and 3-D programs for construction and design, among others, this ability has become indispensable to be able to navigate in a more data-based and visual environment (Montello et al., 2014). This necessity, therefore, does not only arise for everyday life but also for educational and professional purposes. Research suggests a strong correlation between spatial thinking skills and success in the STEM areas (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), which are essential for economic growth, innovation and welfare (Davies and Horst, 2016; Freeman et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2023). Numerous studies have reported the links

between spatial thinking in STEM learning in the areas of math (e.g., Cheng & Mix, 2014), biology (e.g., Rochford, 1985), physics (e.g., Kozhevnikov et al., 2007), engineering (e.g., Sorby, 2009), chemistry (e.g., Stieff et al., 2012), computer programming (e.g., Jones & Burnett, 2008), design (e.g., Lin, 2016) and medical studies (e.g., Hegarty et al., 2007). Moreover, as previously mentioned, Wai, Lubinski and Benbow (2009), carried out a longitudinal study, in which they tested the spatial skills of over 400000 high school students and followed their trajectory eleven years after graduating. Results showed that 45 % of those with a PhD in a STEM field were in the top 4 % on the spatial ability tests eleven years before and nearly 90 % were in the top 12 % or above. Even if the underlying reasons for this correlation are still unclear, Montello and colleagues promote research on the topic by stating that:

Spatial learning in educational and everyday settings is important because it holds the promise of improving spatial thinking, which in turn holds the promise of contributing to a host of desirable outcomes, including generating economic development, making more user-friendly and functional technology, fostering equitable access to employment, and generally helping people realize their potential. To the extent that these claims are valid, there is little doubt that spatial concepts, thinking, and learning are quite important and worthy of our attention as academics, researchers, and educators (Montello et al., 2014).

However, the STEM field still deals with a major issue: a significant gender gap that gives boys an advantage over girls. The 2015 PISA data sheds some light on this, revealing two key facts: while males generally scored higher in math and science, females excelled in reading. Additionally, boys showed more confidence and interest in learning science. Consequently, girls are less likely to pursue a career in STEM, which leads to women having fewer promising career prospects and typically earning lower salaries than their male counterparts (Kahn & Ginther, 2017; Ruthsatz et al., 2012), creating social, educational, and economical imbalance. Moreover,

there are several examples of issues in the scientific, medical and technological fields that are consequence of a lack of women's talent, perspectives and experiences, such as higher women's mortality in car accidents due to security systems being tried in smaller male dummies (Criado Pérez, 2020); or the higher risk of women of dying of a cardiac arrest because the commonly known symptoms are those affecting men (Ketepe-Arachi & Sharma, 2017). It is therefore essential to support young girls in science, encouraging them and providing them with the training they need. Due to the link between STEM success and spatial abilities, one way of achieving this is by providing an appropriate spatial skills training, that sets a base of knowledge and abilities to later pursue a STEM career.

Nevertheless, this ability is not itself absent of gender differences favouring men over women. Historically, researchers have found small or insignificant gender differences for most areas of spatial ability, with the exception of mental rotation (Bartlett & Camba, 2023). In fact, it is considered to be the “cognitive ability with the largest documented sex difference in favor of men” (Hegarty, 2018, p. 1212). This topic will be dealt with in detail in chapter 2.

Spatial Thinking Skills Trainability

One question that arises when dealing with this topic is whether spatial skills are innate or if they can be trained and improved over time. While there is evidence to suggest that some individuals may have a genetic predisposition to high spatial skills (Bednarz & Lee, 2011), research indicates that these skills are indeed trainable through targeted practice and experience (Maresch & Sorby, 2021).

Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of specific training programs and interventions in enhancing spatial thinking abilities across different age groups. These programs often involve activities such as solving spatial puzzles, playing spatially-oriented video games, engaging in hands-on construction tasks, or participating in virtual reality simulations (Uttal et al., 2013; Terlecki et al., 2008; Feng et al., 2007; Jirout & Newcombe, 2015; Kucian et al.,

2011). However, many researchers discuss whether the improvements are substantial and durable. For instance, Uttal & Cohen (2012) consider three potential limitations of spatial training programs effects, specifically for STEM learning:

- Non-transferability to other experiences: gains in an area of spatial thinking do not necessarily convey gains in other contexts, which might mean a narrow improvement in STEM.
- Duration of the training: many studies are implemented in laboratory settings and do not last more than a few hours. The results of these short interventions might not endure outside of that setting.
- Validity of the training: the improvement in the spatial tasks might not be caused by the training per se, but by the effect of taking the test several times.

It is hence essential to design spatial training programs that acknowledge these issues and aim at enhancing spatial thinking as an intricate ability compound by several aspects, that have an appropriate length, which can lead to sustainable gains, and that ensures that the training and evaluation instruments avoid the improvement by the effect of repetition. Moreover, it is necessary to do it in a way that addresses the gender differences found in literature, so that they do not create gender biases, increasing the differences or, ideally, are designed incorporating features that reduce or eliminate them.

The Four Perspectives of Spatial Thinking

Since Galton (1879) published one of the first verifiable works on spatial ability (Maresch et al., 2023) a large number of contributions have been made to the field. In the following section, we are going to examine four different perspectives of spatial thinking research, based on four disciplinary areas that have handled spatial thinking from diverse traditions and with diverse purposes (Maresch & Sorby, 2021). These four perspectives are: developmental psychology, visual perception, factor-analytic models and neurology.

Developmental Psychology

Developmental psychology is the study of human physical, cognitive, social, intellectual, perceptual, personal and emotional growth throughout life and it is essential to understand how humans learn, mature and adapt (American Psychological Association, 2014). Therefore, concerning spatial thinking, it deals with how it develops over a person's lifetime (Maresch & Sorby, 2021). During the 20th century, several psychologists proposed different theories for cognitive and intelligence development, in which spatial thinking was either indirectly embedded or considered a central element. Although there are a number of theories that have had a great repercussion in education, such as Vygotsky's, Bloom's or Skinner's, in this work we are going to focus on those that have a direct relation with spatial thinking. The models developed by Piaget (1952), the van Hiele researcher couple (1986), Bruner (1960), Thurstone (1937) and Stückrath (1963) are described in detail below.

- **Piaget - Stages of Cognitive Development Theory.** Piaget's theory was focused on the role of biological maturation in children's ability to understand and interact with the world (Oogarah-Pratap et al., 2020). He argued that we build our knowledge actively, using what we already know, adapting it to new experiences. His work was based on how children's cognitive development takes place and how it changes their thoughts and abilities to navigate the world while growing (Saldarriaga-Zambrano, 2016). As a result, he divided the cognitive development into four stages ranging from birth to adulthood (Linares, 2007; Piaget, 1952; Piaget & Inhelder, 1984; Saldarriaga-Zambrano et al., 2016): (1) Sensorimotor stage; (2) Preoperational stage; (3) Concrete operational stage; and (4) Formal operational stage. In order to reach fully developed human intelligence, we have to go through each stage.
 - ***Sensorimotor stage (0-2 years old).*** This stage begins with the birth of the child and lasts approximately until they start speaking. During this stage, children develop their

reflexes and senses through their experiences with their environment. These lead to the awareness of objects beyond our own bodies and the development of intentional movements and conduct. A key milestone at this stage is the realization that objects remain existent even when we cannot see them, in Piaget's words "object permanence" (also known as working memory).

- ***Preoperational stage (2-7 years old)***. The symbolic function emerges, which allows children to mentally represent ideas and objects that are not present at the time, as they can now use and understand gestures, words, numbers and images. They use intuitive reasoning, as they still do not have the ability to think logically. Another limitation of the preoperational stage is the focus on one aspect of the stimuli. This explains their incapacity to understand the idea of conservation (i.e. a quantity does not change if it is altered), so if we pour the water from a wide glass into a tall, narrow glass, they are going to think that the tall one has more water.
- ***Concrete operational stage (7-11 years old)***. At this stage, logical thinking is achieved, which allows children to perform concrete cognitive operations, such as sorting objects in a certain order and understanding reversible actions. Inductive reasoning is also possible now, so they can draw conclusions about concrete ideas and generalize. Finally, they can grasp the concept of conservation.
- ***Formal operational stage (12 years old-adulthood)***. During this stage, formal intelligence is developed. Children can think rationally about abstract concepts and ideas, make hypotheses and use deductive reasoning. They can extract logical conclusions from the relationship between two premises (propositional logic) and address problems by applying scientific reasoning. This stage is in constant development throughout life.
- **Van Hiele - Model of Geometric Thinking**. Dina van Hiele-Geldof and Pierre van Hiele developed a theory explaining how children learn geometry. After teaching mathematics for

several years, they realized that many students had trouble with this area and even though they changed their teaching methods, the difficulties remained. Therefore, they introduced their theory on the process of developing geometric and spatial thinking, which later served as a basis for geometry curricula and education standards throughout the world (Vojkuvkova, 2012). The rationale behind this was to know at what level of thinking the learner is, in order to teach contents that are appropriate for their cognitive developmental stage and in a way in which they can make use of geometry as fast as possible (Van Hiele, 1986). In their theory, they describe five consecutive levels (labels may vary): (0) Visualization; (1) Analysis; (2) Abstraction; (3) Deduction; and (4) Rigor (Crowley, 1987; Mason, 2021; Vargas & Araya, 2013; Van Hiele, 1986; Vojkuvkova, 2012).

- **Level 0: Visualization.** At this level, pupils can recognize figures by their appearance as a whole, not seeing individual parts. They usually compare them with familiar objects of their close environment and can reproduce them. However, they cannot identify or explain their properties. For example, they know that a triangle is a triangle because it *looks* like a triangle, but they do not know what a triangle is.
- **Level 1: Analysis.** Pupils can now identify the components and properties of geometric figures, through experimentation and manipulation. Although they can recognize figures by their properties, they do not relate or classify them, so they do not know which ones are necessary or sufficient to describe the object. For example, they recognize that triangles have three sides.
- **Level 2: Abstraction (informal deduction).** At this level, learners understand the relationships between properties and figures. They distinguish different classes of figures and can make meaningful definitions based on their necessary attributes. For instance, they know that triangles have three sides and therefore, the sum of their angles is always going to be 180° . This stage is based on manipulative and empiric experiences, so they still cannot comprehend axioms and make more formal logical deductions.

- **Level 3: Deduction.** Learners can now give deductive and logical proofs. They can get to the same results even when starting with different premises. They understand the role of definitions, axioms, theorems and proofs. For example, at this stage they can use the Pythagoras' Theorem to establish the relationship between the three sides of a right-angled triangle. However, they do not acknowledge the importance of rigor when reasoning.
- **Level 4: Rigor.** This level is acquired in university-level mathematics. It involves a high level of understanding formal aspects of deduction, such as establishing and comparing mathematical systems, and mastering Euclidean and non-Euclidean geometry.
- **Bruner - Model of Learning.** In the 1960s, Bruner (1960) claimed in his book *The Process of Education* that “We begin with the hypothesis that any subject can be taught effectively in some intellectually honest form to any child at any stage of development” (1960, p. 33). This was the ground for the notion “spiral curriculum”, which, in other words, states that even difficult knowledge can be explained to young children if fragmented and introduced appropriately. Therefore, learners revisit the same topic multiple times during their school period; however, its complexity is increased each time. He divided the human cognition process into three stages: *Enactive*, *Iconic* and *Symbolic*, giving name to the EIS-Theory. These stages go from concrete to abstract and are developed successively with age, however, when learning new material, it is likely to go back to simpler stages and progress from there (Rannikmäe et al., 2020).
 - **Enaction stage.** According to Bruner, the first approach to learning is with hands-on activities. Children learn with physical actions. For example, to understand the concept of subtractions ($4 - 2 = 2$), they will put four fingers up and then put two down or take four pencils and take away two.
 - **Iconic stage.** At this stage, children are able to make iconic representations that derive from their experiences. That means, they recognize images and can think using them.

For instance, to do the same math operation ($4 - 2 = 2$), they can draw four apples and visualize that if they take two away, they still would have two left.

- ***Symbolic stage.*** In the symbolic stage, language, mathematical symbols and other symbol systems are used to learn, understand and represent ideas, thoughts and knowledge. Using the same example, children now can answer the mathematical problem using the mathematical expression “ $4 - 2 = 2$ ”.
- **Thurstone - Primary Mental Abilities Theory.** In the first half of the 20th century, Thurstone developed a model, where he described seven intelligence attributes or mental abilities in order to understand human intelligence. Namely verbal comprehension, word fluency, number facility, spatial visualization, associative memory, perceptual speed and reasoning (Beaujean & Benson, 2019; Thurstone, 1937, Thurstone, 1946).
 - ***Verbal comprehension.*** It is the ability to understand verbal information. It includes several aspects, such as vocabulary, verbal reasoning, semantics, syntax or pragmatics.
 - ***Word fluency.*** In contrast to the previous one, this factor is related to the production of language. One example of a task could be to write a list for a certain topic.
 - ***Number facility.*** It refers to the facility of doing simple numerical calculations, such as addition, subtraction, multiplication and division.
 - ***Spatial visualization.*** It concerns the ability to visualize figures in both 2D and 3D. According to Thurstone, we can find differences in the readiness of people to visualize, which will have implications for their education and employment choices. For instance, he specifies that an individual with poor spatial visualization will not enjoy descriptive geometry and similar subjects (Thurstone, 1946).
 - ***Associative memory.*** It involves the ability to memorize and retain information, which has a great influence on other factors discussed, such as verbal comprehension, word fluency or number facility.

- **Perceptual speed.** It includes the skills of spotting mistakes, discarding unnecessary information and finding patterns, similarities and differences.
- **Reasoning (or induction).** It describes the capacity to discover the rules, principles and relationships of the information one is working with.
- **Stückerath – Stage Theory of Spatial Orientation.** At the end of the 20th century, Stückerath (1955) studied how spatial orientation was developed and proposed a theory based on four moments founded on the recognition and interaction of a child with the world around them: the *Leibraum* (body space), *Ichraum* (ego space), *Handlungsraum* (action space) and *Laufraum* (walking space) (Hutsteiner, 2011; Ragger, 2018; Stückerath, 1955).
 - **Leibraum (Body space).** The *Leibraum* concerns the first spatial experiences in the life of a child. It starts with the discovery of the own body (primarily by the introduction of the hand in the mouth) and is followed by the ability to look at things beyond the own body and direct the hands towards objects that are away from it.
 - **Ichraum (Ego space).** With the beginning of the capacity to move (crawl, walk, run) the existing space goes now beyond the own body and extends to the world outside of it. During this process, children learn the concept of position (outside/inside, left/right). Space reaches as far as the child's actions do.
 - **Handlungsraum (Action space).** In the *Handlungsraum* there are three stages that take place. In the first one, the child has a holistic comprehension of figures and objects. In the second one, they recognize different types of forms, their relationships and their place in space. Finally, in the third stage they start understanding the geometric characteristics of figures, such as width, length, angles, etc.
 - **Laufraum (walking space).** Within this level, the child develops the ability to remember and imagine a route to orientate. In the first phase, they can only visualize places where they have been. In the second, they can rebuild the route. It is in the third

phase, when they can finally remember all the information about the place and the path, so they can reverse it or even find a shortcut.

Although all these theories date back several decades, they have provided a solid base for further research and have improved our understanding of humans' cognitive development. More specifically, the notions of spatial thinking being a specific factor within intelligence, in constant evolution since birth, and necessary for developing other abilities, give consistent arguments to consider it crucial for the proper development of individuals.

Visual Perception

Visual perception is the ability to see, process and understand the visual information that is retrieved from the environment. It involves a sensory function (or visual-receptive component), which corresponds to the extraction and organization of the information, and a specific mental function (or visual-cognitive component), which organizes and deciphers the visual stimuli (Schneck, 2013). This skill allows us to identify objects, shapes, colors, light, size and spatial relations between objects.

- **The Visual-Receptive Field.** The visual-receptive field is a region in the visual field in which a visual cell responds to visual stimuli (Lindeberg, 2013). This field is composed of different elements, each of them responsible for a different function (Schneck, 2013).
 - **Visual fixation:** is the ability to maintain the gaze on a stationary object.
 - **Visual pursuit:** enables us to follow a moving object.
 - **Saccadic eye movements:** are rapid changes of focus from one point to another within the visual field.
 - **Acuity:** is the ability to see fine details of objects.
 - **Accommodation:** is the ability to adjust the sight to maintain a clear image of an object as it moves.

- **Binocular fusion:** is the ability to mentally combine the visual information from both eyes into a single one.
- **Stereopsis:** is the perception of depth and three-dimensionality that results from the disparity between the images received by each eye.
- **Convergence and divergence:** are the movements of both eyes inward to focus on a near object, or outward to focus on a distant one.
- **The Visual-Cognitive Field.** The visual-cognitive field is the area of the visual field in control of the mental processes that provide the visual stimuli with meaning. It has four components (Schneck, 2013):
 - **Visual attention** is the ability to focus and select information out of the visual stimuli. It comprises: alertness, selective attention, visual vigilance, and divided or shared attention.
 - **Visual memory** is the ability to encode, store and retrieve visual information, integrating it with previous memories and experiences. It includes various types of memories, such as working memory, short-term memory, and long-term memory.
 - **Visual discrimination** is the ability to distinguish objects according to their features, which involves recognizing, matching, and categorizing different characteristics, such as shape, color, size, pattern or texture.
 - **Visual imagery or visualization** is the ability to mentally represent or reproduce visual stimuli without physically seeing them.

Visual perception is a preliminary stage of spatial ability as it involves the anatomical and basal cognitive steps to recognize, match and store spatial objects in the memory that will then be necessary to reason with and manipulate spatial objects purely mentally (Maresch & Sorby, 2021).

With the aim of assisting children with learning difficulties caused by visual perception disturbances, Frostig and Horne (1964) created a model of visual perception skills, along with a test (Developmental Test of Visual Perception) that included five sub-areas: eye-motor coordination, form-constancy, position in space, spatial relation, and figure-ground perception.

Factor-Analytic Models

The study of spatial ability has undergone a historical development that can be differentiated into three phases. First, the pre-factorial phase (1904-1950), in which many researchers focused on the study of intelligence. Second, the factorial phase (1950-1994), when after having established spatial ability as an essential aspect of intelligence, researchers concentrated on determining the individual factors that compose it. Finally, the post-factorial phase (1994-present), is characterised by the desire to understand the mental processes involved, such as the strategies used to solve spatial ability tasks or working memory, and to develop more suitable models.

Pre-Factorial Phase (1904-1950). During the pre-factorial phase, the study of intelligence gained popularity, resulting in an extensive body of literature that, for the first time, provided definitions, descriptions and models (Maresch, 2013). In the beginning, intelligence was perceived as a broad and general aspect that did not discern into different dimensions, as demonstrated by some early definitions of intelligence:

- Stern (1912) considered intelligence as the general ability of an individual to consciously adjust their thinking to new challenges and adapt to new tasks and conditions in life.
- Binet (Binet & Simon, 1905) defined intelligence based on the individuals' judgement, common sense and adaptability.

With these foundations, later researchers started to deepen the examination of intelligence, developing models that identified and specified different elements.

- Spearman (1904) proposed the Two-Factor Theory of Intelligence, where he divided intelligence into (g), general intelligence; and (s), specific intelligence. (G) is the general mental ability that underlies all cognitive tasks. According to Spearman, that indicated that being intelligent in one area would likely mean being intelligent in other areas as well. On the other hand, (s) refers to the specific abilities needed for particular tasks, which cause individual differences in performance on those specific tasks.
- Thurstone (1937) considered that intelligence was not a single factor, but a combination of seven primary mental abilities: verbal comprehension, word fluency, number facility, spatial visualization, associative memory, perceptual speed and inductive reasoning.
- The Cattell-Horn-Carroll (CHC) theory integrates the theoretical models of fluid and crystallized intelligence (Cattell, 1943, 1963) and the three-stratum theory (Carroll, 1993). The basic principle of this theory is that intelligence is multidimensional and functionally integrated (Schneider & McGrew, 2018). The dimensions of ability have a hierarchical structure divided into three strata: at the top, the most general level of intelligence that only includes one factor: g (general intelligence). The second stratum contains the broad abilities, that include fluid reasoning, comprehension knowledge, short-term memory, visual processing, auditory processing, long-term storage retrieval, processing speed, reading and writing and quantitative knowledge, among others (McGrew, 2009). The last stratum corresponds to the specific cognitive skills that are connected to each of the abilities in the second stratum, for example, for the broad ability *reading and writing*, some necessary narrow abilities are spelling ability, writing ability, reading speed, etc. (McGrew, 2009).
- Guilford (1967) designed a multidimensional framework that tried to reflect the diverse nature of human intelligence. He considered three dimensions, which combined lead to 120 factors of intelligence (5 x 4 x 6):

- The operation dimension refers to the intellectual processes. Factors: memory, divergent production, convergent production and evaluation.
- The content dimension refers to the areas of information in which the operations are applied. Factors: figural, symbolic, semantic or behavioural.
- The product dimension refers to the results of applying an operation on a content. Factors: unit, class, relation, system, transformation and implication.
- Gardner (1991) identifies seven original factors of intelligence, to which later added two more:
 - Linguistic intelligence: proficiency with language.
 - Logical-mathematical intelligence: logical reasoning, problem-solving and mathematical skills.
 - Spatial intelligence: ability to think in 3-D space, visualize and navigate the physical world.
 - Musical intelligence: sensitivity to pitch, melody, rhythm and other aspects of music.
 - Bodily-Kinesthetics intelligence: physical coordination and control of the own body.
 - Interpersonal intelligence: ability to understand and interact with others.
 - Intrapersonal intelligence: self-awareness and understanding of one's own internal world.
 - Naturalistic intelligence: understanding of and interacting with the natural world.
 - Existential intelligence: contemplating philosophical and existential questions.

Factorial Phase (1950-1994). Despite the differences between these models of intelligence, most of them have in common that they consider, to some extent, spatial ability as an area of intelligence. That is why, during the factorial phase, research was focused on dissecting spatial ability to identify and describe its own individual factors. Several researchers, such as Lohman (1993), Maier (1994) or Thurnstone (1946), among others, made important

contributions to the topic. Examining the existing literature of this period, there are five factors that have consistently been recognized as aspects of spatial ability: visualization, spatial relations, spatial orientation, spatial perception and mental rotation (Maresch, 2013).

- Visualization: cognitive ability to construct mental images of objects and manipulate them (rotating, folding, transforming, moving, etc.). Classical task examples include paper folding or objects divided into several parts and rotated (Hegarty, 2010).
- Spatial relations: ability to understand the arrangement of elements within a visual image, mainly with reference to the human body (Michael, Zimmerman & Guilford, 1950, as cited in Maier, 1994).
- Spatial orientation: ability to understand spatial relations in which the body orientation of the observer is essential to the problem (Thurnstone, 1951, as cited in Maier, 1994).
- Spatial perception: ability to determine spatial relationships between objects with respect to the orientation of their own bodies (Linn & Petersen, 1985).
- Mental rotation: refers to the cognitive process of mentally rotating or manipulating mental representations of objects or spatial configurations. It involves the ability to mentally transform and manipulate visual or spatial information to understand the relationships between objects from different perspectives (Shepard & Metzler, 1971; Cooper & Shepard, 1973).

Post-Factorial Phase (1994-present). Despite researchers' attempts to establish one consistent model of spatial ability, it was an unsuccessful aim due to mainly two causes: the impossibility of giving a specific definition of each factor and research results on spatial ability varying widely (Maresch, 2014). This led to a shift in the focus of spatial ability research: First, more attention was paid to the strategies used to solve spatial ability tasks; and second, different models were created to compile the different factors and characteristics of spatial ability.

Strategies in spatial ability. As possible explanations for the differing results on spatial ability tasks, Lohman (1979) suggests that (1) different persons might apply different strategies to solve the same task; and that (2) the same person might apply different strategies for different tasks. Therefore, research on spatial ability started to focus on identifying and describing the solution strategies used (Maresch, 2014).

Following, we are going to describe four pairs of solution strategies that are generally used in spatial ability tasks (Figure 1). These are not independent of one another and the preference for any of them is given by the following parameters (Maresch, 2014): intrapersonal preference, size of the individual repertoire of strategies, type of task, level of difficulty of the task, and experience in solving similar or related tasks.

Figure 1

The four pairs of strategies for the solution of spatial ability tasks (Maresch, 2014, p. 128)

Holistic strategy – analytical strategy

Barrat (1953) made a distinction in solving spatial problems between “whole approach” and “part approach”, which are now referred to as holistic and analytical strategies. The use of a holistic strategy involves looking at the whole picture without focusing on individual details.

This approach is especially useful in recognizing patterns, shapes, and relationships between objects. On the other hand, analytical strategies suggest the examination of the individual components of an image within a spatial context. This approach includes actions such as, comparing an object (or part) with possible solutions, applying analytical-verbal description or logical consequential thinking (Maresch, 2014).

Spatial thinking – planar thinking

People who use spatial thinking strategies create a three-dimensional model of the image in their minds, being able to mentally manipulate it (rotating, folding, cutting, etc.). On the contrary, using planar thinking does not involve a three-dimensional representation of the setting, but manipulating a two-dimensional picture of it, which considerably reduces the difficulty of the task (Maier, 1994; Maresch, 2014).

Move object – move self

In this case, the focus is on the position of the person solving the task. If they position themselves as observers of the setting, they are outside of it and can move the individual objects, whereas if they position themselves inside the setting, they are the ones who can mentally move around the setting (Maresch, 2014).

Verifying strategy – falsifying strategy

Lüthje (2010) identified the verifying and falsifying strategies as two further approaches for solving spatial tasks. The first implies actively looking for the correct answer, whereas the second involves identifying the correct options and excluding them until finding the right one (Maresch, 2014).

Models of spatial ability. Deriving from the factor analysis of spatial thinking, several models emerged to organize them and allow to categorize tasks according to the aims and characteristics. Current models follow a minimalist (Newcombe & Shipley, 2015), maximalist (Buckley et al., 2018) or cross-domain (Maresch, 2020) structure.

Minimalist model

Newcombe and Shipley (2015) designed a minimalistic model based on linguistic, cognitive and neuroscientific investigations (Uttal et al., 2013). It makes use of two essential distinctions: intrinsic and extrinsic information and static and dynamic tasks. First, intrinsic information is the conventional aspects usually considered to define an object, while extrinsic information deals with the relationships between objects within a group, considering their relative positions to each other or their connection to a general framework. For instance, distinguishing between a triangle and a square would require intrinsic information, and recognizing if one is on the left to the other would require extrinsic information. Second, as their names indicate, static tasks are those that present fixed objects or whose solutions do not require movement, whereas dynamic tasks involve objects that can move or be moved. When considering the combination of the two dimensions, we obtain a 2 x 2 classification of spatial skills (see Figure 2) (Newcombe & Shipley, 2015; Uttal et al., 2013):

- Intrinsic-Static: recognizing objects, paths or spatial configurations over distracting background information.
- Intrinsic-Dynamic: putting together objects into more complex configurations, mentally visualize, transform and rotate objects.
- Extrinsic-Static: understanding abstract spatial principles, such as left, right, horizontal, vertical, etc.
- Extrinsic-Dynamic: visualizing spatial information in its entirety from different perspectives.

Figure 2

2 x 2 classification of spatial skills (Newcombe, 2020)

Maximalist model

Buckley and colleagues (Buckley et al., 2018) propose an extension of the CHC theory, including a total of 25 factors that can be divided into two areas of spatial ability: static spatial factors or dynamic spatial factors. Within static spatial factors we can find:

Table 1

Factors of spatial ability according to Buckley and colleagues (Buckley et al., 2018)

Static Spatial Factors	Dynamic Spatial Factors
Visualization	Dynamic Visual Memory
Spatial Orientation	Directional Judgement
Length estimation	Dynamic Serial Perceptual Integration
Static Visual Memory	Speed Judgment
Closure speed	Dynamic Spatial Scanning
Flexibility of closure	Movement Detection
Shape and Direction Illusions	Dynamic Perceptual Alternations
Static Serial Perceptual Integration	
Spatial Relations	
Speeded rotation	

Size Contrast Illusions

Static Spatial Scanning

Imagery Quality

Imagery Speed

Overestimation Illusions

Underestimation Illusions

Frame of Reference Illusion

Static Perceptual Alternations

Cross-domain model

Maresch (2020) developed a holistic model with the aim of merging the four perspectives of spatial thinking described above (i.e., developmental psychology, visual perception, factor-analysis and neurology). The model of the basic practices of spatial thinking (original name:

Modell der Groundroutinen des räumlichen Denkens und Handelns) is structured in eight stages (see Figure 3) (Maresch, 2020):

- Visualization: ability to filter and focus on relevant facets of an image.
- Form constancy: ability to recognise objects by their characteristics; ability to draw similar objects; ability to describe the characteristics of objects.
- Position in space: ability to recognise relative positions of objects to each other; ability to actively position relative positions of objects to each other.
- Transformation in space: ability to recognise the relationship between the source object and the target object; ability to create spatial transformations.

- Object combination: ability to recognise and create supplementary parts, object sections and Boolean operations.
- Dynamics: ability to track moving objects when the observer is stationary; ability to anticipate the course of movement.
- Motor skills: eye-hand coordination.
- Spatial orientation: ability to imagine scenes from other positions; ability to estimate positions and distances from and to objects when moving in real environments.

Figure 3

The eight basic practices of spatial thinking (Maresch, 2020)

The first five stages (i.e., visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combination) are conceived as successive stages. Children and adolescents usually develop these stages gradually, starting with visualization (Maresch & Sorby, 2021). The other three stages (i.e., dynamics, motor skills and spatial orientation) are rather independent of the first five stages and develop at an individual pace (Maresch, 2020). Besides providing the eight stages of spatial thinking development, the model intends to orient learners at all developmental stages, helping them assess the extent of their spatial thinking skills (Maresch & Sorby, 2021).

In addition, Maresch (2015) also adapted the model of spatial ability of Maier (1994), which originally consisted of five factors, namely visualization, spatial perception, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation. However, as other authors consider that spatial perception can be integrated in the factor spatial orientation (Thurstone, 1950, as cited in Maresch, 2015), Maresch does not recognize it as a discrete factor. Moreover, from now on, the factor visualization will be named as spatial visualization, in order to differentiate it from the one mentioned before. That way, this model finally includes: spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation.

Neurology

Until the invention of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in 1971 by Lauterbur, research on the brain aimed at understanding its functioning was essentially impossible. Since that, functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and other imaging techniques have been developed, which allow observing the internal structures of the brain in a non-invasive way (Maresch & Sorby, 2021). Since then, researchers have focused on comprehending the brain, its development, connections, and pathways.

Before the 1970s, the concept “mind’s eye” was used to describe the notion of mentally creating an image. However, it was discarded by psychologists for being too subjective, and replaced by research on the topic of mental imagery, which established that the same of the cortical areas activated by visual stimuli are also activated in imagery (Farah, 2000). In other words, the same areas of the brain are activated when we look at an object and when we think about it.

In relation to spatial perspective and spatial orientation, in 2005, Moser, Moser and O’Keefe (2014) discovered a type of neuron that fires in a grid-like pattern, creating cognitive maps of space, which allow animals to navigate their surroundings. Moreover, they are also responsible for path integration, which helps to keep track of location and orientation relative to a starting

point. Their study revolutionized the understanding of spatial cognition and memory, which gained them a Nobel prize in 2014.

The RIF Platform

With the purpose of training spatial thinking skills in a computer-based environment, experts from the University of Salzburg in collaboration with other universities of Austria, created in 2019 the online platform RIF 2.0 (Maresch & Müller-Kreutzer, 2021). RIF 2.0 (from the German “*RaumIntelligenzFörderung*”) offered more than 700 interactive tasks for participants aged 13 and over, and in the lapse of less than two years, more than 45000 users used the platform [date of the data: 02.06.2022]. Given its success, a newer version of the platform, RIF 3.0, (www.rif4you.eu) has been developed with the support of the European Union within the framework of the SellSTEM project (MSCA Project No. 956124). Now, the more than 60000 learners [date of the data: 15.02.2024] from the age of seven can find more than 1500 tasks in German, English and Spanish. All the materials in this website can be used freely by anyone, both independently and in the context of the classroom.

Following, we present the nine different areas of spatial thinking that can be trained with the platform. The first five areas were created following the first basic practices of spatial thinking (Maresch, 2020), while the four last, the model of spatial ability of Maier (1994) adapted by Maresch (2015).

- Visualization: Ability to filter and focus on relevant facets of visual information.
- Form constancy: Ability to recognize objects based on their characteristics.
- Position in space: Ability to recognize relative positions of objects to each other.
- Transformation in space: Ability to recognize the relationship between source object(s) and target object(s) when moving in space.
- Object combination: Ability to recognize object intersections and Boolean operations.
- Spatial visualization: Ability to recognize spatial objects in different spatial situations.

- Mental Rotation: Ability to rotate spatial objects purely mentally.
- Spatial relations: Ability to recognize relationships between spatial (partial) objects.
- Spatial orientation: Ability to imagine spatial scenes from other positions.

Current Study

In chapter 4 of this dissertation, the process of development of spatial tasks for the area visualization for the RIF platform is described. As explained in previous sections, training spatial abilities is crucial for its improvement, especially if it starts from a young age. Therefore, creating tasks adapted for the cognitive stage of children is necessary. This chapter details the processes of preparation, development, evaluation and final establishment of the tasks. Moreover, it reports the design of a color-blindness check instrument to inform users of a possible presence of this condition that can affect their performance. Finally, we also illustrate the translation of process of the platform into Spanish.

In chapter 5, an in-depth evaluation of the RIF platform is conducted, in which the results of participants in the nine areas are analysed by age group and gender. This is aimed at assessing participants' performance and the presence of gender differences in the nine areas.

Chapter 2: Mental Rotation and Gender Differences

Introduction

Mental rotation is a cognitive process that involves imagining a spatial object and mentally rotating it, visualizing it from different angles or orientations. It is defined as the “ability to rotate a two- or three-dimensional figure rapidly and accurately” (Linn & Petersen, 1985, p. 1483). This ability allows us to navigate the world, solve puzzles and analyse complex structures.

Generally, two types of mental rotation tests are used to assess this skill: the Vandenberg and Kuse psychometric test (1978) and the Shepard and Metzler chronometric test (1971). The Vandenberg and Kuse Test, later redrawn by Peters et al. (1995), counts with 24 items divided in two sets of 12 items each. Each item consists of an exemplary figure, and four possible answers from which two are correct and two incorrect. The correct answers are identical to the example in a rotated position. The Shepard and Metzler test includes 16 pairs of figures. Each pair includes a target figure and a comparison figure. Participants are asked to determine whether the comparison figure is the same as the target or if it is a rotated version of it.

Gender differences in mental rotation favouring males have been widely addressed (Moè et al., 2018), and are often considered one of the largest in cognitive psychology (Voyer et al., 1995). Even though there is extensive research on the topic, the underlying causes of these gender differences are still not clear. Several theories have tried to explain them, pointing to biological factors, such as brain activation, sex hormones or puberty (Pezaris & Casey, 1991; Titzte et al., 2010; Levine et al., 2016); while others have focused on psycho-social causes, such as gender stereotypes (Moè, 2012), educational aspects (i.e., preferences of toys, parents’ language use) (Moè, 2012; Newcombe, 2020) or strategy selection to solve the tasks (Hegarty, 2018). However, none of these theories provide conclusive evidence for gender differences. As Jost and Jansen (2023) indicate, all the research focused on studying gender differences were based

on the Vandenberg and Kuse test (1978) (from now on VK), which usually produces gender differences. Nonetheless, studies on chronometric tests based on the Shepard and Metzler test (1971) (from now on SM) do not generally show these results. This suggests that these differences might not be related to mental rotation skills, but to the characteristics of the tests, which Jost and Jansen (2023) divide into two categories: differences between the individual trials of each test, and differences of the tests design. In terms of the differences between the individual trials of both tests, in contrast to participants in the VK, are informed that half the possible answers are correct. Moreover, the trials have different number of alternatives. Regarding the differences between mental rotation tests, they identify 8 characteristics (Jost & Jansen, 2023):

- Ending condition/time limits: while the VK test is limited by time (6 min.) and number of trials (two times 3 min for 12 trials), the SM is only limited by the number of trials. Research found that by extending or eliminating time limits in VK test, gender differences were reduced, but not eradicated (Peters, 2005).
- Stimulus material: VK and SM tests use similar stimuli, that are abstract cube figures. It has been examined whether different types of stimuli could diminish gender differences. For VK tests, studies have focused on using human figures (e.g., Jansen & Lehmann, 2013), female stereotyped stimuli (e.g., Ruthsatz, et al., 2014, 2017), and realistic three-dimensional objects (Fisher et al., 2018; Robert & Chevrier, 2003). In all these cases gender differences were still present but reduced. In the case of the realistic three-dimensional objects, even though gender differences were reduced, in the study of Robert and Chevrier males solved the tasks faster than females and in the study of Fisher et al., results indicated possible ceiling effects. This will be discussed in a following section. For SM tests, results are mixed. When using human figures, Voyer and Jansen (2016) found that men performed better than women, while Campbell et al. (2018) detected better performance of women.

Jansen-Osmann and Heil (2007) compared several types of stimuli and found gender differences only for two-dimensional polygons, while Heil and Jansen-Osmann (2008), trying to replicate these results found differences for complex polygons. However, expect for the polygons, all gender differences found in SM tests are small.

- Rotational axis: the VK test only uses in depth rotations, while the SM test combines in depth and rotations in the picture plane. Results on whether the rotational axis affects gender differences in VK tests are inconclusive, as Ruthsatz et al. (2014) found larger differences in children's results when figures were rotated in depth compared to picture plane rotations, whereas Battista and Peters (2010) concluded that gender did not interact with this variable in adults. In SM tests, rotations in depth show no or small gender differences (Rahe et al., 2019).
- Type of distractors: SM tests use mirrored items as distractors in the possible solutions, whereas VK tests also uses structurally different items. Several studies have found mostly no significant effects of distractors on gender differences in VK tests (e.g. Boone & Hegarty, 2017; Doyle & Voyer, 2013; Voyer & Hou, 2006).
- Test administration: the VK test was originally designed as a paper and pencil test, whereas SM is computerised, which allow to measure reaction time. Currently, there are several online versions of VK tests, which, although report better performance of males, effect sizes are sometimes reduced in comparison to the paper and pencil test (Peters et al., 2007, Voyer et al., 2020). In the case of the SM, Titze et al. (2010) found larger gender differences in performance in a paper and pencil version.
- Participant organization: while the VK test was designed to test large groups, the SM was designed as an individual testing. This can be related to Moè's (2018) hypothesis of group composition and stereotypes influencing performance, however, Peters et al. (2006) concluded that there were no differences in group or individual testing.

- Scoring system: the VK test uses a scoring system in which they award one point to a trial if only both correct alternatives are selected (two out of four options). The SM test includes the reaction time and accuracy as measurements. This means that the scores of both tests are not directly comparable.
- Practice trials and feedback: VK tests usually use three or four practice trials, while there is no standard for SM tests. There is no systematic investigation on gender differences related to practice trials. In the case of feedback, some studies have investigated the inclusion of feedback in SM tests. Rahe et al. (2019) found missing feedback as a possible moderator for gender differences, while Jansen-Osmann and Heil (2007) and Voyer and Jansen (2016) included feedback in all trials and found gender differences.

Jost and Jansen (2023) identify two additional aspects that might influence gender differences in mental rotation performance. First, they theorize that gender differences only emerge on tests that are sufficiently difficult. In the previously described characteristics, gender differences were sometimes reduced when using simpler stimuli, distractors that could be easier identified, when more time was available, or tests were online. However, gender differences were still present in VK tests but not or smaller ones appeared in SM tests. Second, they also consider trial design as a potential influence, referring to features of the tests such as the number of alternatives per trial, the number of simultaneously presented trials or the ways alternatives are presented. These aspects might affect the strategies used to solve the tasks, which might be, again, causing gender differences to emerge.

Research on Types of Stimuli

As stated above, several studies have focused on examining the role of types of stimuli in gender differences in mental rotation performance. Some researchers have investigated the influence of changing the types of objects, using more female-stereotyped figures (e.g., Rahe et al., 2021; Ruthsatz et al., 2017), while others have targeted the realism of the traditionally used cube

figures (Robert & Chevrier, 2003; Daxinger & Maresch, 2018; Fisher et al., 2018; Schilchegger and Maresch, 2018). In this section, we are going to focus on the latter.

Robert and Chevrier (2003) conducted a study with 60 men and 60 women between 20 and 30 years old, in which they used 18 items of the Vandenberg and Kuse (1978) Mental Rotation Test. They created three conditions: the visual/paper condition, in which they presented participants with a paper and pencil version of the test; the visual/object condition, where participants could see a real wooden representation of the figures that corresponded to the same figures, in the same order and orientation as in the visual/paper condition; and the haptic/object condition, where participants were presented with the same objects but they could only touch them and not see them (see Figure 4). The purpose of this study was to examine if any of the conditions was more effective than the others in improving participants' outcomes and to analyse what strategies they used to solve them. Results showed that both females' and males' accuracy was higher in the visual/object condition and lowest in the haptic/object and the difference between both genders was not significant. Regarding the strategies, females reported having used more often analytic strategies, such as verbally describing the objects or focusing on their key features. Robert and Chevrier concluded that both genders benefited to the same extent from seeing real objects as they accelerated the analysis of the configuration of the figures and the identification of the orientations their parts. Moreover, this condition facilitated the extraction of depth cues in contrast to the visual/paper condition. These outcomes, however, count with the limitation of the participants' sample, as the original 120 were divided into the three conditions, counting only with 20 participants per gender and condition (Jost & Jansen, 2023).

Figure 4

Materials for the visual/paper condition (left) and for the visual/object and haptic/object condition (right) (Robert & Chevrier, 2003)

In their study, Fisher et al. (2018) investigated the effect of five ways of representing stimuli. They hypothesized that more realistic types of stimuli would lead to reduce or eliminate gender differences. They carried out two studies. In the first one, 132 women and 107 men were sorted into a drawing condition (classic Vandenberg and Kuse paper and pencil test) or a photograph condition. For the latter, they created real wooden figures representing the ones in the Vandenberg & Kuse test and photographed them (see Figure 5). This study showed gender differences favouring males. However, while males performed better in the drawing condition than in the photograph condition, women's outcomes were equivalent across conditions. In the second study they tried to replicate these results, but they included three additional conditions: a mounted condition, in which participants could see the real wooden objects and not a paper representation; a blindfold condition, in which they could touch the objects but not see them; and a touch condition, in which they could see and touch the objects. Results revealed that males significantly outscored females in the drawing condition, but no gender differences were found in any other condition. The descriptive statistics showed that this was not caused by males declining in their performance, but women improving across conditions. They concluded that more realistic types of stimuli tend to reduce the sex differences found on the MRT. Moreover,

they discuss that the use of drawings, which are abstract and lack of features that are seen in real life (shadows, light, depth, etc.), might be hindering women from using their preferred strategies to solve the task. On the contrary, more realistic representations are more similar to life-like situations, which allow them to use real-world mental rotation skills. Even though results are promising, one limitation of this study is a possible ceiling effect, as participants' scores are close to the maximally achievable.

Figure 5

Photograph version of mental rotation stimuli (Fisher et al., 2018)

Slightly differing from these studies, Daxinger and Maresch (2018) examined the effects of three different types of representations of the figures in the Peters et al. test (1995) (which is based on the Vandenberg and Kuse MRT (1978)). They used three-dimensional constructions in an online setting. In addition to the traditional one used in the test, they created a color block model (each block of the figure was painted in a different color); and a realistic model that represented the figure in a rendered version simulating plastic to make it as close to reality as possible (see Figure 6). Their sample consisted of 36 students (18 females and 18 males) between 13 and 14 years old. Results revealed that students got the best outcomes with the

traditional version and the worst with the realistic model, however, differences are not significant. They also do not report significant gender differences in any of the types of representations. In terms of limitations, the authors discuss whether the realistic representation of the objects could have been improved by using other types of materials (wood or metal texture) or using photos of real objects. Moreover, the sample size is rather limited, as participants of both genders are below 20.

Figure 6

Classic model, color block model and realistic model used by Daxinger and Maresch (2018)

In this line of research, Schilchegger and Maresch (2018) analyzed the effect of three different types of representations in mental rotation tasks. The types of representations included a wire model, a color model and a model with concealed edges (see Figure 7). 65 students (34 males and 31 females) between 14 and 18 years old participated in the study. Results reveal that the total number of correct answers was higher when using the color model, which, in addition, was found the easier to interpret. Although no specific gender difference analysis was carried out, the authors report that significantly more males than females were able to solve more tasks correctly.

Figure 7

Wire model, color model and model with concealed edges used by Schilchegger and Maresch (2018)

Current Study

Literature reveals that the abstract representation of figures in mental rotation tests might be contributing to the gender differences found in performance. Though there is some literature on the effects of different types of representations, mainly realistic ones, on mental rotation performance and its influence in gender differences, research shows no clear results. Some of the main limitations of previous studies are a small sample size and possible ceiling effects. Therefore, in chapter 6 we report a study conducted to analyse the impact on students' outcomes in mental rotation tasks in the RIF platform of four different types of representations: a classic representation that resembles the one in the Vandenberg and Kuse MRT; a grey-shaded representation; a color block representation; and a rendered representation that simulates a photograph. Moreover, we aim at examining whether more realistic types of representations can reduce or eliminate the gender differences found in the classic version (see chapter 5).

Chapter 3: Formative Assessment

Introduction

Assessment in the context of education is a process through which teachers and students collect, evaluate and use evidence of student learning for several purposes, such as diagnosing students' strengths and weaknesses, monitoring their progress, assigning grades and providing feedback (McMillan, 2013). Scriven (1967) introduced the terms summative and formative assessments, which are identified by their purpose, timing and level of generalization sought by the items in the examination used to collect data for the evaluation (Bloom et al., 1971). On the one hand, summative assessment refers to the general evaluations used to grade students at the end of a term or course and has the purpose of determining students' overall achievement in a specific area of learning at a particular time (Bloom et al., 1971; Moss, 2013). Summative assessments can be used to make adjustments at different educational levels, as they "(a) allow for comparing learner performances across diverse populations on clearly defined educational objectives and standards; (b) provide reliable data that can be used for accountability purposes at various levels and for various stakeholders; and (c) can inform educational policy" (Shute & Rahimi, 2017, pp. 3). However, this approach is quite limited and cannot accurately represent what students are capable of, which leads to higher test anxiety among students and lower self-esteem in low achievers (Moss, 2013). On the other hand, formative assessment focuses on gathering evidence of students' performance and understanding during the learning process, with the purpose of identifying the parts that are not mastered yet to adapt the instruction to improve their learning (Bloom et al., 1971; Bennett, 2011; Schildkamp et al., 2020). Therefore, teachers integrate it daily in the classroom, using students' outcomes in activities, tasks or quizzes to redirect the class (Shute & Rahimi, 2017). In comparison to summative assessment, formative assessment is a student-centred approach, where learners are actively involved in their learning process, usually receiving feedback to help them self-regulate their learning

progress (Timmers et al., 2013; van der Kleij et al., 2012). In this study, we are going to focus on formative assessment, and more specifically in formative feedback.

Feedback is understood as information provided by an agent about students' performance (Hattie, 2010), with the aim of enhancing the learning process (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). Through formative feedback, students can not only identify and correct errors by developing more efficient strategies (Van der Kleij et al., 2015), but it also can have an influence on achievement because it is a motivating learning factor, as it reduces uncertainty about their performance on the tasks (Shute, 2008). However, some types of feedback, such as feedback directed to the self or one that produces cognitive interferences with the task, might hinder the learning process (Fyfe et al., 2015; Fyfe & Rittle-Johnson, 2015; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996). Causes for these heterogeneous results are found in students' characteristics, such as their prior knowledge and experiences, motivation or attitudes; in the types of tasks used (high-/low-order); and mainly, in the characteristics of the feedback provided, as the type of feedback and feedback timing.

Feedback Characteristics

Feedback Type

In her work, Shute (2008) carries out a thorough examination of formative feedback. One aspect on which the study is focused, is the types of feedback that can be used to provide students with information about their progress. Although the classification includes numerous categories (e.g., verification, correct response, try again, error flagging, elaborated, attribute isolation, topic contingent, etc.), research is generally concentrated in the categories *verification*, *correct response* and *elaboration*.

Verification feedback, usually referred to as *knowledge of response (KR)*, aims at confirming whether an answer is correct or incorrect (Shute, 2008) and its main purpose is to help students recall the correct facts (Van der Kleij, 2013). KR can benefit the learning process, as it can

reduce students' reliance on external validation and promote their reflection on the task and their strategies. However, it can be insufficient for difficult tasks or topics that might need further explanation. Moreover, if students lack motivation or ability to self-reflect on their performance, it can also be ineffective (Jaehnig & Miller, 2007; Van der Kleij et al., 2011, 2015).

Correct response feedback or *knowledge of correct response (KCR)* informs about the correct answer to the task in questions and can also include the KR. KCR can be valuable to reduce ambiguity when learners are incorrect, as puts the focus on the ideas to grasp. It can also be seen as a motivational reinforcement when the answer is correct. On the contrary, a constant exposure to the right answers might reduce students' willingness to make an effort to find it by themselves, as they know they are going to discover it later (Jaehnig & Miller, 2007; Van der Kleij et al., 2011, 2015).

Elaborated feedback (EF) gives further instructional information about the correct answer in different forms, such as strategic hints, cues, explanations or worked-out examples (Narciss et al., 2014; Shute, 2008). It is usually reported as more effective than KR or KCR, however, it should be concise as too much information could have the opposite effects, distracting students from processing their own thoughts (Maier et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2019) and increasing the cognitive load (Sweller, 1988). In addition, high-knowledge students might not benefit as much as low-knowledge students from feedback, which can be solved by allowing them to have more control over feedback, skipping it when not necessary (Fyfe, 2016).

Feedback Timing

Feedback timing refers to the moment of the learning process in which feedback is provided to students. Literature identifies two alternatives: immediate and delayed feedback (Shute, 2008). Although there is no clear definition for these terms, immediate feedback usually means getting information after each answer, while delayed feedback concerns a time lapse of at least one day. Researchers do not agree on what is the best time to give feedback. On the one hand, one line

of research considers delayed feedback as more beneficial, as it would not interfere with the delay retention effect (Kulhavy & Anderson, 1972). This states that the receiving the correct response too close in time to the incorrect response given, might hinder the learning of the correct one (Shute, 2008). Moreover, delayed feedback might be more effective for easy tasks and high-ability learners (Attali & Van der Kleij, 2017). On the other hand, researchers supporting immediate feedback claim that it is easier to retain the correct information if it is provided sooner (Shute, 2008). At the same time, this type of feedback can be more beneficial for low-ability learners and difficult tasks, as well as for certain types of skills, such as memorisation, motor skills or procedural skills (Attali & Van der Kleij, 2017; Shute, 2008). This suggest that there might not be an unequivocal effect of feedback timing (Shute, 2008), but that it depends on the interaction with other variables, such as students' knowledge level, the type of learning and the difficulty of tasks (Attali & van der Kleij, 2017; Bokhove & Drijvers, 2012; Fyfe & Rittle-Johnson, 2016).

Feedback Levels

Hattie and Timperley (2007) discuss that the effectiveness of feedback depends on the level on which it is applied. They differentiate four levels based on a previous model developed by Kluger and DeNisi (1996):

- Task level: this is the most common type of feedback and aims at informing students about their performance in the task, reporting the correctness of their answers. Though it can be very effective in the learning process, it should be kept simple and concise to prevent students to focusing on the short-term goals of knowing the answer rather than the strategies they need to reach the learning objectives.
- Process level: feedback at the process level focuses on providing cues about the processes needed to solve a task, guiding learners to reject unsuccessful strategies and directing them

into more valid ones. This type of feedback seems to be the more effective one for deeper learning.

- Self-regulation level: at this level, feedback encourages learners to reflect on their own learning process. It prompts them to consider their goals, monitor their progress, and adjust their strategies accordingly. This level emphasizes metacognitive skills and self-awareness.
- Self-level: Feedback directed at the self is the least effective one for learning but the most used by teachers. It is aimed at the characteristics of the learners, usually based on praising. It can be highly counterproductive as it does not provide any useful information about the task, performance, or progress.

Computer-Based Assessments

Computer-based assessments (CBAs) are instruments used to promote learning, in which students answer items in a computer environment instead of in other formats (such as paper-and-pencil tests) (Miller, 2009; van der Kleij et al., 2012). CBAs present several didactic advantages for learning in contrast to more traditional settings. For instance, it allows to provide feedback while students are taking the test or immediately after taking the assignments, which might improve learning outcomes as it closes the gap between what is known and what needs to be learned (Faber et al., 2017; van der Kleij et al., 2012; Van der Kleij et al., 2015). Moreover, teachers can spend less time grading and therefore focusing more on instruction and individual assistance (Koedinger et al., 2010; Maier et al., 2016), as they can receive information about the progress of their learners, at the individual and at the classroom level (Faber et al., 2017). In addition, different types of stimuli can be integrated, such as texts, audios, videos or animations (Maier et al., 2016; Scalise & Gifford, 2006), which might lead to higher motivation and engagement of students.

Various systematic reviews and meta-analysis have provided valuable insight into the topic of feedback effects in CBAs. Van der Kleij and colleagues (2011) carried out a systematic review

to investigate the effectiveness of different methods for providing feedback in a CBA. They analysed 18 articles (from 1989 to 2010) that dealt with knowledge of response (KR), knowledge of correct response (KCR) and/or elaborated feedback (EF), however, the types of EF varied greatly from studies. From those 18, only nine reported one feedback condition as significantly superior to another. Regarding type of feedback, their findings suggest that KCR and EF can be beneficial for lower-order learning outcomes (i.e., remember, understand, apply, describe, etc.), whereas for higher-order learning outcomes (i.e., analyse, evaluate, problem-solve, etc.), only EF seems to be effective. Moreover, when EF is aimed at the task and the process levels or the task and regulation levels, it seems to positively influence the learning process. Concerning the timing, results are not homogeneous, as positive effects have been found for both immediate and delayed feedback.

Jaehnig and Miller (2007) conducted research about the effectiveness of different types of feedback in programmed instruction. They analysed 33 documents from 1964 to 2004, including the same types of feedback as the previous study. They concluded that KR is not effective for learning, KCR can be effective, and EF is the most effective approach. Coinciding with the study of Van der Kleij et al. (2011), their findings about feedback timing are not conclusive, as there were no differences between the effects of both types. This is also influenced by the unclear definition of immediate and delayed feedback, as the timing for both were different among studies. Moreover, it should be noted that many of the studies used date back more than 50 years and CBAs have deeply evolved in the last decades.

Van der Kleij, Feskens and Eggen (2015) evaluated 40 documents from 1968 to 2012 in the meta-analysis with the objective of gaining insight into the effectiveness of various methods for providing item-based feedback in computer-based environments. Their results are in line with previous research, having KR the smallest effect and EF, the largest. In terms of timing, they

also found that there is no significant interaction between feedback timing and learning outcomes.

Even though results differ greatly from studies, it seems that there is a consensus considering elaborated as the most effective type of feedback in computer-based assessments, specially in the form of subtle guidance rather than being highly specific (Van der Kleij et al., 2015). It is in the topic of feedback timing where it is more difficult to find a definite answer. As it has been stated in previous sections, research suggest that its interaction with other variables (i.e., students' level or difficulty of task) can influence its effect on learning outcomes.

Feedback Animations

Given the dynamic component of spatial abilities, animations can be a valuable resource to upgrade spatial thinking trainings, especially in computer-based environments, as they can aid in the understanding of spatial processes. Animations are dynamic visualizations that present information changing over time (Türkay, 2016). They can be a powerful learning tool, since learners can use them as scaffolding before, during and after the instruction to build appropriate mental models regarding new knowledge and skills (Lin & Li, 2018). This can be especially significant when training spatial thinking skills, as many of the areas within involve mental strategies to imagine processes and movement (Maresch, 2014). Although results on animations benefits on learning are conflicting (Stebner et al., 2017; Tversky et al., 2002), Cohen and Hegarty (2014) showed positive effects of using interactive animation to train spatial visualization skills. Moreover, a study on Lego manipulative tasks that involved mental rotation also found gains when providing animations to support this activity (Castro-Alonso et al., 2015). In this line, a meta-analysis on spatial ability and learning with visualizations concluded that dynamic visualizations can positively support low spatial ability learners (Höffler, 2010). Considering this information, using animations as a way of providing formative assessment in spatial thinking skills training, could involve higher achievement, as it would be a way to help

learners close the gap between the unsuccessful strategies they are using and those they should employ to solve the spatial tasks.

Feedback and Gender

Although there is not much literature about the influence of gender in feedback effects, a few studies have shed some light into the topic. Rahe et al. (2019) carried out a study to observe the effects of feedback on gender differences in a chronometric mental rotation test. They concluded that, although participants who received feedback reacted faster than those who did not, they made more errors. In terms of gender, females benefited more than males in reaction time, but did not improve their confidence in their responses. In another study, Rahe and Quaiser-Pohl (2020), also observed the effects of feedback on the performance in a mental rotation test in children. They found no positive effects of feedback for error rate, and only boys benefitted in reaction time. In contrast to the previous study, they did not ask about confidence. Narciss et al. (2014) explored the effect of several student characteristics on feedback effects. For gender, they found that girls benefitted more than boys and had more learning gains, however, both genders declined in their perceived competence.

Current Study

Considering the evidence available on the vast body of literature on feedback presented in the previous sections, chapter 7 of this dissertation focuses on developing and providing computer-based assessment for spatial thinking tasks in the online platform RIF. More specifically, the assessment will be defined as immediate elaborated feedback and knowledge of correct response (in the form of animated videos) on the task and the process level. It will show students the right answer by demonstrating a solving strategy for the task. As research finds conflicting results regarding the effects of different ways of providing feedback, this study has the purpose of contributing to the literary corpus related to feedback in computer-based environments, concretely on the area of spatial ability tasks. Moreover, it intends to improve the learning

experience with the RIF platform, since, as it is a computer-based learning environment, interactions between instructor and student are highly limited. We aim at examining whether immediate EF + KCR has a positive effect on students learning outcomes in spatial thinking tasks as opposed to not receiving any feedback. Moreover, the interaction of gender on feedback effects will also be explored, along with the impact of feedback in learners' confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks.

Section Summary

In the previous chapters we reviewed the literature related to the topics addressed in the dissertation. We began with a description of spatial thinking, its trainability and link to STEM, and its history of research. Following, mental rotation, the tests used for its assessment and the gender differences found in those were explored. Finally, formative feedback, its characteristics and its application in computer-based environments were reported. In the next chapters, the experimental part of the thesis is described. Chapter 4 deals with the development and evaluation of spatial thinking tasks for the RIF platform. In chapter 5 an evaluation of the RIF platform is carried out. Chapter 6 explores the effects of using different types of representations in mental rotation tasks in students' outcomes and gender differences. Lastly, chapter 7 examines the impact of animated feedback in the RIF platform as a computer-based environment on students' outcomes.

Empirical Studies

Introduction

Considering the context presented in the previous section, in the next chapters we attempt to address the following topics: (1) the design and assessment of tasks for primary school children; (2) the evaluation of participants' performance in the platform tasks; (3) the improvement of outcomes in mental rotations tasks and decrement of gender differences; and (4) the support of learning with the platform by providing detailed feedback. The four topics are divided into four consecutive chapters.

Chapter 4 describes the development and evaluation of tasks for the RIF platform. In this stage, numerous tasks for primary school students for different areas of spatial thinking were created. These tasks were then assessed using the results of users of the platform, which led to their improvement. Moreover, the creation of a color-blindness check and the translation of the platform into Spanish is also addressed.

Chapter 5 reports the evaluation of the RIF platform. Results of 41664 participants are analysed to answer the following research questions:

1. How do participants perform in each area of spatial thinking trained in the RIF platform?

1.1. How do participants perform in each area per age group?

2. Are there differences in the performance of females and males in any of the nine areas of spatial thinking trained in the RIF platform?

2.1. If so, in which area(s)?

2.2. If so, in which age group(s)?

Chapter 6 focuses on exploring the effects of using different types of representations in mental rotation tasks to improve students' outcomes and reduce the gender differences found in this area in chapter 5. The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. Does the use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks help to improve students' outcomes?

1.1. Do they have a different effect in females' and males' outcomes?

1.2. Does the use of more realistic types of representations in tasks similar to the ones in the MRT-Test help improve students' outcomes?

2. Can the use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks decrease or eliminate gender differences?

2.1. Can gender differences be reduced or eliminated in the tasks similar to the MRT-Test when using more realistic types of representations?

3. Which type of representation do girls and boys prefer?

3.1. Is there a link between preference for type of representation and performance in the assessment instrument?

In chapter 7, we aim at enhancing the learning process when practicing with spatial tasks in a computer-based environment, where there is little to no interaction between the instructor and students. Therefore, in this chapter the impact of animated feedback in spatial thinking online training is analysed, considering the following research questions:

1. Does immediate elaborated feedback (videos) have a positive effect on students' learning outcomes in online spatial thinking tasks?

1.1. Do low-skilled students benefit more from feedback?

1.2. Which condition (feedback or no-feedback) is more beneficial for girls and for boys?

2. Does feedback have an impact on students' confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks?

2.1. Are there differences between girls and boys on confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks?

Chapter 4: Development and Evaluation of Tasks

Introduction

This chapter describes the preliminary phases of the studies that are presented in the following chapters. The first section corresponds to the development of the tasks for the online spatial training platform RIF, that will later be used as instruments for the studies. In this section, the process of preparation, development, evaluation and final establishment of the tasks is detailed. The second section illustrates the design of a color-blindness check instrument. This instrument was created to inform users of a possible presence of color-blindness that could potentially affect their performance in the RIF platform, as many tasks are colored-based. Finally, the third section outlines the process of translation of the platform to Spanish, which allows it to reach to a larger number of users around the world.

Development of the Tasks

Following the model of the basic practices of spatial thinking (Maresch, 2020), the aim of this work is to create tasks for the initial five stages of this model, namely: visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combinations, for children between 7 and 12 years old. These stages are first ones to be developed by children and are the foundation for spatial skills. As described in previous chapters, these areas involve (RIF 3.0, 2023):

- Visualization: ability to filter and focus on relevant facets of visual information (e.g., colors, shapes, patterns, separation of irrelevant and relevant visual information).
- Form constancy: ability to recognize objects based on their characteristics (e.g., recognize and distinguish similar objects such as triangles, squares, describe characteristics of objects).

- Position in space: ability to recognize relative positions of objects to each other (e.g., front, back, top, bottom, left, and right).
- Transformation in space: ability to recognize the relationship between source object(s) and target object(s) when moving in space (e.g., be able to recognize slides, rotations, reflections, and scales).
- Object combination: ability to recognize object intersections and Boolean operations (e.g., be able to recognize intersection patterns, recognize union, average, and difference of two spatial objects).

In order to base the tasks in previous valid ones, we treated with the books from Frostig & Horne (1977), Helwig and Schaadt (2008), and Homering and Uta (2014), as they are well-accepted experts in the matter. After a thoughtful examination of the tasks displayed in these books, we created a list of tasks that could be implemented in our work. We took into account the following aspects: the age of the children our tasks are aimed to; the possibility of adapting the tasks to an online setting; and the compatibility with the five stages of the basic practices. Those discarded were usually tasks that could not be created for a digital platform or did not fit into any of the five stages (for example, tasks related to eye-motor coordination, as they usually involve drawing fine lines, which would be difficult to achieve with a computer mouse and also complicated to properly assess). As these books were mainly aimed at pre-school children and learners in the first grades in primary schools, we encountered that there were no tasks related to transformation in space and object combinations, as these are more complex skills. Moreover, to include tasks more suitable for older students, we also considered the Test of Visual Perceptual Skills (TVPS) (Martin, 2017) and the Spatial Ability Practice Test 1 (Newton & Bristoll, n.d.).

Following, a more detailed analysis was conducted with the goal of identifying the different types of tasks that would compose each category. Table 2 below shows the result of this analysis, which were only possible in the first three areas:

Table 2

Types of tasks of the first five basic practices of spatial thinking included in the RIF 3.0 platform

Area	Types of tasks
Visualization	Size
	Color
	Shape
	Brightness
	Figure-ground perception
	Combination of properties
Form constancy	Form identification
	Geometric shape identification
	Daily object identification
	Locating an object
	Shaded images
	Object position
Position in space	Sequence
	Missing
	Objects touching
	Perspective
	Relative position
	Transformation in space
Object combination	-

After having a wide selection of different types of tasks, the following step was to create brand new tasks considering the restriction of developing them for a digital setting and through the

QuizMaker software from the iSpring company, in which the types of tasks that can be made are already established. Namely, most of the tasks are multiple choice, drag and drop, hotspot, matching, sequence, true/false, and select from the lists. A total of 452 tasks were developed, for the five categories: 168 for visualization; 62 for form constancy; 38 for position in space; 116 for transformation in space; and 68 for object combinations. I focused on developing the tasks for the visualization area (168 tasks) and part of the position in space (18).

Evaluation of the Tasks

The evaluation of the tasks was divided into three stages: an internal evaluation, a first external evaluation and a second external evaluation.

The internal evaluation consisted of gathering expert feedback through a cross-evaluation of the tasks. Each of the task-creators revised the tasks developed by other members of the group. Different issues were analysed, such as the clarity of the headings, correct size of figures, understanding of the task, etc. This stage lasted from January to February 2022. After the review, the necessary changes were undertaken.

The second stage of the evaluation had the purpose of improving the quality of the tasks by consulting both students and teachers. As there were various areas to be evaluated, this stage was divided into several researchers; therefore, we are going to focus on the visualization area henceforth, as it was my area of expertise.

First External Evaluation

The first external evaluation involved trying the tasks for the first time with learners to test their validity. This stage was conducted in two public primary schools in Chiclana de la Frontera (Spain) in May 2022.

From the preliminary 168 tasks created for the visualization area, 100 were selected to create four task groups of 25 tasks each. The four task groups were isomorphic, meaning they

consisted of the same type questions, only varying in the figures, numbers or colors used. This way, we could later compare the results of the four task groups.

In addition to the four task groups, participants answered a short questionnaire (Table 3) aimed at learning their opinions about the tasks (see Annex 1): enjoyment, difficulty, interest, etc. Most of the questions (9/12) were answered through a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree). One question was a yes/no question with a related question in case they answered yes, and one was an open question where they could add further comments on the tasks. One last question was meant to know what device they used.

Table 3

Questions included in the questionnaire for students

Question number	Spanish	English
Q1	He entendido bien las actividades.	<i>I understood the tasks well.</i>
Q2	Las actividades son interesantes.	<i>The tasks are interesting.</i>
Q3	Las actividades son divertidas.	<i>The tasks are fun.</i>
Q4	Me gustaría haber hecho más actividades.	<i>I would like to have solved more tasks.</i>
Q5	¿Cuántas más? (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, más de 5).	<i>How many more? (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, more than 5).</i>
Q6	No podía concentrarme bien en las últimas actividades.	<i>I could not concentrate well on the last tasks.</i>
Q7	Las actividades eran demasiado fáciles para mí.	<i>The tasks were too easy for me.</i>
Q8	Podía concentrarme bien en las últimas actividades.	<i>I could concentrate well on the last tasks.</i>
Q9	Las actividades eran muy difíciles para mí.	<i>The tasks were too difficult for me.</i>
Q10	Me gustaría hacer estas actividades más a menudo.	<i>I would like to do these tasks more often.</i>

Question number	Spanish	English
Q11	La dificultad de las actividades estaba bien para mí.	<i>The difficulty of the tasks was fine for me.</i>
Q12	¿Qué dispositivo has utilizado?	<i>Which device did you use?</i>
Q13	Escribe aquí qué te han parecido las actividades, qué podríamos hacer mejor y cualquier otra cosa relacionada que se te ocurra.	<i>Write here what you thought of the tasks, what we could do better and anything else related that you can think of.</i>

Note: The language of the questionnaire was Spanish, however, the English translation is provided for clarification.

Moreover, teachers' perception of the tasks (difficulty, clarity of headings, age appropriateness, etc.) was also collected through a questionnaire (Table 4). They answered the same questionnaire after their students had completed each task group (see Annex 2).

Table 4

Questions included in the questionnaire for teachers

Spanish	English
Las actividades son adecuadas para la edad de mis alumnos/as.	<i>The tasks are appropriate for the age of my learners.</i>
Las actividades logran captar y mantener el interés de mis alumnos/as.	<i>The tasks manage to capture and maintain the interest of my learners.</i>
Los enunciados eran claros y fáciles de entender.	<i>The statements were clear and easy to understand.</i>
Me ha dado la impresión de que mis alumnos/as pudieron mantener su concentración hasta la última actividad.	<i>I felt that my students were able to maintain their concentration until the last task.</i>
Sabiendo que cada grupo de actividades consta de 25 actividades y teniendo en cuenta las capacidades habituales de concentración	<i>Knowing that each practice group consists of 25 tasks and taking into account the usual concentration abilities of your students: do you think this is an adequate number?</i>

de su alumnado: ¿cree que es una cantidad adecuada?

¿Cuántas cree que deberían tener?

How many do you think they should have?

No dude en proporcionar más comentarios sobre las actividades.

Feel free to provide further comments on the tasks.

Note: The language of the questionnaire was Spanish, however, the English translation is provided for clarification.

Participants solved the four task groups in two days (two task groups per day) individually in a laptop or a tablet. Immediately after finishing each task group, they responded to the questionnaires. They had access to the Spanish version of the task groups and the questionnaires through the website: <https://geometriedidaktik.at/>. The researcher was present at all times when the task groups were being solved.

Participants. A total of 96 participants were recruited for this study, however figures change from one task group to another. For the first task group we counted with a sample size of 94 (51 females and 43 males) from 10 to 13 years old ($M_{\text{age}} = 11.20$; $s = .697$). In the second task group participated 94 learners (53 females and 41 males) from 10 to 13 years old ($M_{\text{age}} = 11.17$; $SD = .713$). The third and fourth task groups were carried out by 96 participants (50 females and 46 males) from 10 to 13 years old ($M_{\text{age}} = 11.21$; $SD = .695$ and $M_{\text{age}} = 11.24$; $SD = .692$, respectively). They were fifth and sixth grade primary school students (according to the Spanish educational system).

For the comparison of the results of the four task groups, we considered the data of the 83 participants that completed all four task groups (45 females and 38 males).

Four teachers answered the questionnaire aimed at them (three females and one male).

Results. Results of the four task groups, their internal consistency and the average percentage of time spent in each task group were analysed, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5*Average percentage of correct answers, average time and Cronbach's alpha by task group*

	Average percentage of correct answers		Average time		α
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	
Task group 1	82.85	10.07	11'43"	3'52"	.551
Task group 2	88.85	9.95	6'44"	2'44"	.654
Task group 3	89.33	8.74	5'52"	1'51"	.576
Task group 4	91.13	8.69	4'49"	1'09"	.657

From Table 5, we can infer that outcomes tend to improve with each task group and the average time spent tends to decrease. The most noticeable difference in percentage of correct answers and time lies between the first and the second task group.

The reliability analysis show a low consistency of the tasks in all the task groups.

Improvement between groups. In order to compare the results in each task group, we considered the data from the participants who completed all four task groups (N = 83). Table 6 summarizes the average percentage of correct answers and average time spent per task group.

Table 6*Average percentage of correct answers and time by task group*

	Average percentage of correct answers		Average time	
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S
Task group 1	84.02	9.03	11'39"	3'47"
Task group 2	89.40	8.76	6'17"	1'43"
Task group 3	90.60	7.13	5'45"	1'26"
Task group 4	91.71	7.67	5'28"	1'26"

Outcomes of participants who solved the four task groups improved with each task group and so does the average time spent on them.

The statistical significance between the difference in average percentage of correct answers and average time spent of each task group was also analysed (Table 7):

Table 7

Statistical significance of difference of average percentage of correct answers and time between task groups

	P
Task group 1 – Task group 2	<.001*
Task group 2 – Task group 3	.223
Task group 3 – Task group 4	.078
Task group 1 – Task group 4	<.001*
Time TG 1 – Time TG 2	<.001*
Time TG 2 – Time TG 3	.016*
Time TG 3 – Time TG 4	.081
Time TG 1 – Time TG 4	<.001*

Note: TG stands for Task group.

*Statistically significant.

Improvements in the outcomes between task groups are significant at the .001 level from the first to the second task group and from the first to the fourth. Regarding the time, improvements are significant at the .001 level from the first to the second task group and from the first to the fourth and at the .05 level from the second to the third task group.

Questionnaire for students. Table 8 presents the means of the answers of the questions that were answered by Likert-scale in the four questionnaires responded by students.

Table 8

Means and std. deviation of answers of the Likert-scale questions in the four questionnaires for learners

	Questionnaire 1		Questionnaire 2		Questionnaire 3		Questionnaire 4	
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	s
Q1	4.38	.705	4.45	.738	4.57	.630	4.57	.694
Q2	4.40	.825	4.39	.837	4.38	.806	4.39	.842
Q3	4.36	.922	4.49	.794	4.45	.847	4.49	.766
Q4	2.03	1.24	2.06	1.30	1.71	1.16	1.62	.885
Q7	3.64	1.15	3.71	1.03	3.90	1.03	3.87	1.08
Q8	4.13	1.04	4.02	1.18	4.43	.899	4.23	1.01
Q9	1.88	1.27	1.73	1.07	1.86	1.17	1.80	1.02
Q10	4.44	.858	4.38	.981	4.54	.766	4.42	.962
Q11	4.03	1.07	4.29	.798	3.92	1.08	4.00	1.15

1: strongly disagree – 5: strongly agree

Note: Q stands for question.

Data shows positive results in students understanding the tasks (Q1); finding them interesting and enjoyable (Q2 and Q3); being able to concentrate through all the tasks (Q8); and wanting to do these type of tasks more often (Q10). On the contrary, they generally disagree on not being able to concentrate in the last tasks (Q4) and the tasks being too difficult (Q9). Finally, results reveal that they find the tasks rather easy (Q7), though the agreement in the difficulty being appropriate is high (Q11).

Figures 8 and 9 represent the percentage of answers to the question “I would like to have solved more tasks” and to “How many tasks would you like to have solved?” respectively.

Figure 8

Percentage of yes/no answers to “I would like to have solved more tasks”

Figure 9

Percentage of answers to “How many tasks would you like to have solved?”

Regarding the number of tasks solved, 91.90 % of participants in the first questionnaire, 83.70 % in the second, 87 % in the third, and 86.90 % in the fourth express their predisposition

to have solved more tasks. More specifically, in all cases, the vast majority chose the option “more than five”.

At the end of the questionnaire, students were given the opportunity to add further comments on their opinion about the tasks. Among a great number of positive remarks (276 comments of participants) (student 1: “I found the tasks really cool”; student 2: “The tasks were really fun to solve and would like to do them more often”), 15 learners expressed that some questions were difficult to understand and 42 that the tasks were excessively easy for them.

Questionnaire for teachers. Table 9 summarises the means of the answers of each questions in the four questionnaires responded by teachers after their students completed the four task groups.

Table 9

Means and std. deviation of answers of the Likert-scale questions in the four questionnaires for teachers

	Questionnaire 1		Questionnaire 2		Questionnaire 3		Questionnaire 4	
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	s
Q1	3.50	1.92	3.50	1.00	3.67	2.31	4.00	1.41
Q2	2.50	1.00	3.50	1.00	4.33	1.16	3.80	1.79
Q3	3.00	1.63	4.00	1.16	3.67	1.16	4.20	1.10
Q4	2.50	1.00	3.50	1.00	4.33	1.16	3.80	1.79
Q5	1.75	.500	2.00	.000	2.00	.000	1.80	.447

1: strongly disagree – 5: strongly agree

Note: Q stands for question.

Teachers generally rate the tasks as appropriate for the age of their students (Q1) and the headings as clear and easy to understand (Q3). However, they find that they might have encountered some difficulties maintaining the concentration (Q2 and Q4), especially in the first

task group. There is a consensus in the number of tasks being low (Q5), for what they suggest increasing the number by at least 30 tasks per task group.

Concerning the comment section at the end of the questionnaire, they rate the task groups positively and recommend to improve the headings in some of the questions to either simplify them or adapt them to vocabulary to which students are more used to. Table 10 shows a compilation of examples of modifications:

Table 10

Examples of modifications of questions after teachers' feedback

Original version	Adapted version
<p>¿Qué figura falta? Selecciónala y arrástrala al signo de interrogación.</p> <p><i>What shape is missing? Click on it and drag it to the question mark.</i></p>	<p>Completa la serie arrastrando la figura que falta al signo de interrogación.</p> <p><i>Complete the series dragging the shape that is missing to the question mark.</i></p>
<p>Mira la figura de abajo.</p> <p>¿Qué figuras del recuadro de arriba se han usado para formarla? Haz clic sobre ellas.</p> <p><i>Look at the image below.</i></p> <p><i>Which shapes in the box above have been used to form it? Click on them.</i></p>	<p>Haz clic sobre las figuras del recuadro de arriba que se han usado para formar la imagen de abajo.</p> <p><i>Click on the shapes in the box above that have been used to form the image below.</i></p>
<p>¿Qué fragmento falta en la imagen?</p> <p><i>Which part of the image is missing?</i></p>	<p>Selecciona el fragmento de la izquierda que completa la imagen.</p> <p><i>Select the fragment on the left that completes the image.</i></p>
<p>Mira las figuras de la primera fila. Cada una tiene un número.</p> <p>Encuentra las figuras en la segunda fila y arrastra el número que les corresponda.</p> <p><i>Look at the shapes in the first row. Each one has a number.</i></p> <p><i>Find the shapes in the second row and drag the number that corresponds to them.</i></p>	<p>Mira las figuras de la primera fila y sus números.</p> <p>Encuentra las mismas figuras en la segunda fila y arrastra el mismo número hasta ellas.</p> <p><i>Look at the shapes in the first row and their numbers.</i></p> <p><i>Find the same shapes in the second row and drag the same number to them.</i></p>

Original version	Adapted version
¿En cuál de estas cuatro imágenes se encuentra la figura de la izquierda? Haz clic sobre ella.	Haz clic sobre la imagen en la que se encuentra la figura de la izquierda.
<i>In which of these four images is the shape on the left? Click on it.</i>	<i>Click on the image that has the shape on the left in it.</i>

Note: changes have been made in the Spanish version of the tasks. The English translation in italics is for clarification.

Second external evaluation

The aim of the second stage of the external evaluation of the tasks was to confirm the results obtained in the first one with more participants, and further analyse the consistency of the task groups and difficulty of the tasks, in order to create the final version of the task groups.

Participants. For this study, we counted with a total of 795 participants (387 females, 371 males and 38 other) from the ages 7 to 13. In Table 11, we present a summary of the sample size and average age of the participants in the second stage of the evaluation of the tasks.

Table 11

Sample size and average age of participants by gender in each task group

	N				Age	
	Total	F	M	Other	\bar{x}	S
Task group 1	418	219	184	15	11.76	1.453
Task group 2	109	111	89	9	11.92	1.280
Task group 3	147	87	53	7	12.02	1.230
Task group 4	121	70	45	5	12.12	1.166

Age range: task group 1: 7-13; task group 2: 8-13; task group 3: 9-13; and task group 4: 8-13.

The task groups were posted online on the website: <https://geometriedidaktik.at/>, where volunteers from around Austria could access and solve any task group.

Results. Following, the results of the second external evaluation of the tasks are presented.

Table 12 summarises the average percentage of correct answers and average time spent per task group.

Table 12

Average percentage of correct answers and time by task group

	Average percentage of correct answers		Average time	
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S
Task group 1	83.98	13.55	5'29"	3'13"
Task group 2	89.70	10.59	5'53"	2'30"
Task group 3	90.48	10.95	5'08"	2'36"
Task group 4	91.34	9.68	5'20"	2'53"

Outcomes tend to improve with each task group, while time stays more stable.

Table 13 displays the consistency coefficient (α) of each task group and the difficulty of each item (\bar{X}).

Table 13

Cronbach's alpha of each task group and difficulty of tasks

	Task group 1		Task group 2		Task group 3		Task group 4	
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	s
	$\alpha = .784$		$\alpha = .737$		$\alpha = .769$		$\alpha = .737$	
T1	,85	,353	,90	,295	,92	,275	,93	,250
T2	,46	,499	,70	,460	,88	,329	,85	,357
T3	,55	,499	,57	,496	,73	,443	,71	,455
T4	,94	,242	,91	,281	,97	,182	,97	,180
T5	,92	,277	,90	,295	,92	,275	,95	,218

	Task group 1		Task group 2		Task group 3		Task group 4	
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	s
	$\alpha = .784$		$\alpha = .737$		$\alpha = .769$		$\alpha = .737$	
T6	,97	,160	,96	,192	,62	,487	,96	,200
T7	,88	,322	,98	,153	,97	,163	,92	,276
T8	,88	,330	,93	,251	,97	,182	,99	,091
T9	,98	,145	,97	,167	,99	,082	,97	,180
T10	,95	,214	,98	,137	,98	,142	,98	,156
T11	,49	,501	,99	,119	,83	,377	,96	,200
T12	,90	,304	,94	,233	,93	,253	,98	,128
T13	,70	,459	,96	,192	,79	,409	,48	,502
T14	,87	,338	,96	,192	,78	,414	,97	,180
T15	,96	,192	,96	,192	,94	,241	,98	,156
T16	,96	,198	,81	,394	,96	,199	,97	,180
T17	,94	,233	,96	,203	,96	,199	,89	,311
T18	,89	,313	,98	,137	,99	,116	,97	,180
T19	,83	,372	,91	,288	,94	,241	,96	,200
T20	,83	,372	,87	,336	,96	,199	,96	,200
T21	,70	,457	,68	,466	,96	,199	,88	,321
T22	,97	,180	,94	,233	,95	,214	,92	,276
T23	,89	,313	,93	,251	,93	,264	,92	,276
T24	,89	,310	,90	,301	,93	,253	,93	,263
T25	,78	,413	,81	,391	,83	,377	,86	,349

Notes: T stands for task. Figures highlighted in bold show a \bar{x} lower than .67.

The four task groups show an acceptable-to-good consistency ($\alpha = .784$; $\alpha = .737$; $\alpha = .769$; and $\alpha = .737$, respectively). However, six items exceed in their difficulty in comparison to the others, namely: in task group 1: task 2 ($\bar{x} = .46$), task 3 ($\bar{x} = .55$) and task 11 ($\bar{x} = .49$); in task group 2: task 3 ($\bar{x} = .57$); in task group 3: task 6 ($\bar{x} = .62$), and in task group 4: task 13 ($\bar{x} = .48$). All

these items were deleted from the tasks groups, as they fall into the first quartile, having a success rate of less than 66.67 % (i.e., .67).

Conclusion

In this section, the stages of development and evaluation of the tasks have been described. The development phase included several steps that made it possible to obtain a large selection of tasks aimed at primary school students ranging from 7 to 12 years old. It involved (1) understanding and establishing the differences between the five first areas of the basic practices of spatial thinking (Maresch, 2020); (2) classifying the diverse types of tasks that could be included in each area; (3) selecting the most appropriate tasks; and (4) designing the tasks for a web-based format.

The evaluation phase was divided into three stages: (1) an internal evaluation, in which experts of the matter carried out a cross-area evaluation of the tasks; (2) a first external evaluation of the Visualization area with a smaller sample (N = 96); (3) and a second external evaluation of the Visualization area with a larger sample (N = 795). The internal evaluation led to some changes, such as improvement in the headings, adjustments of the figures (size, clarity), or alignment of texts, among others. The first external evaluation shed some more light about the tasks. We learnt that students enjoyed solving them and found them motivating, as they would like to do them more often. Results improve with practice and they need less minutes each time. However, given that the sample was between 10 and 12 years old, they found the tasks rather easy and short. Moreover, learners expressed that some headings were difficult to understand, statement that was also addressed by teachers. Given these points, we undertook two main changes: adapt the problematic headings into more clear instructions, and extend the number of tasks per task group from 25 to 30. The second external evaluation provided more information about the tasks. More specifically, though a Cronbach's alpha coefficient performed in each practice group revealed a good internal consistency, some tasks were deleted in order to

improve these results, as they showed a significantly lower rate of right answers. These modifications conducted to the final version of the tasks, which were now ready to be published.

Color Blindness

Color blindness is a color vision deficiency (CVD) that affects an individual's ability to perceive and distinguish shades of certain colors (Oktarianti et al., 2022). It is often genetically inherited and more prevalent in males (1 in 12) than in females (1 in 200) (Lockett, 2020). There are mainly two types: total or partial color blindness. In the first case, the person can only see black, white and grey, while in the second case, they can have difficulties discriminating between red and green (which is the most common) or blue and yellow.

In 1971, Shinobu Ishihara designed a color vision instrument for the detection of red-green color blindness within a few minutes. It contains 25 plates that show either numbers or lines formed by small colored circles that contrast with the background of the opposite color, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10

Plate number 2 in the Ishihara's Tests for Color Blindness Concise edition (Ishihara, 1982)

Considering that many tasks in the platform are colored-based, a possible color blindness could lead to failing them without teachers knowing the cause. Therefore, two measurements were

taken: First, we developed an informative document (see Annex 3) where we listed all the colored-based tasks, so that those could be skipped or not taken into account in the evaluation and second, we incorporated a shorter version of the Ishihara Test into the platform (Ishihara, 1982) (see Annex 4), for participants to voluntarily take it before starting the task groups. This series of questions do not diagnose color blindness, but in case of positive results, they can be an indicator to seek for professional help (<https://rif4you.eu/colors/en/>).

Spanish Translation

Due to the significant success of the platform in both German and English and the international nature of the SellSTEM project in which this work is framed, we decided to translate the platform into Spanish, my native language.

Spanish is the fourth most spoken language in the world, after English, Mandarin and Hindi with 548 million speakers around the world (Statista, 2023) and the second language with more native speakers distributed in 21 countries (Instituto Cervantes, 2018). Therefore, offering the platform in Spanish meant making it available for a great number of users, who would have the opportunity to improve their spatial skills in a new way.

This work involved translating:

- The 51 task groups offered in the platform;
- The text of the website;
- The commands and messages from the platform.

Until now, we have received data from several Spanish-speaking countries, namely: Spain, Peru, Argentina, Mexico, Venezuela, Ecuador, Dominican Republic and Guatemala.

General Conclusions of the Chapter

In this chapter, the processes of development and evaluation of tasks and a color-blindness check for the online spatial thinking training RIF platform have been described, along with its translation to Spanish.

First, regarding the tasks, a thorough analysis of pre-existing tasks and the model of basic practices of spatial thinking proposed by Maresch (2020), has supported the creation of new tasks that aim at helping students train their spatial skills from a young age. Moreover, their evaluation and recurrent feedback from teachers concluded in tasks that are not only motivating and engaging, but that also fit in the classroom environment.

Second, the inclusion of a color-blindness check makes the platform a more inclusive space that bears in mind some learning difficulties that learners might encounter. With this information, not only can those who appear to have color-blindness get it professionally checked, but also make teachers aware of reasons why those students might have difficulties with some tasks (in- and outside the RIF platform).

Third, translating the platform into Spanish make it accessible to a large part of the world population, as it is the fourth most spoken language in the world and the second with more native speakers.

These new tasks and additions were included in the new version of the platform, which will serve as the context of this work.

In the following chapter, a detailed evaluation of the RIF platform, including the previous and new areas is carried out.

Chapter 5: Evaluation of the Platform

Introduction

In this chapter, the results of the evaluation of the RIF platform are presented. The outcomes of participants (N = 41664; 18056 females and 23608 males) between the ages of 7 and +21, in 50 task groups of the nine areas of spatial thinking that are found in the RIF platform were analysed to assess participants' performance in each area and in different age groups. Moreover, results of females and males were compared to establish whether there are gender differences in any of the areas and age groups. The chapter is structured beginning with the presentation of the research questions, followed by the method employed in the study to collect and analyse data and finishes with the presentation of the results and discussion.

Research Questions and Hypothesis

This study aims at providing further information about the RIF platform, its tasks and the results of its users. Therefore, the specific research questions are as follow:

1. How do participants perform in each area of spatial thinking trained in the RIF platform?
 - 1.1. How do participants perform in each area per age group?
2. Are there differences in the performance of females and males in any of the nine areas of spatial thinking trained in the RIF platform?
 - 2.1. If so, in which area(s)?
 - 2.2. If so, in which age group(s)?

Derived from these research questions, the study is guided by the following hypothesis:

H1: Participant's outcomes in the categories spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation are lower than in the categories visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combination.

H1.1: Participant's outcomes tend to improve with age.

H2: There are no significant differences in the areas of spatial thinking trained in the platform except for mental rotation.

H2.2: Differences between females and males are larger between the ages of 12 to 18.

Method

Design

In this study, a quantitative research based on an experimental design was carried out to analyse the results of the users of the RIF platform in each area. Moreover, females' and males' outcomes have been compared to establish whether there are gender differences in any of the nine areas of spatial thinking offered in the RIF platform.

Participants

The sample was formed by a group of 41664 students (18056 females and 23608 males, $M_{age} = 15.63$; $SD = 7.373$, age range: 7 to +21 years old). Data have been divided into six age groups (see Table 14): 7-9 years old ($n = 319$; 153 females and 166 males); 10-12 years old ($n = 4289$; 2220 females and 2069 males); 13-15 years old ($n = 30241$; 12306 females and 17935 males); 16-18 years old ($n = 2844$; 942 females and 1902 males); 19-21 years old ($n = 1552$; 1119 females and 433 males); and +21 years old ($n = 2419$; 1316 females and 1103 males).

Table 14*Number of participants in total, per age group and gender*

	Total	Females	Males
Total	41664	18056	23608
7-9	319	153	166
10-12	4289	2220	2069
13-15	30241	12306	17935
16-18	2844	942	1902
19-21	1552	1119	433
+21	2419	1316	1103

Instruments

This study was developed using 50 task groups divided into the nine areas of spatial thinking of the RIF platform. The distribution of the 50 tasks groups into the areas is as follows: spatial visualization: 6; spatial relations: 6; mental rotation: 6; spatial orientation: 6; visualization: 6; form constancy: 6; position in space: 3; transformation in space: 6; and object combination: 5. The task groups in the areas visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combination consist of 30 tasks. The tasks groups in the area spatial relations contain 22 tasks (4 task groups) and 44 tasks (2 task groups). The task groups in the areas spatial orientation and mental rotation include 20 tasks (4 task groups) and 40 tasks (2 task groups). Finally, the task groups in the area spatial visualization consist of 30 tasks (4 task groups) and 60 tasks (2 task groups).

Data analysis

Results of the various task groups of each area where unified by finding the mean percentage of correct answers between all the task groups. The following analysis were carried out in total (N = 41664) and within each age group:

- Average percentage of correct answers in each area per age group;
- Difference in average percentage of correct answers between females and males;

- Difference in average percentage of correct answers between age groups within gender.

Some criteria were applied to filter the results. First, we discarded all participants aged below 7 years old, as tasks were designed for users from up to that age. Second, participants who selected “other” in the gender question were also removed, as they did not serve the purpose of this study. Third, results below one third of correct answers were discarded, as they might imply that the answers have been randomly selected. Finally, results of the age group 1 in the areas of spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation, and results of the age groups 4 to 6 in the areas of visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combination were eliminated as the sample size was not large enough to draw valid conclusions. In addition, the difficulty of the tasks was also considered to discard these data, as the four first areas are excessively challenging for age group 1, while the last five areas lack of sufficient challenge for older learners, which could alter the general outcomes of this study.

Results

In this section, the results of the evaluation of the RIF platform are presented. First, the outcomes divided into the six age groups previously described were analysed: age group 1 (7-9); age group 2 (10-12); age group 3 (13-15); age group 4 (16-18); age group 5 (19-21); and age group 6 (+21). Second, we present the results of the total number of participants in each area. Third, we compare the results of each age group in each area. And finally, we contrast the evolution of results of females and males in each area across age.

Age group 1 (7 to 9 years old)

Table 15 and Figure 11 display the results of participants aged 7 to 9 years old in the areas visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combination.

Table 15

Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 7 to 9 years old)

	Total		Females		Males		Diff.*	p
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S		
VI	82.66	14.39	82.69	14.60	82.63	14.29	0.06	.980
FC	81.96	13.41	80.07	14.38	83.71	12.38	3.64	.242
PS	79.39	17.16	81.11	16.14	78.06	18.06	3.05	.511
TS	68.23	17.87	67.90	18.23	68.55	17.89	0.65	.899
OC	92.38	8.41	93.70	6.31	91.43	9.77	2.27	.700

Diff.: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that area between females and males.

Figure 11

Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 7 to 9

Results in the five areas are considerably positive. In the first three (VI, FC and PS) they remain rather stable, then lowering in transformation in space and improving in object combination. Both females and males share this trend. In regards to gender differences, results are similar

between both groups, differing more in form constancy (boys outscoring girls), position in space (girls outscoring boys) and object combination (girls outscoring boys), though none if these are significant.

Age group 2 (10 to 12 years old)

Table 16 and Figure 12 show the results of participants aged 10 to 12 years old in the nine areas of spatial thinking in the RIF platform.

Table 16

Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 10 to 12 years old)

	Total		Females		Males		Diff.^	p
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S		
SV	57.27	18.56	55.78	18.00	58.73	19.01	2.95	.023*
SR	44.90	15.74	43.32	15.72	46.62	15.63	3.3	.028*
MR	49.82	18.82	46.42	17.47	53.25	19.54	6.83	<.001*
SO	73.05	15.08	72.19	14.50	73.98	15.66	1.79	.165
VI	89.71	9.45	91.19	8.58	87.92	10.15	3.27	<.001*
FC	87.96	10.12	89.11	9.46	86.85	10.62	2.26	.032*
PS	88.46	10.82	89.21	9.83	87.61	11.83	1.54	.116
TS	79.51	14.42	80.15	13.51	78.79	15.39	1.36	.328
OC	90.12	8.99	91.20	9.30	88.93	8.52	2.27	.044*

^Diff.: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that area between females and males.

*Statistically significant.

Figure 12

Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 10 to 12

Results in the first four areas fluctuate from being satisfactory (SV), to not reaching half of the possible points (SR and MR), to rather positive outcomes (SO). This tendency of scoring higher in SV and SO and lower in SR and MR is consistent for females and males. In the case of the last five areas, results are better than in the first four, especially in VI, FC, PS and OC. In regards to differences in average percentage of correct answers between females and males, boys are slightly better than girls in spatial orientation and significantly in the spatial visualization, spatial relations and mental rotation areas. On the other hand, girls are significantly better than boys in the visualization, form constancy and object combination areas. Boys tend to perform better in the first four areas, while girls do in the last five. Differences between boys and girls are more pronounced in mental rotation and less in spatial orientation, position in space and transformation in space.

Age group 3 (13 to 15 years old)

Table 17 and Figure 13 show the results of participants aged 13 to 15 years old in the nine areas of spatial thinking in the RIF platform.

Table 17

Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 13 to 15 years old)

	Total		Females		Males		Diff. ^	p
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S		
SV	65.78	18.03	64.50	17.37	66.66	18.41	2.16	<.001*
SR	52.01	16.48	50.28	16.12	53.17	16.62	2.89	<.001*
MR	57.00	20.44	52.83	19.52	59.77	20.58	6.94	<.001*
SO	76.36	15.56	74.78	15.55	77.47	15.48	2.69	<.001*
VI	90.94	10.58	91.94	8.24	90.10	12.16	1.84	.062
FC	91.73	7.23	92.67	5.64	91.01	8.19	1.66	.103
PS	90.66	10.14	90.90	8.78	90.46	11.13	0.44	.656
TS	78.51	16.59	80.09	16.02	77.17	16.97	2.92	.072
OC	90.50	7.29	90.92	7.02	90.22	7.48	0.70	.533

^Diff.: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that area between females and males.

*Statistically significant.

Figure 13

Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 13 to 15

In the first four areas, results are rather satisfactory, being lower in SR and MR and higher in SV and SO. In the last five areas, results are in all cases above 90 %, except for TS, where they round 80 %. These data are persistent in females' and males' outcomes. Concerning the differences between both genders, males score significantly higher than females in the first four areas, whereas females outscore boys in the last five areas, though not significantly. Differences between girls and boys are more pronounced in mental rotation and less in visualization, form constancy, position in space and object combination.

Age group 4 (16 to 18 years old)

Table 18 and Figure 14 show the results of participants aged 16 to 18 years old in spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation.

Table 18

Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 16 to 18 years old)

	Total		Females		Males		Diff.^	p
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S		
SV	73.75	18.12	71.86	18.27	74.79	17.97	2.93	.024*
SR	58.83	17.76	58.49	18.03	58.98	17.66	0.49	.733
MR	65.31	21.03	58.84	21.29	68.29	20.25	9.45	<.001*
SO	80.07	17.04	77.91	18.36	81.29	16.16	3.38	.028*

^Diff.: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that area between females and males.

*Statistically significant.

Figure 14

Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 16 to 18

Results tend to be higher in SO and, in decreasing order, in SV, MR and SR, which remains valid for both females and males. Both genders score similarly in spatial relations. However, males significantly outperform females in the other three areas, being the largest difference between them in mental rotation.

Age group 5 (19 to 21 years old)

Table 19 and Figure 15 show the results of participants aged 19 to 21 years old in spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation.

Table 19

Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 19 to 21 years old)

	Total		Females		Males		Diff.^	p
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S		
SV	78.86	14.59	79.98	12.68	76.03	18.35	3.95	.034*
SR	65.73	16.85	66.55	16.05	63.88	18.44	2.67	.148
MR	72.27	18.27	73.40	16.73	69.39	21.54	4.01	.080
SO	86.71	11.31	87.24	10.87	85.05	12.50	2.19	.150

^Diff.: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that area between females and males.

*Statistically significant.

Figure 15

Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 19 to 21

Outcomes of both females and males are higher in SV and SO and lower in SR and MR. In terms of gender differences, females outperform males in all the areas, but only significantly in spatial visualization. The largest differences between the two genders are in spatial visualization and mental rotation.

Age group 6 (+21 years old)

Table 20 and Figure 16 show the results of participants above 21 years old in spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation.

Table 20

Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group over 21 years old)

	Total		Females		Males		Diff.^	p
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S		
SV	69.49	18.73	70.53	17.51	68.22	20.09	2.31	.105
SR	57.99	19.04	60.34	18.45	55.27	19.38	5.07	.001*
MR	64.80	21.74	65.90	21.05	63.46	22.51	2.44	.188
SO	80.40	17.59	81.78	16.77	78.78	18.41	3.00	.043*

^Diff.: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that area between females and males.

*Statistically significant.

Figure 16

Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from 21 years old

Results are generally higher in SO, lowering through SV, MR and SR. In regards to differences in outcomes between females and males, females outperform males in all the areas, but only significantly in spatial relations and spatial orientation. The largest differences between the two genders are in spatial relations.

Total number of participants

The following section shows the results of the total number of participants in the nine areas of spatial thinking.

Table 21 and Figures 17 and 18 show the results of all participants in the nine areas of spatial thinking in the RIF platform.

Table 21

Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (total number of participants)

	Total		Females		Males		Diff.^	p
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	%	
SV	66.42	18.43	65.58	17.94	67.05	18.76	1.47	<.001*
SR	53.22	17.20	52.36	17.31	53.84	17.10	1.48	<.001*
MR	58.65	20.93	55.71	20.62	60.80	20.90	5.09	<.001*
SO	77.07	15.82	76.19	15.88	77.76	15.74	1.57	<.001*
VI	89.45	10.83	90.54	9.67	88.34	11.79	2.2	.001*
FC	88.45	10.17	89.08	9.95	87.90	10.35	1.18	.139
PS	88.92	11.30	89.48	10.06	88.39	12.35	1.09	.135
TS	78.44	15.83	79.47	15.12	77.43	16.45	2.03	.052
OC	90.39	8.35	91.22	8.49	89.64	8.16	1.58	.043

^Diff.: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that area between females and males.

*Statistically significant.

Figure 17

Average percentage of correct answers in SV, SR, MR and SO per gender from all participants

Figure 18

Average percentage of correct answers in VI, FC, PS, TS and OC per gender from all participants

In the first four areas, results are higher in SV and SO and lower in SR and MR. Males significantly outscore females in the four areas. Results in the last five areas are higher than in

the previous four, except for TS, whose results are similar to SO. Females outscore males in the five areas, however only significantly in visualization. Differences in the percentage of correct answers between both genders are considerably larger in mental rotation in comparison to the other areas.

Results in each area across age groups by gender

In this subsection, results of each age group in the nine categories are compared to analyse how outcomes vary through age by gender.

Figure 19 shows the average percentage of correct answers of females in each age group in the nine categories.

Figure 19

Females' average percentage of correct answers in each area per age group

In the first four areas, results tend to improve with age from 10 to 21 years old. However, results of the age group 6 (+21) are lower than those from 19 to 21, being closer to age group 4 (16 to 18). In the case of the last five areas, results improve with age, being similar from 10 to 15. In OC, results are similar in the three age groups.

Figure 20 displays the average percentage of correct answers of males in each age group in the nine categories.

Figure 20

Males' average percentage of correct answers in each area per age group

In the first four areas, results tend to improve with age from 10 to 21 years old. However, results of the age group 6 (+21) are lower than those from 16 to 18. In the case of the last five areas, results improve with age, being similar from 10 to 15. In OC, results are similar in the three age groups.

Results per area

In this subsection, females' and males' results in in each age group are compared in each category.

Spatial visualization. Figure 21 presents females' and males' average percentage of correct answers in spatial visualization in each age group.

Figure 21

Average percentage of correct answers in the spatial visualization area per age group by gender

Results of both genders are similar across ages and tend to improve until the age of 21, when they start decreasing. Females reach their peak at the ages 19 to 21, while males do at 16 to 18. Males' outcomes are slightly above females' from ages 10 to 18, from when females marginally outscore males.

Spatial relations. Figure 22 presents females' and males' average percentage of correct answers in spatial relations in each age group.

Figure 22

Average percentage of correct answers in the spatial relations area per age group by gender

Females' and males' results remain similar across ages, only males scoring slightly higher than females from 10 to 15 and females higher than males from 19 to +21. Results of both groups improve until the age of 21, when they start decreasing. Both females and males reach their peak at 19 to 21.

Mental rotation. Figure 23 presents females' and males' average percentage of correct answers in mental rotation in each age group.

Figure 23

Average percentage of correct answers in the mental rotation area per age group by gender

Results of both genders tend to improve until the ages of 19 to 21, when they start decreasing. Males stay more stable from 16 to 21, while females have a significant improvement from age group 16-18 to 19-21. Gender differences favouring males are consistent from 10 to 18 years old. However, in the age group 19-21 tables are turned and females outscore males.

Spatial orientation. Figure 24 presents females' and males' average percentage of correct answers in spatial orientation in each age group.

Figure 24

Average percentage of correct answers in the spatial orientation area per age group by gender

Females' and males' results are similar through all age groups. Both genders improve with age until 21, from where results start to lower. Both reach their peak at 19-21, though males' improvement is more stable, while females improve more from 16-18 to 19-21 years old.

Visualization. Figure 25 presents females’ and males’ average percentage of correct answers in visualization in each age group.

Figure 25

Average percentage of correct answers in the visualization area per age group by gender

Results of both groups are almost identical across ages, although females tend to score slightly higher than males. Outcomes tend to marginally improve with age.

Form constancy. Figure 26 presents females' and males' average percentage of correct answers in form constancy in each age group.

Figure 26

Average percentage of correct answers in the form constancy area per age group by gender

Both genders score similarly in all age groups and tend to improve their results with age. Males outscore females minimally in the age group from 7 to 9, while females do in the other two age groups.

Position in space. Figure 27 presents females' and males' average percentage of correct answers in position in space in each age group.

Figure 27

Average percentage of correct answers in the position in space area per age group by gender

Results of both genders are very similar in all cases, improving more notoriously from 7 to 12, from where it stays more stable. Females slightly outscore males in the three age groups.

Transformation in space. Figure 28 presents females' and males' average percentage of correct answers in transformation in space in each age group.

Figure 28

Average percentage of correct answers in the transformation in space area per age group by gender

Results of both groups are almost identical, improving from 7 to 12. In the case of males, results decrease from 12 to 15 and stay stable in the case of females.

Object combination. Figure 29 presents females' and males' average percentage of correct answers in object combination in each age group.

Figure 29

Average percentage of correct answers in the object combination area per age group by gender

Results of both genders tend to minimally decrease with age. Though their outcomes are rather similar, females marginally outscore males.

Discussion

This study reports an evaluation of the online spatial thinking RIF platform. The aims were to assess participants' results in each area in different age groups and establish whether there were gender differences in any of the nine areas. The study was guided by the following hypothesis:

H1: Participant's outcomes in the categories spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation are lower than in the categories visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combination.

H1.1: Participant's outcomes tend to improve with age.

H2: There are no significant differences in the areas of spatial thinking trained in the platform except for mental rotation.

H2.2: Differences between females and males are larger between the ages of 12 to 18.

We analysed results of 41664 online participants (18056 females and 23608 males) in 50 task groups divided into nine areas of spatial thinking.

Results in the nine areas are in line with expectations and previous research (Maresch et al., 2023), as the first four areas (SV, SR, MR and SO) show lower outcomes and the last five (VI, FC, PS, TS and OC) higher, in accordance with their difficulty and the age they were designed for. Participants' outcomes tend to improve with age, both males and females reaching their peak at age group 5 (19 to 21). However, from that age onward, results lower, being similar or below the outcomes of the age group 4 (16 to 18). These findings lead to accepting Hypothesis 1 and partially accept Hypothesis 1.1, as, although outcomes improve with age, they lower from the age of 21.

When looking into gender differences, results have shown that there are strong variations depending on the age groups. In the age group 1 (7 to 9), there are no significant gender differences in any of the areas. In the age group 2 (10 to 12), boys significantly outscore girls in SV, SR and MR, while girls do in VI, FC and OC. In the age group 3 (13 to 15), boys perform significantly better than girls in the four first areas (SV, SR, MR and SO). In the age group 4 (16 to 18), boys outscore girls in three of the first four areas (SV, MR and SO). From this age, tables are turned, and in the first four areas, girls outscore boys being this difference significant in SV for the age group 5 (19 to 21) and in SC and SO in the age group 6 (+21). When considering all the participants, boys significantly outscore girls in the first four areas and girls do in VI. In general, boys from 10 to 18 perform better than girls in the four areas, and from 19 years old onwards, it is girls who perform better than boys in the same areas. In the case of the last five areas, girls tend to slightly perform better than boys. Even though the variation between females' and males' performance is in occasions statistically significant, the difference in

percentage of correct answers is, in all cases except for mental rotation, below 4 %. Therefore, the area with the largest gender differences, results show that girls and boys differ the most in mental rotation. The difference between the percentage of correct answers between girls and boys (favouring boys) is above 6 % in age groups 2 and 3, and above 9 % in age group 4. Hypothesis 2 is therefore partially accepted as, although the largest gender differences have been found in mental rotation, there are also gender differences in other areas, depending on the age group. Hypothesis 2.2 is partially accepted, since the largest gender differences have been found from ages 10 to 18. These results are consistent with the research conducted by Maresch (2023), where he analysed the results of 12-to-27-year-old participants of the RIF platform and concluded that gender differences were larger between 12 to 17 and the area with the largest differences was mental rotation. In addition to this, there is extensive literature reporting boys outscoring girls in mental rotation tasks (e.g. Vandenberg & Kuse, 1978; Linn & Petterson, 1985; Voyer et al., 1995).

Implications

This study provides further information about the performance of participants of the RIF platform based on age and gender. In terms of age, results in the nine areas of spatial thinking tend to improve, only lowering from the age of 21. Although no final conclusions can be drawn as to why results decrease from that age because of the anonymity of the participants, one possible explanation is the occupation of those participants. We can assume that many of those participants are already in the labour market and many of them might not have been in contact with educational tasks that might resemble the ones in the platform, thus making it more difficult for them to answer correctly.

Regarding gender differences, there are mainly three remarkable outcomes: one, that mental rotation is the area in which there are larger gender differences favouring males from ages 10 to 18; two, that in the areas of spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial

orientation, males outscore females between the ages 10 to 18; and three, that females outscore males in those areas from the age of 19. In the case of mental rotation, these gender differences have been largely reported. It is hypothesized that those gender differences might be influenced by the way the objects are represented, which is examined in the following chapter.

As for the other areas, several factors might have had an impact in the outperformance of males until the age of 18, such as their familiarity with those types of tasks that might resemble more stereotypically male toys and videogames, their confidence, or biological factors, as they coincide with the adolescence ages.

Regarding the outperformance of females from the age of 19 onwards, it could also have been influenced by biological factors. In addition, one plausible explanation could be interest: many participants in school and high-school years might have been encouraged by their teachers to solve the tasks. However, participants that are already outside of compulsory education might have solved the tasks because of personal interest, which might be related to their abilities.

Further research is needed to clarify these results, in which more information about the participants should be collected (e.g., occupation, education level, educational field, etc.).

As for the other five areas (i.e., visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combination), differences between females' and males' results are virtually inexistent (only females outscoring males in some cases). This might have been caused by different aspects, such as a lower level of difficulty or the design of the tasks (which is more artistic, including more colours, shapes and figures), to which girls might have been able to identify more closely with. Moreover, also the age of the participants might have influenced, as only data from 7 to 12 has been collected. Further research is needed to understand these outcomes.

This data not only is significant to get a broader picture of RIF, but also contributes to the body of literature related to gender differences in spatial thinking. These findings shed more light about the topic of spatial thinking skills, suggesting that they can be developed through age. It is therefore senseful to provide tools and materials to train them from a young age, to reach the highest potential of students. Moreover, gender differences in mental rotation tasks should be further analysed with the aim of reducing them.

The outcomes of this chapter add to the rationale of the following chapters, in which we will study (1) the effects of using different types of representations in mental rotation tasks to improve students' results and reduce gender differences; and (2) the impact of animated feedback in students' learning outcomes when using the RIF platform.

Chapter 6: Effects of Using Different Types of Representations in Mental Rotation

Tasks

Introduction

In chapter 2, it was observed that among the nine areas of spatial thinking trained in the RIF platform, mental rotation was the one that showed larger and consistent gender differences favoring males, between the ages of 10 and 18.

Previous research on the topic, as addressed in chapter 2, suggest that gender differences in mental rotation tasks might be a product of the way in which the objects are represented. For instance, the absence of natural cues, such as light and shadow, might hinder the interpretation of what test-takers are seeing (Bartlett & Camba, 2023; Fisher et al., 2018).

This chapter deals with the results of an experimental study aimed at analyzing the effects of using different types of representations in mental rotation tasks and its impact in gender differences. The results of participants (N = 1077; 476 females and 601 males) between the ages of 10 and 18 obtained in each type of representation were compared to the classic stimuli employed in mental rotation tasks to establish whether more realistic types of representations can improve students' outcomes. Moreover, females' and males' results were compared to determine if these new types of representations can reduce or eliminate gender differences in the performance of mental rotation tasks. We also gathered information about learners' preference for type of representation. The chapter begins with the formulation of the research questions and hypothesis, followed by a description of the methods used to collect and analyse data, and concludes with the presentation of the results and discussion of the findings.

Research Questions and Research Hypothesis

This research intends to provide further information about the effects that more realistic types of representations can have in mental rotation tasks performance and gender differences.

Following, the research questions of this study are presented:

1. Does the use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks help to improve students' outcomes?

1.1. Do they have a different effect in females' and males' outcomes?

1.2. Does the use of more realistic types of representations in tasks similar to the ones in the MRT-Test help improve students' outcomes?

2. Can the use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks decrease or eliminate gender differences?

2.1. Can gender differences be reduced or eliminated in the tasks similar to the MRT-Test when using more realistic types of representations?

3. Which type of representation do girls and boys prefer?

3.1. Is there a link between preference for type of representation and performance in the assessment instrument?

Derived from these research questions, the study is guided by the following hypothesis:

H1: The use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks improve students' outcomes.

H1.1: The use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks have a more positive effect in females' outcomes than males'.

H1.2: The use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks specially improves students' outcomes in MRT-like tasks.

H2: The use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks reduces gender differences.

H2.1: The use of more realistic types of representations reduces gender differences in MRT-like tasks.

H3: Both girls and boys prefer the rendered representation of the objects.

H3.1: Participants who liked the rendered representation performed better in the tasks.

Method

Design

In this study, a quantitative research based on an experimental design was carried out to compare the effects of using different types of representations in students' outcomes in mental rotation tasks and its impact on gender differences in mental rotation. We compared the results of three different types of representations (Figure 30): (2) grey-shaded, (3) colored, and (4) rendered) to the (1) classic representation used in the RIF platform, which mimics the one employed in the MRT-Test.

Figure 30

The four types of representation used in the study

Participants accessed the assessment instrument through a link posted on the website <https://geometriedidaktik.at/>. Moreover, an invitation to teachers to participate in the study was posted in the ADG-Newsletter (Österreichischer Fachverband der Geometrie). Information about their gender, their age and date of birth was collected. This former, although might seem

redundant, was used to verify the age of participants, as some might enter a random number instead of their real age.

Participants

A group of 1077 students (476 females and 601 males, $M_{\text{age}} = 13.85$; $SD = 1.352$, age range: 10-18 years old) from Austria took part in the study. Data have been divided into four age groups: 10-12 years old ($n = 97$; 47 females and 50 males); 13-14 years old ($n = 749$; 338 females and 411 males); 15-16 years old ($n = 158$; 58 females and 100 males); and 17-18 years old ($n = 73$; 33 females and 40 males).

Instruments

This study was developed using a 28-question assessment instrument (see Annex 5) that included seven tasks of each type of representation (see Figure 30 above). Moreover, there were five different types of tasks, all aimed at practicing mental rotation skills. Figures 31 to 35 show an example task of the five different types of tasks.

Figure 31

Task type 1

English translation: You are looking at three figures of exactly the same series of cubes and at one figure of a different series of cubes. Click on the figure with the different series of cubes.

Figure 32

Task type 2

English translation: The figure on the right side shows the left cube in a different position. Tick off around which axis the cube has been rotated by 90° - the x, y, or z axis.

Figure 33

Task type 3

English translation: The given object has been rotated around the y axis from its start position. Click on the correct figure.

Figure 34

Task type 4

English translation: Around which coordinate axis has the cube been rotated once? Click on the correct box.

Figure 35

Task type 5

English translation: The drawings depict wooden cubes of which several corners in all cases have been milled out.

Only two of these cubes are identical. Which ones? Click on the correct images. Hint: Hidden cube corners are not milled out.

For the task type 1, there were a total of 12 tasks, three per type of representation. For tasks types 2, 3, 4 and 5 there were one per type of representation (total of 16 tasks). The rationale behind this is that we wanted to perform a further analysis on the effects of using different types of representation in this type of task, as they resemble the ones used in the MRT-Test.

A preliminary analysis of results showed a high internal consistency of the assessment instrument ($\alpha = .839$). However, we found that in the task type 5, results in the rendered version ($\alpha = .52$) were largely distant from the other versions (classic: $\alpha = .72$; grey-shaded: $\alpha = .79$; color: $\alpha = .78$). Moreover, feedback received from teachers confirmed that students had problems understanding the rendered version of this type of task and that even them (teachers) could not easily get to the right answer. After further analysis of the task and deliberation, it was decided to delete this type of task, as the rendered version was designed with a higher difficulty than the other versions and, therefore, comparisons were not equitable.

The assessment instrument was thus compound of 24 questions (six per type of representation) of the task types 1, 2, 3 and 4. A new reliability analysis was conducted using a Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which indicated a high level of consistency within the tasks ($\alpha = .851$).

At the end of the assessment, participants answered one question about their preference for the four types of representations (Figure 36).

Figure 36

Question about preference for type of representation

Beantworte diese Frage:

	Modell ohne Farbe und nur mit Kanten	Grau schattiert	Modell mit Farben	Gerenderte Modelle
Welche Darstellungsform hat dir am besten gefällt?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

English translation: Answer this question: Which type of representation did you like best? Answer options: Model without color and only with edges; gray-shaded; model with colors; rendered model.

Tasks development

All the tasks that use the classic representation are directly extracted from the RIF platform. In the case of the tasks illustrated with the other three types of representations, they were either adapted from RIF-tasks that were in the classic version to a different type of representation or new figures were created using the RIF-tasks as reference, as in some cases, there were not enough tasks for a task type. The new figures were created using the Bentley-CAD (computer aided design) software, MicroStation.

Data analysis

The results of participants in each type of representation were compared using the Mann & Whitney U-Test and the Wilcoxon-Test. The following analysis were carried out in total (N = 1077) and within each age group:

- Differences between females and males in the average percentage of correct answers in each type of representation;
- Differences within gender in the average percentage of correct answers in each type of representation;
- Differences between females and males in the average percentage of correct answers in each type of task;
- Differences within gender in the average percentage of correct answers in each type of tasks;
- Differences between females and males in the average percentage of correct answers in each type of representation in the task type 1;
- Differences within gender in the average percentage of correct answers in each type of representation in the task type 1.

Results between age groups have also been compared.

In regards to the question at the end of the assessment instrument, the following analysis have been performed:

- Preference for type of representation within gender by age group;
- Correlation between preference for type of representation and average percentage of correct answers in the assessment instrument.

As the data were collected from online participants, some filter criteria were established to eliminate those that could have provided unserious information. The following filters were adopted:

- Time filter: participants who solved the assessment instrument in less than 7 min. 2 sec. (percentile 5);
- Percentage of correct answers filter: results equal and below 33.33 % were discarded. This percentage corresponds to 8 correct answers (out of 24), which means having less than a third of correct answers.

Additionally, answers from participants older than 19 ($n = 21$) were deleted, as the sample was too small in comparison to the other age groups. Participants who selected “other” in the gender question were also removed, as they corresponded to 3.5 % of the total number of participants and comparisons with the two other genders were not viable.

Results

The distribution of the variables was assessed, and it was found that the data did not follow a normal distribution ($p < .001$), as determined by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. Hence, non-parametric assessment instruments such as the Mann & Whitney U-Test and Wilcoxon-Test were employed for data analysis.

In the following section, we are going to present the results of the study divided in five parts: total number of participants; age group 1 (10 to 12); age group 2 (13 to 14); age group 3 (15 to 16); and age group 4 (17 to 18).

Total number of participants

Results of the total number of participants are presented below.

Results per type of representation. Results of the average percentage of correct answers in the whole assessment instrument and in each of the four types of representations have been compared within and between genders to establish whether more realistic types of representations can improve participants’ outcomes in mental rotation tasks and reduce gender differences (Table 22).

Table 22

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{x}	s	Diff _F	\bar{x}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	70.94	22.75	-	79.06	22.01	-	.001	8.12
Grey-Shaded	72.69	24.47	+1.65	79.31	22.34	+0.25	.002	6.62
Colored	67.40	23.55	-3.54	76.76	22.44	-2.3	<.001	9.36
Rendered	73.77	23.23	+2.83	82.22	21.23	+3.16	.005	8.45
Total	71.20	19.77	-	79.34	18.86	-	<.001	-

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Both females and males improve their performance when practicing with the grey-shaded and the rendered version, however, the colored figures decrease their percentage of correct answers in comparison to the classic ones. Males significantly outscore females in the whole assessment instrument and in each of the four types of representations. Gender differences are only reduced in the grey-shaded version, though the best results of both females and males are in the rendered version.

Table 23 shows the significance of the difference between the percentages of correct answers of the grey-shaded, colored and rendered representations in comparison to the classic representation.

Table 23

Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version

	Classic/Grey-shaded	Classic/Color	Classic/Render
Females	.500	<.001	<.001

Males	.954	<.001	<.001
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Results in the rendered version are significantly better than results in the classic version, whereas the colored version significantly decreases the percentage of correct answers in comparison to the classic. Differences between the classic and grey-shaded figures are not significant.

Results per type of task. Table 24 shows the outcomes of females and males in each type of task.

Table 24

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender

	Females		Males		p
	\bar{X}	s	\bar{X}	s	
Task type 1	81.55	18.32	86.33	17.21	<.001
Task type 2	63.29	34.04	72.55	33.03	<.001
Task type 3	63.13	33.50	71.71	33.18	<.001
Task type 4	59.61	33.65	69.68	30.67	<.001

Both females and males score higher in the task type 1 and lower in the task type 4. Males significantly outscore females in all the task types, though the difference in average percentage of correct answers between the two is smaller in the task type 1 (4.78 %) than in the other three task types (task type 2: 9.26 %; task type 3: 8.58 %; task type 4: 10.07 %).

Results per type of representation in task type 1. Table 25 shows the average percentage of correct answers per type of representation by gender in the task type 1.

Table 25

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type 1

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{X}	s	Diff _F	\bar{X}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	80.60	25.58	-	84.97	24.14	-	.001	4.37
Grey-shaded	79.69	27.59	-0.91	84.58	24.77	-0.39	.002	4.89
Colored	68.91	27.61	-11.69	76.71	26.05	-8.26	<.001	7.8
Rendered	89.57	22.18	+8.97	92.73	19.55	+7.76	.005	3.16

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Both females and males score higher in the rendered version than in the classic one. Gender differences are thus reduced in the rendered version. On the contrary, their outcomes are considerably lower in the colored version and slightly (almost identical) in the grey-shaded in comparison to the classic version. Males, however, significantly outscore females in all cases.

Age group 1 (10-12 years old)

Results of participants between 10 to 12 years old are presented below.

Results per type of representation. Table 26 displays the results of participants in each type of representation by gender. Moreover, it shows the difference between the average percentage of correct answers in each type of representation and the classic version within gender, and the differences in each type of representation between genders.

Table 26

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{x}	s	Diff _F	\bar{x}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	66.31	21.28	-	74.67	21.62	-	.062	8.36
Grey-shaded	69.15	21.13	+2.84	74.67	23.14	0	.199	5.52
Colored	65.96	24.07	-0.35	71.33	22.60	-3.33	.339	5.37
Rendered	70.21	22.51	+3.9	72.67	25.37	-2	.493	2.46
Total	67.91	17.61	-	73.33	20.13	-	.153	-

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Females score higher in the grey-shaded and the rendered version and lower in the colored version in comparison to the classic. Males, on the other hand, do not improve their results with any of the three types of representation: they score equally in the classic and the grey-shaded version and lower in the colored and rendered version. Although males score higher than females in all cases, differences in the percentage of correct answers between the two groups are not significant in any case. Moreover, as girls improve their results with the grey-shaded and rendered versions, gender differences are reduced in both cases, especially in the rendered version. Though they are also smaller in the colored version, the cause is that both females' and males' results are worse.

Table 27 shows the significance of the difference between the percentages of correct answers of the grey-shaded, colored and rendered representations in comparison to the classic representation by gender.

Table 27

Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version

	Classic/Grey-shaded	Classic/Color	Classic/Render
Females	.168	.165	.002
Males	.856	.203	.142

Differences between the percentages of correct answers in each type of representation within gender are only significant in the case of females' results in the rendered version in comparison to the classic version.

Results per type of task. Table 28 shows the outcomes of females and males in each type of task.

Table 28

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender

	Females		Males		p
	\bar{X}	s	\bar{X}	s	
Task type 1	83.87	14.68	84.17	20.01	.321
Task type 2	62.77	34.92	63.50	37.19	.875
Task type 3	60.11	35.61	65.00	36.77	.409
Task type 4	59.57	34.40	65.50	32.30	.399

Females and males score higher in the task type 1. While females score lower in the task type 4, males do in the task type 2. Although males outscore females in all task types, it is not significant, being the difference in the percentage of correct answers between the two, minimal in the task type 1 (0.3 %) and 2 (0.77 %) and slightly wider in the task type 3 (4.89 %) and 4 (5.93 %).

Results per type of representation in task type 1. Table 29 presents the average percentage of correct answers per type of representation by gender in the task type 1.

Table 29

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type 1

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{X}	s	Diff _F	\bar{X}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	79.43	23.62	-	83.33	25.42	-	.270	3.9
Grey-shaded	84.40	21.81	+4.97	82.67	27.14	-0.66	.869	1.73
Colored	71.63	28.64	-7.8	74.67	23.87	-8.66	.750	3.04
Rendered	90.07	20.75	+10.64	88.00	26.73	+4.67	.857	2.07

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Females and males score higher in the rendered version than in the classic version. However, females also improve with the grey-shaded version and worsen with the colored, while males worsen with both the grey-shaded and the colored version in comparison to the classic one. Males outscore females in the classic and colored version, while females outscore males in the grey-shaded and rendered, none being significant. Moreover, females' improvement from the classic to the rendered version is larger (10.66 %) than males' (4.67 %). Gendered differences are not only reduced, but inversed in the grey-shaded and rendered version, where females score higher than males.

Age group 2 (13-14 years old)

Results of participants between 13 to 14 years old are presented below.

Results per type of representation. Table 30 displays the results of participants in each type of representation by gender. Moreover, it presents the difference between the average percentage of correct answers in each type of representation and the classic version within gender, and the differences in each type of representation between genders.

Table 30

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{X}	s	Diff _F	\bar{X}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	71.45	22.63	-	78.06	22.40	-	<.001	6.61
Grey-shaded	72.78	24.87	+1.33	78.47	22.71	+0.41	.002	5.69
Colored	66.77	23.29	-4.68	75.59	22.87	-2.47	<.001	8.82
Rendered	74.31	22.75	+2.86	81.51	21.65	+3.45	<.001	7.2
Total	71.33	19.73	-	78.41	19.11	-	<.001	-

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Both females and males improve their results in the rendered version and in the grey-shaded version (though slightly in the latter) compared to the classic representation and lower them in the colored version. Males significantly outscore females in all cases. Though results are improved in the grey-shaded and the rendered version, gender differences only decrease with the grey-shaded representations, where males improve less than females.

Table 31 shows the significance of the difference between the percentages of correct answers of the grey-shaded, colored and rendered representations in comparison to the classic representation.

Table 31

Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version

	Classic/Grey-shaded	Classic/Color	Classic/Render
Females	.117	<.001	.005
Males	.632	.018	<.001

Differences between the results in the rendered and in the classic version are significant for both females and males. Outcomes in the classic version are also significantly better for both groups than in the colored version.

Results per type of task. Table 32 shows the outcomes of females and males in each type of task.

Table 32

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender

	Females		Males		p
	\bar{X}	s	\bar{X}	s	
Task type 1	82.10	17.59	85.34	17.18	<.001
Task type 2	62.57	34.14	70.86	33.47	<.001
Task type 3	62.35	33.48	70.25	33.70	<.001
Task type 4	58.36	33.94	67.64	31.02	<.001

Females and males get the best results in the task type 1 and the worst in the task type 4. Although males significantly outscore females in the four types, differences between them in the task type 1 (3.24 %) are smaller than those in task type 2 (8.29 %), task type 3 (7.90 %) and task type 4 (9.28 %).

Results per type of representation in task type 1. Table 33 presents the average percentage of correct answers per type of representation by gender in the task type 1.

Table 33

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type 1

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{X}	s	Diff _F	\bar{X}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	82.15	24.23	-	83.62	24.79	-	.233	1.47
Grey-shaded	79.09	28.42	-3.06	83.13	25.22	-0.49	.075	4.04
Colored	69.23	27.30	-12.92	75.43	26.42	-8.19	.001	6.2
Rendered	91.03	19.93	+8.88	92.38	19.51	+8.76	.242	1.35

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Females and males improve their results in comparison to the classic version with the rendered version and deteriorate them in the colored version (considerably) and in the grey-shaded version (slightly). Although males outscore females in the four scenarios, the difference is only significant in the colored version. Gender differences are slightly lessened in the rendered version.

Age group 3 (15-16 years old)

Results of participants between 15 to 16 years old are presented below.

Results per type of representation. Table 34 displays the results of participants in each type of representation by gender. Moreover, it presents the difference between the average percentage of correct answers in each type of representation and the classic version within gender, and the differences in each type of representation between genders.

Table 34

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{X}	s	Diff _F	\bar{X}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	65.23	25.23	-	80.83	22.39	-	<.001	15.6
Grey-shaded	67.82	24.95	+2.59	81.17	22.18	+0.34	<.001	13.35
Colored	63.79	23.39	-1.44	79.17	21.50	-1.66	<.001	15.38
Rendered	68.96	26.94	+3.73	85.67	17.57	+4.84	<.001	16.71
Total	66.45	21.04	-	81.71	18.11	-	<.001	-

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Though females' and males' results are higher in the rendered and the grey-shaded version than in the classic, gender differences are only reduced with the grey-shaded representations, as boys' improvement is lower than females', as opposed to the rendered version. Outcomes with the colored representations are lower than with the classic. Males significantly outscore females in all cases.

Table 35 shows the significance of the difference between the percentages of correct answers of the grey-shaded, colored and rendered representations in comparison to the classic representation.

Table 35

Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version

	Classic/Grey-shaded	Classic/Color	Classic/Render
Females	.407	.485	.230
Males	.935	.322	.011

Differences between results are only significant between the classic and rendered version for males.

Results per type of task. Table 36 shows the outcomes of females and males in each type of task.

Table 36

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender

	Females		Males		p
	\bar{X}	s	\bar{X}	s	
Task type 1	73.85	21.99	89.25	16.21	<.001
Task type 2	56.03	34.19	79.00	29.02	<.001
Task type 3	59.48	33.06	76.50	30.32	<.001
Task type 4	53.44	31.57	74.50	29.30	<.001

Although males significantly outscore females in all task types, both genders get better results in the task type 1 and worse in the task type 4. Differences between the percentage of correct answers between females and males are rather large in the four types of tasks, but it is in the type 1 where they are the smallest (type 1: 15.4 %; type 2: 22.97 %; type 3: 17.02 %; type 4: 21.06 %).

Results per type of representation in task type 1. Table 377 displays the average percentage of correct answers per type of representation by gender in the task type 1.

Table 37

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type 1

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{x}	s	Diff _F	\bar{x}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	68.97	33.55	-	88.33	21.90	-	<.001	19.36
Grey-shaded	75.86	27.78	+6.89	89.67	22.07	+1.34	<.001	13.81
Colored	59.20	25.78	-9.77	79.33	27.54	-9	<.001	20.13
Rendered	82.18	29.43	+13.22	95.33	19.10	+7	<.001	13.15

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Both females and males score higher in the grey-shaded and the rendered version and lower in the colored version compared to the classic version. Though males significantly outscore females in all types of representation, differences between them are smaller in the rendered (13.15 %) and grey-shaded (13.81 %) than in the colored (20.13 %) and classic (19.36 %) versions. Moreover, girls' improvement rate in the rendered and grey versions are considerably larger than boys'.

Age group 4 (17-18 years old)

Results of participants between 17 to 18 years old are presented below.

Results per type of representation. Table 38 presents the results of participants in each type of representation by gender. Moreover, it presents the difference between the average percentage of correct answers in each type of representation and the classic version within gender, and the differences in each type of representation between genders.

Table 38

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{X}	s	Diff _F	\bar{X}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	82.32	16.63	-	90.42	11.87	-	.025	8.1
Grey-shaded	85.35	19.88	+3.03	89.17	13.89	-1.25	.774	3.82
Colored	82.32	21.22	0	89.58	13.96	-0.84	.196	7.26
Rendered	81.82	20.14	-0.5	92.92	11.87	+2.5	.009	11.1
Total	82.95	16.48	-	90.52	9.76	-	.094	-

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Females' results improve with the grey-shaded representations, stay stable with the colored and slightly decrease with the rendered. Males, on the other hand, only improve with the rendered version and slightly worsen with the grey-shaded and colored ones. Although males outscore females, differences are only significant in the classic and the rendered versions. Gender differences are diminished in the grey-shaded and colored version, in both cases scoring males lower than they do in the classic.

Table 39 shows the significance of the difference between the percentages of correct answers of the grey-shaded, colored and rendered representations in comparison to the classic representation.

Table 39

Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version

	Classic/Grey-shaded	Classic/Color	Classic/Render
Females	.373	.717	.930
Males	.956	.755	.115

In no case are the differences in results between the different types of representations significant for females nor males.

Results per type of task. Table 40 shows the outcomes of females and males in each type of task.

Table 40

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender

	Females		Males		p
	\bar{x}	s	\bar{x}	s	
Task type 1	86.11	20.38	91.88	14.68	.289
Task type 2	84.09	23.23	85.00	27.03	.502
Task type 3	81.81	25.98	83.13	26.18	.773
Task type 4	83.33	23.11	83.75	23.03	.862

Both females and males score higher in the task type 1 and similarly in the other three task types. Males outscore females not significantly. Differences between the percentage of correct answers between genders are larger in the task type 1 (5.77 %) than in the others: type 2: 0.91 %; type 3: 1.32 %; type 4: 0.42 %.

Results per type of representation in task type 1. Table 41 presents the average percentage of correct answers per type of representation by gender in the task type 1.

Table 41

Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type 1

	Females			Males			p	Diff _{FM}
	\bar{x}	s	Diff _F	\bar{x}	s	Diff _M		
Classic	86.87	20.31	-	92.50	19.22	-	.121	5.63
Grey-shaded	85.86	25.04	-1.01	89.17	21.86	-3.33	.575	3.31
Colored	78.79	28.65	-8.08	85.83	18.31	-6.67	.466	7.04
Rendered	86.87	28.79	0	95.83	13.48	+3.33	.157	8.96

Diff_F: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the females group.

Diff_M: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation and the classic representation in the males group.

Diff_{FM}: difference between the average percentage of correct answers in that type of representation between females and males.

Females score equally in the classic and the rendered version and decrease their percentage of correct answers in the grey-shaded and the colored versions. Males also worsen in these two latter versions, but improve with the rendered representations. Although males score higher than females, differences are not significant. Gender differences are reduced in the grey-shaded version, being the reason that both genders lower their scores.

Differences between age groups

Results of females and males in each age group have been compared to establish whether there are differences between their outcomes.

Differences between age groups by age group in the four types of representations.

Figure 37 displays the differences in average percent of correct answers between females in the four age groups in the four types of representations.

Figure 37

Females' average percentage of correct answers per type of representation per age group

Females participants show an improvement in results from the age group 1 to the age group 2. Outcomes considerably sink at the ages of 15 and 16 and then experience a large rise at the ages of 17 and 18. In terms of the types of representation, from 10 to 16, they get better results in the rendered version and grey-shaded in comparison to the classic. The improvement rate is similar in the three age groups. The colored representation is the one with which they score the lowest. In contrast, girls between 17 and 18 get similar results in the classic, colored and rendered version and only improve with the grey-shaded version.

Figure 38 presents the differences in average percent of correct answers between males in the four age groups in the four types of representations.

Figure 38

Males' average percentage of correct answers per type of representation per age group

Males show a constant improvement of results through age, being the difference between 15-to-16-year-olds and 17-to-18-year-olds the largest. In all age groups, except for the first, they get the better results with the rendered version, being the 15-to-16-year-olds the ones with the largest improvement rate. The colored version caused a decrease in results in all age groups, though the older participants also worsened with the grey-shaded.

Differences between age groups in the four types of tasks. Figure 39 displays the differences in average percent of correct answers between females in the four age groups in the four types of tasks.

Figure 39

Females' average percentage of correct answers per type of task per age group

Females in all age groups score higher in the task type 1, being the difference between task type 1 and the other task types larger in the first three age groups (10 to 16). Results of 17-to-18-year-olds are more stable, showing higher skills than the younger participants in all task types.

Figure 40 displays the differences in average percent of correct answers between males in the four age groups in the four types of tasks.

Figure 40

Males' average percentage of correct answers per type of task per age group

Males' results are in all cases higher in the task type 1, however, differences between the results in the four types of tasks decrease through age.

Differences between ages groups in the four types of representations in task type

1. Figure 41 displays the differences in average percent of correct answers between females in the four age groups in the four types of representations in the task type 1.

Figure 41

Females' average percentage of correct answers per type of representation per age group in the task type 1

Females from 10 to 14 year old get similar results in the four types of representation. 15-to-16-year-olds get the worst results and 17-to-18-year-olds the best, though not by a large difference between the 10-to-14-year-olds. Girls from 10 to 16 significantly improve their outcomes with the rendered version in comparison to the classic. 15-to-16-year-olds show the largest improvement between the classic and the rendered version. Girls from 17 to 18, on the other hand, have more stable results, scoring similarly in the classic, grey-shaded and rendered version. All age groups worsen their results with the colored version.

Figure 42 displays the differences in average percent of correct answers between males in the four age groups in the four types of representations in the task type 1.

Figure 42

Males' average percentage of correct answers per type of representation per age group in the task type 1

Boys between 10 and 14 score similarly in the four types of representation, only differing slightly in the rendered version. 15-to-18-year-olds also get equivalent results in the grey-shaded and rendered version. In all age groups, the largest improvement is seen in the rendered version, being the 13-to-14-year olds the ones who improve the most. They get the worst results with the colored version.

Comparing both genders, females generally show a larger improvement between the results in the rendered and the classic version, especially in the age groups 10 to 12 and 15 to 16. The improvement rate is almost identical in the age group 13 to 14 and larger in males' older participants, as females do not improve in that age group with the rendered representation.

Preferences for types of representation

In the following figures, we display the preference for the four types of representation by age group for females (Figure 43) and males (Figure 44).

Figure 43

Percentage of female participants in each age group who selected each type of representation

Females in the first three age groups (10-16 years old) tend to prefer the colored version to the other three, being the classic the ones they like the least. This is particularly notorious in girls between 10 and 12, who show an evident preference for the colored version. Girls in age group 3 have a predilection for the rendered representation in comparison to the others.

Figure 44

Percentage of male participants in each age group who selected each type of representation

Males in the three younger age groups (10 to 16 years old) prefer the rendered version to the other three, also being the classic version the ones they prefer less. 17-to-18-year-olds incline themselves for the colored and rendered version in the same extent. The representation they like the least, however, is the grey-shaded.

In Figures 45 and 46 we relate the percentage of correct answers in the assessment instrument with the preference for type of representation.

Figure 45

Correlation between females' average percentage of correct answers in the assessment instrument and preference for type of representation

In all age groups, females who selected the rendered version as their preferred one, score on average higher in the assessment instrument than those we opted for any of the other three types. This is particularly noticeable in the age group of 15 to 16 years old, where, in addition, the lower results were found.

Figure 46

Correlation between males' average percentage of correct answers in the assessment instrument and preference for type of representation

In the case of males, outcomes are more varying depending on the age group. Within the ages 10 to 12 those who opt for the rendered version have a higher average on the percentage of correct answers. In the next age group (13 to 14) it is those who chose the classic version, though the differences are not that large. In the last two age groups (15 to 16 and 17 to 18) results are rather similar in the four options.

Discussion

In this study, an experiment was conducted to compare the effects of using different types of representations in students' outcomes in mental rotation tasks and its impact on gender differences in mental rotation. We tested the following hypothesis:

H1: The use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks improve students' outcomes.

H1.1: The use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks have a more positive effect in females' outcomes than males'.

H1.2: The use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks specially improves students' outcomes in MRT-like tasks.

H2: The use of more realistic types of representations in mental rotation tasks reduces gender differences.

H2.1: The use of more realistic types of representations reduces gender differences in MRT-like tasks.

H3: Both girls and boys prefer the rendered representation of the objects.

H3.1: Participants who liked the rendered representation performed better in the tasks.

In addition to the classic representation used in the RIF platform that mimics the one in the MRT-Test, we designed a grey-shaded, a colored and a rendered version. Learners participating online solving a 24-question assessment instrument that included six tasks per type of representation. There were four different types of mental rotation tasks.

Regarding Hypothesis 1, it was expected that practicing with more realistic types of representations led to better results of females and males. This was confirmed, however, different results were found depending on the age group and gender. Females from 10 to 16 benefit from both the grey-shaded and the rendered representations in comparison to the classic one, while those from 17 to 18 only from the grey-shaded. Males from 13 to 16 also benefit from the grey-shaded and rendered representations and 17- to 18-year-olds only from the rendered. In the case of boys between 10 and 12, they do not get better results with any of the new types of representations. Both genders worsen with the colored representation, except for girls between 17 and 18, who get equal results as in the classic version.

In line with Robert's and Chevrier's (2003) work, providing three-dimensional versions of the objects increased accuracy of responses. It seems that providing more realistic objects might have helped with the analysis of the structure of the figures and the identification of their orientation. On the contrary, in the case of the colored representation, a possible explanation of the worsening of results, is that it provides too much information, distracting from the important one and hence, increasing the cognitive load (Sweller, 1988).

As for Hypothesis 2, it can be partially confirmed; though males consistently overscore females in the four types of representations, differences are only significant in the age groups 2 and 3. In the case of the 17-to-18-year-olds, differences are significant only in the rendered and classic versions. Gender differences are reduced in all age groups with the grey-shaded version. However, this is due to boys either not improving, improving less than girls or worsening their results. In addition, although both females and males score higher in all age groups (except age group 4) with the rendered representations, larger differences have been found from 13 to 18 years old, as males tend to improve their results more than females. In the age group from 10 to 12, gender differences are reduced with the rendered representations. The colored version has also caused a decrease in gender differences, however, this are due to worse results of both genders. These results lead to partially accepting Hypothesis 1.1, as improvement of females and males with more realistic types of representations vary greatly from age and type of representation.

We have found that the task type 1, the one resembling the MRT-Test tasks, is particularly sensitive to using more realistic representations of the objects, which confirms Hypothesis 1.2. In fact, excluding the 17-to-18-year-olds, all age groups benefit considerably from the rendered representations. Moreover, girls from 10 to 12 and 15 to 16 also improve their results with the grey-shaded version in comparison to the classic, as do boys from 15 to 16. In the case of the oldest participants, girls do not benefit from any new type of representation, while boys do with the rendered version. In all cases, the colored representation hinder the practice of mental

rotation tasks, substantially decreasing the percentage of correct answers in comparison to the classic representation. Females seem to benefit more than males from the more realistic types of representation, especially in the 15-to-16-years-old group, which is the one with the largest improvement rate.

In terms of gender differences, Hypothesis 2.1 is accepted, as they are reduced with the rendered representations in the age groups 2 and 3, and reversed in the first age group, as girls outscore boys. They are also reduced in age groups 3 and 4 with the grey-shaded representations, and reversed in age group 1, as boys tend to worsen their results or at least not improve them with this type of representation. The age group 3 is the one with the largest gender differences, while the age group 1 is the one with the smallest or almost inexistent.

Boys outscoring females in mental rotation tasks has been widely reported (Vandenberg & Kuse, 1978; Linn & Petterson, 1985; Voyer et al., 1995). The cases in which gender differences are reduced or eliminated are in line with previous research, that came to the same conclusions with 3D representations of mental rotation stimuli in images (Fisher et al., 2018; Neubauer et al., 2010) or virtual reality (Parsons et al., 2004).

The improvement of females' performance with more realistic types of representations might be explained by the strategies used. Studies show that men are more likely to take risks and use new and creative approaches on problem solving tasks (Gallagher and De Lisi, 1994). In the case of the classic representation, as the figures are difficult to interpret because of their abstractness and lack of natural cues (i.e., light, shadow, depth), different strategies as the ones used in every-day-life mental rotation tasks are needed, for which women might have a disadvantage in comparison to men. However, with the realistic types of representations, such as the grey-shaded or rendered version, those known strategies can be applied, as they are more similar to real-world experiences (Fisher et al., 2018).

As for the results in the four types of tasks, both females and males score higher in the first type of task. From 10 to 16, there is a large difference between the scores in the task type 1 and the

other three task types, while they are almost identical between 17 and 18 years old. Scores in the task type 1 do not experience a lot of variation through age in both genders. Although males outscore females, differences are only significant in the age groups 2 and 3. Moreover, results in the task type 1 are similar between girls and boys in the ages of 10 to 14, highly differing at the ages of 15 to 16 and moderately at the ages of 17 to 18. In the other three task types, results are almost identical between both genders in the oldest age group, highly contrasting from 15 to 16, and slightly different in the youngest age group.

In regards to the preferences per type of representation, Hypothesis 3 is rejected, as there is a clearly predisposition of females from 10 to 16 for the colored representation, which contradicts their results, as this is the type of representation which systematically hinders their performance. Females from 17 to 18, however, tend to prefer the rendered version. Males in all age groups prefer the rendered version over the others, only those between 17 and 18 years old also prefer the colored version to the same degree.

When correlating the preference for type of representation to average mean of results in the whole assessment instrument, Hypothesis 3.1 is partially confirmed, as females in all age groups showed a tendency in which those who scored higher on average, opted for the rendered version. However, males do not show a clear trend. 10-to-12-year-olds with a higher score opted for the rendered version, while 13-to-14-year-olds did for the classic. Results in the two oldest age groups are similar in the four options.

Implications

This study provides new perspectives on gender differences in mental rotation. In short, employing more realistic types of representations, especially those that resemble life-like objects (e.g. rendered images) in mental rotation tasks, has a positive effect in learners' outcomes and can help reduce or eliminate gender differences. On this last point, even when they are not reduced, results of both females and males have generally considerably improved in comparison to the classic type of representation.

These findings have relevant implications in the field, as they provide further evidence that the stimuli used in classical mental rotation tests, such as the MRT by Vandenberg and Kuse (1978), can be biased, causing large gender differences that favour males. Moreover, they indicate that the performance of both females and males can be enhanced by designing mental rotation assessment instruments and practice tasks with more realistic stimuli. Nevertheless, more research on this topic is necessary. As the Shepard and Metzler chronometric test (1971) does not usually show gender differences, it should be examined whether results of females and males improve with more realistic types of stimuli. In addition, further investigation in order to determine the underlying reasons why more realistic types of stimuli might potentially reduce gender differences is needed. Finally, although these results have shed some light into the gender differences in mental rotation topic, we can presume that the realism of objects is not the only variable on which it is dependant, therefore, future studies should focus on exploring additional causes.

These results provide further evidence that training and evaluation materials for spatial thinking should be adapted and developed according to the needs of the test-takers, trying to avoid as much bias as possible. If tasks and tests are designed to only accommodate a group of people, we hinder the improvement and learning from a large part of society.

A limitation of this study was the varying sample of participants on the four age groups, as most of the participants were between 13 and 14 years old. Another limitation was the question about the preference of the type of representation. Although participants informed about which type of representation they prefer, we lack the reason behind it and whether they liked those because of aesthetics or because they found them more helpful to solve the task (presumably the first according to the results).

In the next chapter, the effects of providing animated feedback in students' learning outcomes are assessed, as a way to enhance students' experience with the platform.

Chapter 7: The Impact of Animated Feedback in Spatial Thinking Training Using the RIF Platform

Introduction

Feedback is one of the most powerful tools to improve learning. This is especially significant in online learning environments, where the interactions between instructors and students is highly limited. In the RIF platform, users receive information about the correctness of their answers and the actual correct response. However, they do not get any further data that might assist in their learning process. This chapter reports the results of an experimental study aimed at analysing the impact of using immediate elaborated feedback in the form of videos when practicing with the spatial thinking tasks offered in the RIF platform. In this study, the results of learners (N = 179; 88 females and 91 males) between 10 and 14 years old in two conditions (feedback and no feedback), were compared to determine whether receiving animated feedback improves their learning outcomes. Females' and males' outcomes are contrasted to establish if gender has an influence in the effect of feedback. Moreover, we have also gathered information about learners' confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks, in order to observe the effect of feedback on these topics. The chapter begins with a presentation of the research questions that will guide the research. It is followed by a description of the method used to collect and analyse data and concludes with a summary of results and discussion of the findings.

Research Questions and Hypothesis

The research reported in this study attempts to contribute to the body of literature related to feedback in computer-based environments. More specifically, this study explores the effects of immediate elaborated feedback in the form of animated images (videos) in learners' outcomes in online spatial thinking tasks, and the influence of gender in feedback effects. The research questions that are going to guide this study are presented below.

1. Does immediate elaborated feedback (videos) have a positive effect on students' learning outcomes in online spatial thinking tasks?

1.1. Do low-skilled students benefit more from feedback?

1.2. Which condition (feedback or no-feedback) is more beneficial for girls and for boys?

2. Does feedback have an impact on students' confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks?

2.1. Are there differences between girls and boys on confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks in the two conditions?

From these questions, we formulate the following hypothesis:

H1: Receiving feedback improves students' learning outcomes in online spatial thinking tasks.

H1.1: Low-skilled students benefit more than high-skilled students from feedback.

H1.2: Girls benefit more from the feedback condition, while boys benefit more from the no-feedback condition.

H2: Students who receive feedback show more confidence in their performance and perceive tasks as less difficult.

H2.1: Boys show more confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks when not receiving feedback.

H2.2: When receiving feedback, girls gain more confidence in their performance and perceive tasks as less difficult than boys who receive feedback.

Method

Design

In this study, a quantitative research based on a pre-test and post-test design was employed to compare the effects of providing feedback in the RIF spatial thinking training. This approach has been applied in similar studies exploring the effects of feedback in different areas (Attali & Van der Kleij, 2017).

We compared the results of two conditions administered in the pre-test:

(I) The experimental group received feedback immediately after each answer, which consisted of knowledge of correct response (KCR) and elaborated feedback (EF) in the form of animated videos.

(II) The control group did not obtain any feedback after finishing the pre-test.

Students participated in two ways: (I) online, following a link posted on the website <https://geometriedidaktik.at/>; or (II) in-site, as part of a classroom activity. Online participants randomly completed either the experimental test or the control test depending on when they logged in the website. The two links for the tests were published in different time periods to prevent that the same participants solved both tests. All students that engaged on-site solved the experimental test.

The post-test consisted of a summative assessment, in which students could see the correctness/incorrectness and the percentage of correct answers after answering all the questions.

It was anticipated that after random assignment to the conditions, no disparities would exist among the two groups. Therefore, variations in the groups' scores on the summative assessment could be attributed to the different feedback methods used.

Participants

A group of 179 students (88 females and 91 males, $M_{age} = 12.53$; $SD = 1.239$, age range: 10 to 14) from Austria ($n = 145$) and the Netherlands ($n = 34$) participated in this study. The 145 Austrian participants took the test online, while the 34 from the Netherlands did as an instruction from their teachers. Students from the Dutch school solved the test in English, as they were all from different nationalities and were registered in the International School of Delft. 82 learners solved the experimental test (34 females, 48 males); while 97 the control test (54 females, 43 males).

Instruments

The instruments used in this study were:

- A pre-test;
- A post-test;
- And a questionnaire

Both the pre- and post- test consisted of 18 items that included two tasks of each of the nine areas of spatial thinking offered in the RIF platform (i.e., Visualization, Form Constancy, Position in Space, Transformation in Space, Object Combination, Spatial Visualization, Mental Rotation, Spatial Orientation and Spatial Relations) (see Annex 9). A mix of tasks was used to observe how feedback could assist spatial thinking training as a skill that involves several areas. The type of tasks were multiple choice, drag and drop, hotspot, numeric, true or false and matching. The items from the pre- and post- test were not isomorphic, meaning; they were not the same questions with different objects or figures. This could have caused a training effect, as students could have recalled the tasks and answers from the pre-test. However, the tasks pertain to the same area and require the same strategies to be solved. Therefore, the feedback provided attempts to present students the strategies that can be used to reach the correct answer.

Pre-test

The purpose of the pre-test was to support students' learning process by presenting feedback. Two different conditions were delivered. In the experimental group, students received immediate KCR + EF after answering each item. The EF consisted of a short animation, in which the correct answer was shown and explained both when their answer was right and wrong. Students could skip the animations at any time; hence it was their choice to watch them. Figures 47 and 48 show the screenshots of the feedback that learners received when answer correctly and incorrectly, respectively.

Figure 47

Example of feedback input for correct answers in the experimental pre-test

Figure 48

Example of feedback input for incorrect answers in the experimental pre-test

In the control group, students did not receive any feedback after finishing the pre-test.

Post-test

The post-test was intended to measure the effect of feedback in the learning process. Both groups received the same post-test, in which an overview of the test and the percentage of correct answers were displayed after finishing all the questions. Figure 49 shows the screenshots of the messages that learners receive at the end.

Figure 49

Example of feedback input in the post-test

Questionnaire

Two brief questionnaires were administered using questions adapted from Maier et al. (2016). The first questionnaire (Table 41) was only intended for the experimental group (see Annex 6). Students answered it after completing the pre-test. The aim of this questionnaire was to learn

whether they watched the animation-feedback of their correct and incorrect answers, and how useful they found them. The second questionnaire (Table 42) was directed to both groups (see Annexes 7 and 8). They answered it after solving the post-test. The aim was to observe if receiving animated feedback influenced in students' confidence on their performance, their enjoyment solving the tasks and the perceived difficulty of the tasks. An additional question (Question 4) for the experimental group collected information about their impression of the usefulness of the animations in the pre-test when solving the post-test. The answers were provided through a five-point Likert scale in which: 1 = strongly disagree; 2 = disagree; 3 = more or less; 4 = agree; 5 = strongly agree.

Table 42

Questions in the pre- and post- test questionnaires

Question	Pre-test (only experimental group)	Post-test (experimental and control group)
Q1	I watched all the videos for my correct answers.	I'm pretty good at this kind of tasks.
Q2	I watched all the videos for my wrong answers.	I enjoyed solving these tasks.
Q3	The videos of my correct answers were useful to solve other tasks.	The tasks were easy for me.
Q4	The videos of my wrong answers were useful to understand the tasks better.	The videos for the first 18 tasks helped me to better understand the other tasks in this quiz. <i>(experimental group only)</i>

Feedback development

As reviewed in previous chapters, feedback can address several stages of learning and take many forms. However, the most effective feedback type is that focused on the task that provides students with further useful information (elaborated feedback) to successfully solve new tasks.

Given the dynamic nature of the tasks used in this study, designing feedback that visually showed the correct answer of the tasks in form of short videos, seemed to be the most appropriate way to approach this issue. Therefore, for each task, we developed an animated image that displayed the right answer and, when possible, an example of a strategy that could be used to solve it. The rationale behind this is that, although there are numerous angles from which a spatial task can be approached and the source of an incorrect answer can be varied, showing a valid strategy can help learners bridge the gap between where they are and where they want to be.

The figures for the videos were created using the Bentley Systems CAD software *MicroStation* (for the 3D-figures) or PowerPoint (for the 2D-figures). The videos were then built using the Windows application *MakeAVI*, in which a series of images can be assembled to create a time-lapse movie. They last between 3 and 14 seconds and can be stopped, close and fast-forwarded at any time. Figure 50 shows a shortened example of the development of a video:

Figure 50

Example of development of feedback videos

Procedure

The pre- and post-test were administered immediately after each other; otherwise, the scores on the post-test could have been influenced by some intervention other than the feedback. Moreover, we wanted to simulate the way a participant would normally use the platform, so

providing feedback in a longer time-lapse would not be suitable, as we do not know how frequently they would be using it. Students in the experimental group solved the pre-test, then answered four questions, solved the post-test and answered the last part of the questionnaire. Students in the control group solved the 36 tasks and the questionnaire at the end. The three groups could revise the correctness of their answers and the correct answers at the end of the intervention.

Data analysis

The effects of feedback were calculated using the Mann & Whitney U-Test and the Wilcoxon-Test. The following analysis were carried out:

- Feedback effects:
 - Differences between the experimental and the control group in the pre- and post-test;
 - Differences between females in the experimental and control group in the pre- and post- test;
 - Differences between males in the experimental and control group in the pre- and post- test.

- Impact on gender:
 - Differences between females and males in the control group;
 - Differences between females and males in the experimental group.

The same analysis were performed, using only the results from participants in the quartile 1 of percentage of correct answers in the pre-test, as those who have lower skills are more likely to benefit more from elaborated feedback (Shute, 2008).

The questionnaire provided relevant information about participants' confidence in their performance and perception of the tasks (enjoyment and difficulty), as well as use of the videos and their thoughts on their usefulness, in the case of the experimental group. The following analysis were conducted:

- Questionnaire 1 (only experimental group):
 - Proportion of participants that have watched the videos of their correct answers;
 - Proportion of participants that have watched the videos of their incorrect answers;
 - Proportion of participants that found useful to watch the videos of their correct answers;
 - Proportion of participants that found useful to watch the videos of their incorrect answers;
- Questionnaire 2:
 - Differences in answers between groups;
 - Differences in answers between girls in the experimental and in the control group;
 - Differences in answers between boys in the experimental and in the control group;
 - Differences in answers between girls and boys in the experimental group;
 - Differences in answers between girls and boys in the control group.

As most data were collected from online participants, we implemented filter criteria in order to discard those that could potentially not provide serious information. The following filters were established:

- Time filter: participants who solved both tests in less than 9 min. (percentile 5) were eliminated;
- Percentage of correct answers filter: results equal and below 36.11 % were discarded. This percentage corresponds to 13 correct answers (out of 36), which makes up to having less than one third of correct answers.

Answers from participants who selected the “other” option when identifying their gender were also deleted, as they conformed the 3.7 % of the total number of participants and comparisons with the two other genders were not viable.

Results

Feedback effects

Results of the pre- and post-test of the experimental and the control group were compared to establish whether feedback had an effect in the learning outcomes of participants. A Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test showed a not normal distribution of the data in both the pre- ($p = <.001$) and post-test ($p = <.001$), therefore, a Mann & Whitney U-Test was employed. Table 43 shows the results of the comparisons of the mean percentage of correct answers for the experimental and control group.

Table 43*Average percentage of correct answers in the experimental and control group by gender*

	Experimental group						Control group					
	Total		Females		Males		Total		Females		Males	
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S
Pre-test	74.53	14.26	71.24	17.86	76.85	10.65	74.00	15.16	74.79	15.33	73.00	15.07
Post-test	81.64	11.34	81.37	12.30	81.83	10.73	82.19	12.26	82.61	11.67	81.65	13.09
Diff.*	7.11		10.13		4.98		8.19		7.78		8.65	

*Difference of percentages between post-test and pre-test.

From Table 43, it can be determined that students in both groups scored comparably on the pre- and the post- test. We ran a Wilcoxon-Test, which proved that the small variations between the groups are not significant in both cases ($p = 1.00$; $p = .652$). The difference between the percentage of correct answers in the pre-test and in the post-test is however larger in the control group than in the experimental group, yet only just above 1 %. Additionally, the standard deviations were large in both groups.

We contrasted the results of females and males in the experimental and control group. In the case of the females, they score slightly higher in both tests in the control group, though the differences are not significant ($p = .637$; $p = .706$). Males' results in the pre-test are higher in the experimental group, but nearly equal in the post-test, differences being not statistically significant ($p = .78$; $p = .809$). The variation between the percentage of correct answers in the pre- and post- test is, in the case of females, larger in the experimental group by almost 3 % and, in the case of males, larger in the control group, by almost double.

Impact on gender

Results of females and males of the pre- and post-test in both groups have been compared to establish the impact of both conditions on gender, as shown in Table 43.

In the experimental group, males outscore females in the pre-test, yet not significantly

($p = .239$), but the difference in the post-test is almost inexistent ($p = .996$). However, females' improvement between the pre- and post-test is larger than males' by more than 6 %.

In the control group, females score higher than males in both tests, not being significant in both cases ($p = .488$; $p = .971$). The improvement rate is similar in both genders, being that of males' less than 1 % larger than females'.

Feedback effects in participants in the quartile 1

In order to detect if feedback had effects on students' outcomes when they scored equal or less than 66.67 % of correct answers in the pre-test (thus conforming the quartile 1), we compared the results of the experimental and the control group. Table 44 depicts the mean percentage of correct answers for the two groups.

Table 44

Average percentage of correct answers in the experimental and control group by gender

	Experimental group						Control group					
	Total		Females		Males		Total		Females		Males	
	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S	\bar{x}	S
Pre-test	57.26	9.40	53.18	10.16	62.04	62.04	52.78	9.85	54.07	9.96	51.01	9.88
Post-test	75.00	11.89	71.43	9.43	79.17	79.17	73.50	12.80	74.07	11.44	72.73	15.00
Diff.*	17.74		18.25		17.13		20.72		20		21.72	

*Difference of percentages between post-test and pre-test.

Results of both groups, though the experimental group scored higher in both tests, are comparable and not statistically significant ($p = .097$; $p = .711$). The control group, however, improves by almost 3 % more than the experimental group the percentage of correct answers in the post-test than in the pre-test. Standard deviations are also homogeneous between the two groups, however, they are lower in the pre-test.

In regards to the outcomes of females and males, the first score slightly higher in the control

group, though the differences are not significant in both the pre-test ($p = .747$) and the post-test ($p = .715$). The latter, on the other hand, score higher in the experimental group, being the differences significant in the pre-test ($p = .005$), but not in the post-test ($p = .381$). The variations between the post-test and the pre-test are larger for females than males in the experimental group and vice-versa in the control group, however, in both cases they only differ by about 1 %.

Impact on gender in participants in the quartile 1

Outcomes of both genders have been compared within the experimental and control group to analyse the effect of feedback in reducing gender differences, when the participants are situated in the first quartile.

From Table 44, we can observe that in the experimental condition, males score higher than females in both tests, however, differences are only significant in the pre-test ($p = .027$).

As for the control group, females outscore males in the two tests not significantly ($p = .443$; $p = .683$). Both females and males improve more their results from the pre-test to the post-test in the control group, by 1.75 % in the case of females and 4.59 % in the case of males.

Questionnaires

Questionnaire 1. We provided the experimental group with a short questionnaire at the end of the pre-test to learn if they had watched the videos of their correct (Q1) and incorrect (Q2) answers, and how useful they found the videos of their correct (Q3) and incorrect (Q4) answers to solve the rest of the tasks. Table 45 shows the number (n) and percentage (%) of participants per gender and in total that opted for each answer option in each question.

Table 45*Number and percentage of answers per answer option by gender and in total*

		1		2		3		4		5	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Q1	Females	7	20.6	5	14.7	13	38.2	5	14.7	4	11.8
	Males	12	25	14	29.2	13	27.1	4	8.3	5	10.4
	Total	19	23.2	19	23.2	26	31.7	9	11.0	9	11.0
Q2	Females	-	-	-	-	10	29.4	12	35.3	12	35.3
	Males	-	-	-	-	17	35.4	15	31.3	16	33.3
	Total	-	-	-	-	27	15.1	27	15.1	28	15.6
Q3	Females	2	5.9	9	26.5	11	32.4	8	23.5	4	11.8
	Males	8	16.7	13	27.1	14	29.2	8	16.7	5	10.4
	Total	10	12.2	12	26.8	25	30.5	16	19.5	9	11.0
Q4	Females	0	0	2	5.9	3	8.8	21	61.8	8	23.5
	Males	2	4.2	1	2.1	8	16.7	17	35.4	20	41.7
	Total	2	2.4	3	3.7	11	13.4	38	46.3	28	34.1

1: Strongly disagree – 5: Strongly agree

Regarding question 1, most of the participants (46.4 %) affirmed not having watched the videos of their correct answers, as opposed to the 22 % that did. More boys (54.2 %) than girls (35.3 %) claim to not having watched the videos.

Results from participants that selected answer options 1 (strongly disagree) and 2 (disagree) in the question 2 were deleted, as they did not qualify as experimental group participants for not having watched the videos of the incorrect answers. Considering that, the number of answers in the three other options were similar. In the case of each gender, 70.6 % of girls selected the answer options 4 or 5, as opposed to the 64.6 % of boys.

In question 3, results are mixed. 39 % of respondents manifested not finding the videos of the correct answers useful to solve other tasks, while 29.5 % strongly agreed to that. The remaining 30.5 % were more or less in agreement. More boys tended to answer negatively (43.8 %), while girls' answers were more evenly spread.

Answers on question 4 are more consensual: 80.4 % of participants strongly agreed or agreed that watching the videos of their incorrect answers was useful to understand the tasks better.

A higher percentage of girls (85.3 %) than boys (77.1 %) answered positively to this question.

Figure 51 presents the percentage of participants per answer option in each question by gender.

A higher percentage of females answered positively (answer options 4: agree; and 5: strongly agree) or neutral (answer option 3: more or less) to questions 1, 3 and 4. In question 2, more females opted for the answer options 4 and 5, while more males selected option 3.

Figure 51

Answer option selection percentage per gender in each question in the questionnaire 1

Answer options: 1: strongly disagree; 5 strongly agree.

Questionnaire 2. At the end of the post-test in both the experimental and the control group, participants answered a short questionnaire to evaluate their confidence in their performance (Q1), motivation towards the tasks (Q2) and their opinion about the difficulty of the tasks (Q3). Additionally, the experimental group had one more question about the usefulness of the videos to solve the post-test (Q4). Table 46 shows the percentage of participants in the experimental or control group and gender that opted for each answer option in each question.

Table 46

Percentage of answers per answer option by gender and group

		1		2		3		4		5	
		Exp.	Cont.								
Q1	Females	2.9	7.4	2.9	16.7	44.1	35.2	32.4	33.2	17.6	7.4
	Males	2.1	7.0	12.5	9.3	22.9	34.9	50	37.2	12.5	11.6
	Total	2.4	7.2	8.5	13.4	31.7	35.1	42.7	35.1	14.6	9.3
Q2	Females	0.0	7.4	2.9	14.8	29.4	24.1	44.1	29.6	23.5	24.1
	Males	0.0	7.0	6.3	14.0	18.8	25.6	33.3	25.6	41.7	27.9
	Total	0.0	7.2	4.9	14.4	23.2	24.7	37.8	27.8	34.1	25.8
Q3	Females	2.9	1.9	8.8	18.5	58.8	35.2	23.5	35.2	5.9	9.3
	Males	2.1	4.7	12.5	9.3	39.3	51.2	33.3	25.6	12.5	9.3
	Total	2.4	3.1	11.0	14.4	47.6	42.3	29.3	30.9	9.8	9.3
Q4	Females	0.0	-	23.5	-	35.3	-	26.5	-	14.7	-
	Males	2.1	-	20.8	-	33.3	-	29.2	-	14.5	-
	Total	1.2	-	22.0	-	34.1	-	28.0	-	14.6	-

1: Strongly disagree – 5: Strongly agree. Exp.: experimental group; Cont.: control group.

Note: Question 4: “The videos for the first 18 tasks helped me to better understand the other tasks in this quiz”, is only intended for the experimental group.

Comparison between groups. From Table 46, we can infer that participants in the experimental group had higher confidence in their performance than those in the control group, as 57.3 % from the first group marked their answers to the first question with 4 or 5 (agree or strongly agree), in comparison to 44.4 % from the latter. On the contrary, 20.6 % of respondents from the control group answered with strongly disagree or disagree, while the percentage was 10.9 % in the experimental group.

Similarly, a higher percentage of participants in the experimental group (71.9 %) enjoyed solving the tasks than in the control group (53.6 %). While 21.6% of those in the control group did not enjoy the tasks, only 4.9 % of the experimental group affirmed the same feeling.

For the last question, the answers of the two groups seem to be more homogeneous: 39.1 % of partakers in the experimental group claimed to have found the tasks easy for them, as to the 40.2 % in the control group. On the opposite side, 13.4 % of those in the experimental group strongly disagreed or disagreed to this statement, while 17.5 % did in the control group.

Comparison between females and males in the control group. In the control group, males show higher confidence in their performance than females, as 48.8 % of them find themselves good at these tasks, as to 40.6 %. In the same line, more females (24.1 %) than males (16.3 %) disagree or strongly disagree with this statement. However, a similar percentage of participants in both groups claimed to have enjoyed solving the tasks. Regarding the last third question, a higher percentage of females (44.5 %) found the tasks easy, but also a higher percentage of them did not (20.4 %), in comparison to the 34.9 % and 14 % of males.

To throw a clearer image of the results shown in Table 46, data of females and males in the control group are presented in Figure 52. A higher percentage of males in the control group answered neutrally or positively (answer options 3, 4 and 5) to the three questions of the questionnaire, although in question 2 the differences between females and males is nearly inexistent.

Figure 52

Answer option selection percentage per gender in each question in the control group

Answer options: 1: strongly disagree; 5 strongly agree.

Comparison between females and males in the experimental group. In the experimental group, the differences between females' and males' confidence in their performance is larger than in the control group, having agreed or strongly agreed 50 % females to the question and 62.5 % of the males. More males than females however showed disagreement. 75 % of males and 67.6 % of females enjoyed solving the tasks, while 6.3 % of the first and 2.9 % of the latter did not. Similarly, more males consider the tasks easy. Finally, a comparable percentage of females (41.2 %) and males (43.7 %) agreed to finding the videos useful to solve the tasks in the post-test.

Figure 53 shows the data of females and males in the experimental group presented in Table 46. Females in the experimental group tend to opt for the answer options 3, 4 and 5 in a higher proportion than males. Only in question 4, are males' responses slightly more positive than females'.

Figure 53

Answer option selection percentage per gender in each question in the experimental group

Answer options: 1: strongly disagree; 5 strongly agree.

Comparison between genders in the control and the experimental group. From the data shown in Table 46 we can establish that a higher percentage of both girls and boys in the experimental group have higher confidence in their performance and enjoyed solving the tasks than in the control group. However, tables are turned in the third question, as more participants in both genders in the control group found them easy.

Data from Table 46 of males in the experimental and in the control group are presented in Figure 54. A higher percentage of males in the experimental group selected the neutral or positive answer option for questions 1 and 2. However, this proportion is almost identical in question 3.

Figure 54

Males' answer option selection percentage per group in each question

Answer options: 1: strongly disagree; 5 strongly agree.

Figure 55 represents the data of females in the experimental and in the control group shown in Table 46. Females in the experimental group tend to answer more neutrally and positively than females in the control group, especially in questions 1 and 2. However, a higher percentage of females in the control group answer with “agree” or “strongly agree” to question 3.

Figure 55

Females' answer option selection percentage per group in each question

Answer options: 1: strongly disagree; 5 strongly agree.

Discussion

In this study, an experiment was conducted to investigate the effects of elaborated feedback in the form of animated images (videos) on students' learning outcomes in computer-based spatial thinking tasks. The following hypothesis were tested:

H1: Receiving feedback improves students' learning outcomes in online spatial thinking tasks.

H1.2: Low-skilled students benefit more than high-skilled students from feedback.

H1.3: Girls benefit more from the feedback condition, while boys benefit more from the no-feedback condition.

H2: Students who receive feedback show more confidence in their performance and perceive tasks as less difficult.

H2.1: Boys show more confidence in their performance and perceived difficulty of the tasks when not receiving feedback.

H2.2: When receiving feedback, girls gain more confidence in their performance and perceive tasks as less difficult than boys who receive feedback.

Online Austrian participants randomly solved the control or the experimental test, while students in the Dutch classrooms solved the experimental test. Participants in the experimental group answered a short questionnaire after the pre-test and both the experimental and the control group answered a questionnaire after the post-test. The contents of the tests were identical for both groups, except for the feedback in the pre-test, which was only provided to the experimental group. The effects of receiving KCR+EF (experimental group) or no-feedback (control group) were compared.

Regarding feedback effects, it was expected that learners in the experimental group would score significantly higher on the post-test than the control group (Hypothesis 1). A Mann & Whitney U Test showed that the differences between the experimental and the control group in the post-test were not significant, therefore, Hypothesis 1 was rejected. Focusing only on the participants with low-skills (characterized by pre-test scores equal or less than 66.67, i.e., first quartile), the same results were found. In both cases, participants in the control group improve further from the pre-test to the post-tests than participants in the experimental group. These results are in line with various studies on computer-based assessments (e.g. Maier et al., 2016; van der Kleij et al., 2012), which show that feedback in computer-based assessments does not necessarily lead to improved learning outcomes. However, some researchers have found positive effects (e.g. Attali & van der Kleij, 2017; Faber et al., 2017). The causes for these conflicting results can be explained by several variables that have shown a major impact on feedback effects, such as students' characteristics (motivation, self-regulation, initial knowledge or skills); task characteristics (low or high order learning tasks); and feedback characteristics (timing, type and complexity) (Attali & van der Kleij, 2017; Faber et al., 2017; Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Shute, 2008; Van der Kleij et al., 2015). Additionally, in this context, as feedback-videos were specific for each task, they do not appear to have had a far transfer effect between tasks. Therefore, although the videos were meant to help with the development of appropriate strategies for solving different tasks of the same area, they did not achieve this goal.

Low-skilled participants, show a larger improvement between the pre-test and the post-test in both the experimental and the control group in comparison to the whole sample, which confirms Hypothesis 1.1. This a common observation in educational research, that beginners or low-skilled individuals tend to show more rapid improvement with practice compared to those who are already highly skilled in a particular area, which is known as the learning curve (Mazur & Hastie, 1978). As for the differences between the experimental groups, previous research has

found that low-achieving students benefit more from elaborated feedback than high-ability students (Shute, 2008).

Concerning the effects of feedback in both genders, we have found that the differences in percentage of correct answers between females and males are not significant in both conditions. As for the variation rate between the pre- and post-test results between genders, in the experimental group, females improve more than males, and in the control group males improve more than females, which confirms hypothesis 1.2. When comparing both the experimental and control groups (within gender), females undergo a larger improvement in the experimental group, whereas males do in the control group. These results are consistent in the first quartile, except the variation rate of girls being slightly larger in the control group than in the experimental group. This is in conformity with Narciss et al. (2014), who studied different factors that could influence the effectiveness of adaptive feedback in computer-based educational systems in relation to fractions, and concluded that girls benefited more from practicing with feedback than boys in all feedback conditions. A plausible explanation is the gender difference in receptivity to feedback; females tend to react more positively to feedback than males and are more likely to use it (Johnson & Helgeson, 2002; Schleicher et al., 2010). Even though no significant effects were found between the feedback and no-feedback condition, students' answers to the questionnaires shed more light on the topic. As for the first questionnaire, only the experimental group received it, as it was intended to learn whether they had watched the feedback-videos of their correct and incorrect answers and how useful they found them directly after the pre-test. Females showed more disposition to watch the feedback-videos, both of their right and wrong answers. The difference between the percentage of females and males watching the videos of their correct answers is considerably large. Moreover, they also seem to perceive the feedback-videos more helpful than males to understand the tasks and solve other tasks. This can again be explained by females being more open to receiving feedback than males and to further apply it (Johnson & Helgeson, 2002; Schleicher et al., 2010).

In the case of the second questionnaire, it was answered by all participants at the end of the post-test and included for questions about (1) their confidence in their performance; (2) their enjoyment solving the tasks; (3) the difficulty of the tasks. A fourth question about (4) whether they think the videos to the first 18 tasks helped them to better understand the other tasks was only provided to the experimental group. Participants in the experimental group answer more positively to these questions, showing a higher confidence, more enjoyment and a lower difficulty perception of the tasks than participants in the control group. Hypothesis 2 was therefore confirmed. This contrasts with prior research on effects of feedback and confidence in mental rotation tasks, which found no effect of interaction between gender and confidence when receiving feedback (Rahe et al., 2019).

In regards to gender, in the control group, males tend to perceive their performance more positively than females and to find the tasks easy for them, which confirms Hypothesis 2.1. However, both seem to enjoy working with the tasks equally. In the experimental group, on the other hand, results are reversed, being a higher percentage of females who consider themselves “good” at these types of tasks and finding them easy. Hypothesis 2.2 was confirmed by this. Nonetheless, the differences between the two genders are minor and do not lead to any further conclusions. Females’ and males’ answers to the usefulness of the feedback-videos are rather similar. Looking into each gender, females in the experimental group have higher confidence in their performance than those in the control group, and a higher proportion enjoyed the tasks and considered them easy. Males do not show so much difference between the experimental and the control group as females, but they also displayed higher confidence and enjoyed the tasks more. However, answers on the difficulty of the tasks are similar. The differences might be explained by the same arguments given above, as females response to feedback is more positive than males (Johnson & Helgeson, 2002; Schleicher et al., 2010).

Implications

This study provides new insights on the effects of feedback in computer-based assessments and its interaction with gender in the field of spatial thinking. Although no significant effects of feedback in students' learning outcomes were found, feedback does have influence on students' confidence and enjoyment, particularly in girls.

Reasons for this lack of positive effects might be explained by the design of the study. First, the tasks used were very varied, as we included two tasks per area. This might have caused that (1) participants did not have enough room for practicing each type of task; and that (2) even if feedback was helpful for some kind of area, it did not show in the final results. Further research should focus on examining the effects of feedback in each area of spatial thinking trained in the platform separately, especially those with lower outcomes (mental rotation and spatial relations).

This as major implications in the spatial thinking field, as feedback can be a tool to encourage girls' participation in these kinds of tasks. Regarding the limitations of this study, first, the pre- and post- test were administered without a pause between each other, which could cause that the participants were already fatigued to solve the post-test and to only observe short-term effects of the feedback. Second, some tasks appeared to be more difficult than others, which might have had an influence on results. Third, as most students participated online, we could not ensure that they watched the feedback-videos and if they did properly. In future research, it is recommended to implement the study in a longer period, with more time between pre- and post-test, and possibly with more post-test at later points to see if there are long-term effects. Moreover, a qualitative study to better understand students' perception of this type of feedback would be convenient to shed more light on its effect. Finally, more research on the impact of feedback in gender is needed to clarify whether it can be an instrument to increase girls' confidence when dealing with spatial related tasks and interest for spatial activities.

General Conclusions

This dissertation addressed the topic of spatial skills, focusing on the development of tasks and their evaluation for the online platform RIF, gender differences in mental rotation, and the effect of feedback in students' outcomes in said platform. In the first section, significant literature relevant to spatial thinking, mental rotation, and formative feedback was reviewed. The second section dealt with the empirical studies in four different chapters. In chapter 4, the development and evaluation of tasks for the RIF platform was described, focusing on the creation and assessment of numerous tasks for primary school students for the area *visualization*. In addition, the inclusion of a color-blindness check and the translation of the platform into Spanish was addressed as a way to enhance the accessibility of the platform. Chapter 5 details the evaluation of participants' performance in the RIF platform tasks. Results of 41664 participants were analysed to assess their performance in each area of spatial thinking trained in the platform. Chapter 6 focuses on exploring the effects of using different types of representations in mental rotation tasks to improve students' outcomes and reduce gender differences. Chapter 7 reports the results of including feedback in the RIF platform as a tool to enhance the learning process in an online-based environment.

Following, we present the general conclusions of the thesis:

Conclusions of Chapter 4: Development and Evaluation of Tasks

- Students enjoyed solving the visualization tasks and found them motivating.
- Results improve with practice. Participants need less time to solve the tasks each time.
- Some changes and adaptations needed to be made (i.e., rephrasing of questions, increasing the number of tasks per task group, elimination of some tasks to improve the internal consistency of the task groups).

Conclusions of Chapter 5: Evaluation of the RIF Platform

- The first four areas of spatial thinking trained in RIF (spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation) show lower results than the last five (visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combination), as expected due to their difficulty level.
- Outcomes of participants of RIF tend to improve with age, both males and females reaching their peak at the ages of 19-21. From that age onward, results tend to lower.

Regarding gender differences in performance:

- From ages 7 to 9 there are no significant gender differences in any of the last 5 areas.
- From 10 to 12, boys significantly outscore girls in spatial visualization, spatial relations and mental rotation, while girls do in visualization, form constancy and object combination.
- From 13 to 15, boys significantly outscore girls in spatial visualization, spatial relations, mental rotation and spatial orientation.
- From 16 to 18, boys significantly outscore girls in spatial visualization, mental rotation and spatial orientation.
- From 19 to 21, girls outscore boys in all the areas and significantly in spatial visualization.
- From +21, girls outscore boys in all the areas and significantly in spatial relations and spatial orientation.
- Even though the variation between females' and males' performance is in occasions statistically significant, the difference in percentage of correct answers is, in all cases except for mental rotation, below 4 %.

- Mental rotation is the area with the largest gender differences. From ages 10 to 16, the difference between the percentage of correct answers between girls and boys (favouring boys) is above 6 % and above 9 % in the ages 16 to 18.

Conclusions of Chapter 6: Effects of Using Different Types of Representations in Mental Rotation Tasks

- Practicing with more realistic types of representations led to better results of both females and males. Results are improved in general with the grey-shaded and the rendered representations in comparison to the classic.
- Figures that provide unnecessary information (colored) might cause a cognitive-load and/or distract students from the task.
- Though males consistently outscore females in the four types of representations, differences are only significant in the ages between 13 and 16. In the ages 17 to 18 only in the rendered and classic versions.
- Gender differences are reduced in all age groups with the grey-shaded version. This is due to boys either not improving, improving less than girls or worsening their results. Although both females and males in all age groups (except 17 to 18) score higher with the rendered representations, larger differences have been found from 13 to 18 years old, as males tend to improve their results more than females.
- MRT-test-like tasks are particularly sensitive to using more realistic representations. Excluding the last age group, all groups benefit considerably from the rendered representations. Females seem to benefit more than males from the more realistic types of representation, specially 15-to-16-year-olds.
- Gender differences are reduced with the rendered representations in ages from 13 to 16 and reversed in ages from 10 to 12.

Conclusions of Chapter 7: The Impact of Animated Feedback in Spatial Thinking

Training Using the RIF Platform

- There were no significant differences between the experimental and the control group post-test.
- Low-skilled participants show a larger improvement between the pre- and the post-test in both the experimental and the control group in comparison to the whole sample.
- Differences between the rate of correct answers of females and males in both the experimental and the control group are not significant.
- Females showed more disposition to watch the feedback videos than males, both for their right and wrong answers. They also seem to perceive feedback as more helpful than males.
- Participants in the experimental group answered more positively than those in the control group to the questions related to their confidence in their responses, enjoyment and difficulty perception of the tasks.
- Males in the control group tend to perceive their performance more positively than females and to find the tasks easier. Results are reversed in the experimental group.
- Females in the experimental group show more confidence and enjoyment than those in the control group and found the tasks easier, while males do not show so many differences between groups.

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List of tables

Table 1. *Factors of spatial ability according to Buckley and colleagues (Buckley et al., 2018)*

Table 2. *Types of tasks of the first five basic practices of spatial thinking included in the RIF 3.0 platform*

Table 3. *Questions included in the questionnaire for students*

Table 4. *Questions included in the questionnaire for teachers*

Table 5. *Average percentage of correct answers, average time and Cronbach's alpha by task group*

Table 6. *Average percentage of correct answers and time by task group*

Table 7. *Statistical significance of difference of average percentage of correct answers and time between task groups*

Table 8. *Means and std. deviation of answers of the Likert-scale questions in the four questionnaires for learners*

Table 9. *Means and std. deviation of answers of the Likert-scale questions in the four questionnaires for teachers*

Table 10. *Examples of modifications of questions after teachers' feedback*

Table 11. *Sample size and average age of participants by gender in each task group*

Table 12. *Average percentage of correct answers and time by task group*

Table 13. *Cronbach's alpha of each task group and difficulty of tasks*

Table 14. *Number of participants in total, per age group and gender.*

Table 15. *Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 7 to 9 years old)*

Table 16. *Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 10 to 12 years old)*

Table 17. *Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender, difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 13 to 15 years old)*

Table 18. *Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender; difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 16 to 18 years old)*

Table 19. *Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender; difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group 19 to 21 years old)*

Table 20. *Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender; difference between females and males and its level of significance (age group over 21 years old)*

Table 21. *Average percentage of correct answers and std. deviation in each area per gender; difference between females and males and its level of significance (total number of participants)*

Table 22. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender*

Table 23. *Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version*

Table 24. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender*

Table 25. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type I*

Table 26. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender*

Table 27. *Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version*

Table 28. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender*

Table 29. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type I*

Table 30. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender*

Table 31. *Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version*

Table 32. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender*

Table 33. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type I*

Table 34. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender*

Table 35. *Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version*

Table 36. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender*

Table 37. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type 1*

Table 38. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender*

Table 39. *Statistical significance of the difference between the average percentages of correct answers in the types of representation in comparison to the classic version*

Table 40. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of task per gender*

Table 41. *Average percentage of correct answer in each type of representation per gender in task type 1*

Table 42. *Questions in the pre- and post- test questionnaires*

Table 43. *Average percentage of correct answers in the experimental and control group by gender*

Table 44. *Average percentage of correct answers in the experimental and control group by gender*

Table 45. *Number and percentage of answers per answer option by gender and in total*

Table 46. *Percentage of answers per answer option by gender and group*

List of Figures

Figure 1. *The four pairs of strategies for the solution of spatial ability tasks (Maresch, 2014, pp. 128)*

Figure 2. *2 x 2 classification of spatial skills (Newcombe, 2020)*

Figure 3. *The eight basic practices of spatial thinking (Maresch, 2020)*

Figure 4. *Materials for the visual/paper condition (left) and for the visual/object and haptic/object condition (right) (Robert & Chevrier, 2003)*

Figure 5. *Photograph version of mental rotation stimuli (Fisher et al., 2018)*

Figure 6. *Classic model, color block model and realistic model used by Daxinger and Maresch (2018)*

Figure 7. *Wire model, color model and model with concealed edges used by Schilchegger and Maresch (2018)*

Figure 8. *Percentage of yes/no answers to “I would like to have solved more tasks”*

Figure 9. *Percentage of answers to “How many tasks would you like to have solved?”*

Figure 10. *Plate number 2 in the Ishihara’s Tests for Color Blindness Concise edition (Ishihara, 1982)*

Figure 11. *Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 7 to 9*

Figure 12. *Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 10 to 12*

Figure 13. *Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 13 to 15*

Figure 14. *Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 16 to 18*

Figure 15. *Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from ages 19 to 21*

Figure 16. *Average percentage of correct answers in each area per gender from 21 years old*

Figure 17. *Average percentage of correct answers in SV, SR, MR and SO per gender from all participants*

Figure 18. *Average percentage of correct answers in VI, FC, PS, TS and OC per gender from all participants*

Figure 19. *Females’ average percentage of correct answers in each area per age group*

Figure 20. *Males’ average percentage of correct answers in each area per age group*

Figure 21. *Average percentage of correct answers in the spatial visualization area per age group by gender*

Figure 22. *Average percentage of correct answers in the spatial relations area per age group by gender*

Figure 23. *Average percentage of correct answers in the mental rotation area per age group by gender*

Figure 24. *Average percentage of correct answers in the spatial orientation area per age group by gender*

Figure 25. *Average percentage of correct answers in the visualization area per age group by gender*

Figure 26. *Average percentage of correct answers in the form constancy area per age group by gender*

Figure 27. *Average percentage of correct answers in the position in space area per age group by gender*

Figure 28. *Average percentage of correct answers in the transformation in space area per age group by gender*

Figure 29. *Average percentage of correct answers in the object combination area per age group by gender*

Figure 30. *The four types of representation used in the study*

Figure 31. *Task type 1*

Figure 32. *Task type 2*

Figure 33. *Task type 3*

Figure 34. *Task type 4*

Figure 35. *Task type 5*

Figure 36. *Question about preference for type of representation*

Figure 37. *Females' average percentage of correct answers per type of representation per age group*

Figure 38. *Males' average percentage of correct answers per type of representation per age group*

Figure 39. *Females' average percentage of correct answers per type of task per age group*

Figure 40. *Males' average percentage of correct answers per type of task per age group*

Figure 41. *Females' average percentage of correct answers per type of representation per age group in the task type 1*

Figure 42. *Males' average percentage of correct answers per type of representation per age group in the task type 1*

Figure 43. *Percentage of female participants in each age group who selected each type of representation*

Figure 44. *Percentage of male participants in each age group who selected each type of representation*

Figure 45. *Correlation between females' average percentage of correct answers in the assessment instrument and preference for type of representation*

Figure 46. *Correlation between males' average percentage of correct answers in the assessment instrument and preference for type of representation*

Figure 47. *Example of feedback input for correct answers in the experimental pre-test*

Figure 48. *Example of feedback input for incorrect answers in the experimental pre-test*

Figure 49. *Example of feedback input in the post-test*

Figure 50. *Example of development of feedback videos*

Figure 51. *Answer option selection percentage per gender in each question in the questionnaire 1*

Figure 52. *Answer option selection percentage per gender in each question in the control group*

Figure 53. *Answer option selection percentage per gender in each question in the experimental group*

Figure 54. *Males' answer option selection percentage per group in each question*

Figure 55. *Females' answer option selection percentage per group in each question*

Annexes

Annex 1

Questionnaire for students for the first external evaluation of the tasks

26/2/24, 9:32 Uni Salzburg UmfrageTool - Cuestionario para alumnos

Cuestionario para alumnos

Querida/o alumna/o,

después de hacer las actividades, me gustaría saber tu opinión sobre ellas. Solo tienes que ser sincera/o. Tus respuestas serán muy útiles.

¡Muchas gracias! 🙏

Hay 14 preguntas en la encuesta.

Información sobre mí

Nombre y apellidos: *

Por favor, escriba su respuesta aquí:

Edad: *

Sólo se pueden introducir números en este campo.
Por favor, escriba su respuesta aquí:

•

Fecha de nacimiento: *

Por favor, introduzca una fecha:

Género: *

Seleccione una de las siguientes opciones
Por favor seleccione **sólo una** de las siguientes opciones:

- Femenino
- Masculino
- Diverso
- Prefiero no decirlo

Curso *

Seleccione una de las siguientes opciones
Por favor seleccione **sólo una** de las siguientes opciones:

- 5º
- 6º

Código de clase: *

Seleccione una de las siguientes opciones
Por favor seleccione **sólo una** de las siguientes opciones:

- A
- B
- C
- D

Código individual: *

Por favor, escriba su respuesta aquí:

Comentarios generales sobre las actividades (1)

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*

Por favor, seleccione la respuesta apropiada para cada concepto:

	No estoy nada de acuerdo	No estoy de acuerdo	Más o menos	Estoy de acuerdo	Estoy totalmente de acuerdo
<p>He entendido bien las actividades. Las actividades son interesantes. Las actividades son divertidas.</p>					

Comentarios generales sobre las actividades (2)

*

Por favor, seleccione la respuesta apropiada para cada concepto:

	Si	No
Me gustaría haber hecho más actividades.		

¿Cuántas más? *

Sólo conteste esta pregunta si se cumplen las siguientes condiciones:

La respuesta fue 'Si' en la pregunta '9 [a2]' ((Me gustaría haber hecho más actividades.))

Seleccione una de las siguientes opciones

Por favor seleccione **sólo una** de las siguientes opciones:

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- Más de 5

Comentarios generales sobre las actividades (3)

*

Por favor, seleccione la respuesta apropiada para cada concepto:

	No estoy nada de acuerdo	No estoy de acuerdo	Más o menos	Estoy de acuerdo	Estoy totalmente de acuerdo
<p>No podía concentrarme bien en las últimas actividades. Las actividades eran demasiado fáciles para mí. Podía concentrarme bien en las últimas actividades. Las actividades eran muy difíciles para mí. Me gustaría hacer estas actividades más a menudo. La dificultad de las actividades estaba bien para mí.</p>					

Dispositivo digital utilizado

*

Por favor, seleccione la respuesta apropiada para cada concepto:

	Ordenador	Tableta	Móvil	Otro
¿Qué dispositivo has utilizado?				

¿Cuál?

Sólo conteste esta pregunta si se cumplen las siguientes condiciones:

La respuesta fue 'Otro' en la pregunta '12 [a10]' ((¿Qué dispositivo has utilizado?))

Por favor, escriba su respuesta aquí:

¿Quieres decirnos algo más sobre las actividades?

Escribe aquí qué te han parecido las actividades, qué podríamos hacer mejor y cualquier otra cosa relacionada que se te ocurra. *

Por favor, escriba su respuesta aquí:

¡Muchas gracias por participar!
04.05.2022 - 08:06

Enviar su encuesta.
Gracias por completar esta encuesta.

Annex 2

Questionnaire for teachers for the first external evaluation of the tasks

27/2/24, 9:49 Uni Salzburg UmfrageTool - Cuestionario para docentes

Cuestionario para docentes

In dieser Umfrage sind 7 Fragen enthalten.

Proporcione el curso y código de clase:

Curso: *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- 5º
- 6º

Código clase: *

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- A
- B
- C
- D

Comentarios generales sobre las actividades

*

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffende Antwort für jeden Punkt aus:

	Muy en desacuerdo	En desacuerdo	Más o menos	De acuerdo	Muy de acuerdo
--	------------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------	-------------------	---------------------------

Las actividades son adecuadas para la edad de mis alumnos/as.

Las actividades logran captar y mantener el interés de mis alumnos/as.

Los enunciados eran claros y fáciles de entender.

Me ha dado la impresión de que mis alumnos/as pudieron mantener su concentración hasta la última actividad.

*

Bitte wählen Sie die zutreffende Antwort für jeden Punkt aus:

	Había muy pocas actividades.	El número de actividades era adecuado.	Había demasiadas actividades.
--	-------------------------------------	---	--------------------------------------

Sabiendo que cada test consta de 25 actividades y teniendo en cuenta las capacidades

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Había muy pocas actividades.

El número de actividades era adecuado.

Había demasiadas actividades.

habituales de concentración de su alumnado: ¿cree que es una cantidad adecuada?

¿Cuántas cree que deberían tener?

*

Bitte wählen Sie nur eine der folgenden Antworten aus:

- Menos de 15
-
-
-
-

Comentarios específicos sobre las actividades

***Aunque no es necesario rellenar todos los campos, agradecemos su valoración escrupulosa del mayor número posible.**

Grado de dificultad	Figuras bien visibles y comprensibles	Comprensibilidad del texto
(1 fácil - 2 medio - 3 difícil)	(1 bien - 2 medio - 3 difícil)	(1 fácil - 2 medio - 3 difícil)

Actividad 1

Actividad 2

Actividad 3

Actividad 4

Actividad 5

Actividad 6

Actividad 7

Actividad 8

Actividad 9

Grado de dificultad	Figuras bien visibles y comprensibles	Comprensibilidad del texto
(1 fácil - 2 medio - 3 difícil)	(1 bien - 2 medio - 3 difícil)	(1 fácil - 2 medio - 3 difícil)

Actividad 10

Actividad 11

Actividad 12

Actividad 13

Actividad 14

Actividad 15

Actividad 16

Actividad 17

Actividad 18

Actividad 19

Actividad 20

Actividad 21

Actividad 22

Actividad 23

Actividad 24

Actividad 25

Aquí puede darnos su opinión individual sobre las actividades

No dude en proporcionar más comentarios sobre las actividades. *

Bitte geben Sie Ihre Antwort hier ein:

04.05.2022 – 08:05

Übermittlung Ihres ausgefüllten Fragebogens:
Vielen Dank für die Beantwortung des Fragebogens.

Annex 3

Table of color-based tasks in RIF

Area	Group of task	Tasks
Visualization	1	7,11
	2	8
	4	11
	5	18,29
	6	19,30
	Transformation in space	1
2		2,3,5,13,20
3		2,3,5,11,12,19
4		1,2,7,17
5		1,2,3,4,12,28
6		8,10,11,13,14,20
Spatial Visualization	1	2,5
	2	2,4
	3	2,5
	4	2,3,4,5
	5	2,5,6,8,10
	6	3,4,5,8,9,10
Spatial Relations	1	14,15,16,17,18,22
	2	14,15,16,18
	3	14,15,16,17,18,22
	4	14,15,16,18,22
	5	28,29,30,31,32,33,35,36,42,43,44
	6	26,27,28,29,30,31,32,34,35,36,43,44
Spatial Orientation	1	6,8
	2	6,8
	3	6
	4	6
	5	11,13,17
	6	11,12

Annex 4

Templates of the color-blind check (Ishihara, 1982)

Template 1

Template 2

Template 3

Template 4

Template 5

Template 6

Template 7

Template 8

Template 9

Template 10

Template 11

Template 12

Template 13

Template 14

Annex 5

Task group for the study on types of representations in mental rotation tasks

Introductory slide

Mentale Rotation

Hier warten 28 Aufgaben auf dich.
Für jede richtig gelöste Aufgabe erhältst du einen Punkt.

Viel Erfolg!

www.adi3d.at/rif30 | RIF 3.0 ist ein Kooperationsprojekt der ADI Geometrie, der Universität Salzburg und der Europäischen Union.

Information about me - slide

Über mich

Gib dein Alter an Jahre

Gib dein Geburtsdatum an

Gib dein Geschlecht an

Task 1

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 2

Das rechts stehende Bild zeigt den vorgegebenen Würfel in einer anderen Position. Hake an, ob um die x-, y- oder z-Achse um 90° gedreht wurde.

x

y

z

Task 3

Der Würfelteil wurde aus der Ausgangslage um die y-Achse gedreht.

Klicke auf das richtige Bild.

Task 4

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 5

Um welche Koordinatenachse wurde der Würfel einmalig gedreht?
Klicke das richtige Kästchen an.

x

y

z

keine der Achsen

Task 6

Die Zeichnungen stellen Holzwürfel dar, bei denen mehrere Ecken ausgefräst wurden.
Nur zwei dieser Würfel sind identisch. Welche sind dies? Klicke die Bilder an.
Hinweis: Verdeckte Würfecken sind nicht ausgefräst.

Task 7

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 8

Das rechts stehende Bild zeigt den vorgegebenen Würfel in einer anderen Position. Hake an, ob um die x-, y- oder z-Achse um 90° gedreht wurde.

x

y

z

Task 9

Der Würfelteil wurde aus der Ausgangslage um die z-Achse gedreht.

Klicke auf das richtige Bild.

Ausgangslage

Drehachsen

Task 10

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 11

Um welche Koordinatenachse wurde der Würfel einmalig gedreht?
Klicke das richtige Kästchen an.

x

y

z

keine der Achsen

Task 12

Die Zeichnungen stellen Holzwürfel dar, bei denen **drei** Ecken ausgefräst wurden.
Nur zwei dieser Würfel sind identisch. Welche sind dies? Klicke die Bilder an.
Hinweis: Verdeckte Würfecken können ausgefräst sein.

Task 13

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 14

Das rechts stehende Bild zeigt den vorgegebenen Würfel in einer anderen Position. Hake an, ob um die x-, y- oder z-Achse um 90° gedreht wurde.

x

y

z

Task 15

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 16

Der Würfelteil wurde aus der Ausgangslage um die x-Achse gedreht.

Klicke auf das richtige Bild.

Ausgangslage

Drehachsen

Task 17

Um welche Koordinatenachse wurde der Würfel einmalig gedreht?
Klicke das richtige Kästchen an.

x

y

z

keine der Achsen

Task 18

Du siehst drei Bilder
derselben Würfelschlange
und ein Bild einer anderen
Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere
Würfelschlange an.

Task 19

Das rechts stehende Bild zeigt den vorgegebenen Würfel in einer anderen Position. Hake an, ob um die x-, y- oder z-Achse um 90° gedreht wurde.

x

y

z

Task 20

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 21

Die Zeichnungen stellen Holzwürfel dar, bei denen mehrere Ecken ausgefräst wurden.
Nur zwei dieser Würfel sind identisch. Welche sind dies? Klicke die Bilder an.
Hinweis: Verdeckte Würfecken sind nicht ausgefräst.

Task 22

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 23

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.
Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 24

Der Würfelteil wurde aus der Ausgangslage um die y-Achse gedreht.

Klicke auf das richtige Bild.

Ausgangslage

Drehachsen

Task 25

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 26

Die Zeichnungen stellen Holzwürfel dar, bei denen jeweils drei Ecken ausgefräst wurden. Nur zwei dieser Würfel sind identisch. Welche sind dies? Klicke die Bilder an.

Task 27

Du siehst drei Bilder derselben Würfelschlange und ein Bild einer anderen Würfelschlange.

Klicke diese andere Würfelschlange an.

Task 28

Um welche Koordinatenachse wurde der Würfel einmalig gedreht?
Klicke das richtige Kästchen an.

x

y

z

keine der Achsen

Annex 6

Questionnaire for the control group in the feedback study

Answer these questions:					
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	More or less	Agree	Strongly Agree
I'm pretty good at this kind of task.	<input type="radio"/>				
I enjoyed solving these tasks.	<input type="radio"/>				
The tasks were easy for me.	<input type="radio"/>				
I had problems understanding the tasks or the questions.	<input type="radio"/>				

Annex 7

Questionnaire 1 for the experimental group in the feedback study

Answer these questions:					
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	More or less	Agree	Strongly Agree
I watched all the videos for my correct answers.	<input type="radio"/>				
I watched all the videos for my wrong answers.	<input type="radio"/>				
The videos of my correct answers were useful to solve other tasks.	<input type="radio"/>				
The videos of my wrong answers were useful to understand the tasks better.	<input type="radio"/>				

Annex 8

Questionnaire 1 for the experimental group in the feedback study

Answer these questions:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	More or less	Agree	Strongly Agree
I'm pretty good at this kind of tasks.	<input type="radio"/>				
The videos for the first 18 tasks helped me to better understand the other tasks in this quiz.	<input type="radio"/>				
I enjoyed solving these tasks.	<input type="radio"/>				
The tasks were easy for me.	<input type="radio"/>				
I had problems understanding the tasks or the questions.	<input type="radio"/>				

Annex 9

Task group for the feedback study

Introductory slide

Spatial Thinking Tasks
CG

Here are 36 tasks to be solved.
You get one point for each correctly solved task.

Good luck!

University of Salzburg

Introductory about me - slide

About me

Introduce your age years

Select your gender

Select your type of school

Select your grade

What is your country of origin?

How long time have you been speaking English? years

Task 1

The pattern shown here will be colored and the letter at the top right is then created.

Click on exactly that side surface which needs to be colored **purple** after folding.

Task 2

One of the four objects together with the given object results in a complete cube.
Click on the corresponding box.

The given Object	Object 1	Object 2	Object 3	Object 4

Object 1 Object 2 Object 3 Object 4

Task 3

You are looking at three figures of exactly the same series of cubes and at one figure of a different series of cubes.

Click on the figure with the different series of cubes.

Task 4

Which piece of the figure is missing? Click on the right answer.

Task 5

Look at the shape that is on the left.
Now look at the figure on the right and spot where the same shape appears. Click on all those four spots.

Task 6

The **red** car wants to drive out of the parking lot, but the way is blocked. Click on the car that has to be moved **first**, so that the red car can finally get a clear path.

Task 7

Anne is looking for the right key for her toy box. Which key fits in the lock? Drag the right key to the keyhole.

Task 8

Task 9

Task 10

The following pattern of a cube will be folded.

Click on that side surface which is parallel to the blue side surface after folding.

Task 11

The object made of cubic elements was colored in green. The bottom side is left unpainted.

Count all of the visible cubes which include exactly **two sides** colored in green.

State the quantity:

Task 12

All of the cuboids have the same dimensions: 4 x 2 x 1

Is it true that the blue cuboid touches the yellow one?

Yes

No

Task 13

The drawings depict wooden cubes of which three corners in all cases have been milled out. Only two of these cubes are identical. Which ones? Click on the correct images.

Task 14

Which of the figures 1 to 5 is missing in the box at the bottom right?
Drag the correct one into the box with the question mark.

1.

2.

3.

4.

5.

Task 15

Click on the correct reverse shadow of the tree.

Task 16

You see here a figure made of wooden pieces. Is it symmetrical?

Yes

No

Task 17

Sandra wants to recreate her brother's construction. What objects does Sandra have to put together for this? Click on each of the pieces she needs.

Task 18

A tabletop was photographed from the corners A, B, C and D.

Click on the photo that was taken from corner A.

Task 19

The square is folded once. Some parts are removed with a pair of scissors. After unfolding, one of the four illustrated figures emerges. Which is the correct one? Click on it.

That's the way how the paper is folded and then cut.

After unfolding?

Task 20

David looks at a group of cubes.
Which cube is - from his viewpoint - to the right of the given cube (mind the viewpoint direction)?
Assign the images on the left side to the correct images.

Task 21

These two figures show the same cube from a different angle.
Click on the label of the vertex that will be in the coloured box.

- A B D H

Task 22

Which of the figures 1 to 5 is missing in the box at the bottom right?
Drag the correct one into the box with the question mark.

1.

2.

3.

4.

5.

Task 23

Look at the image on the right. That is part of the big picture below.
Spot that part on the big picture and click on it.

Task 24

The left figure is mirrored at the middle thick line.
Is the mirrored figure drawn correctly?

Yes No

Task 25

Patricia has created the tangram in the image.
Click on the gap in the tangram where the green piece fits.

Task 26

Look at the robots in the box. Which picture is the same? Click on it.

Task 27

Click on the figure that matches the following description:

The strawberry is **behind** the tree.

Task 28

The figure on the right shows nine cars in a parking area. Each car is marked with a letter.

Click on the car that is marked with the letter **B** on the right in the image below.

Task 29

Imagine how the shown patterned net of a cube is folded and glued onto the white cube standing on it. Decide what the result must look like.

A
 A

B
 B

C
 C

D
 D

Task 30

These two figures show the same cube from different angles.

Click on the spheres on the right that include the vertices C and H of the rotated position.

Task 31

Which bee is on the right path to the beehive? Click on it.

Task 34

Here you can see a puzzle with two gaps.
Click on the gap where the piece on the left fits.

Task 35

Left picture: Farmer Hans is at work and has a branch with green leaves in his hand.

Right picture: Farmer Hans turns to the animals and feeds the green stuff.

In which hand was Farmer Hans holding the branch before feeding the animals?
Click on the correct arm in the right figure.

